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Executive Summary

Unlike AC systems, which are backed by decades of robust, harmonized standards, DC systems remain relatively under-standardized. Existing DC norms are fragmented and application-specific, offering limited guidance for key aspects like protection coordination, short-circuit analysis, or selectivity—especially in multi-source, converter-based LVDC networks.

The deliverable D2.2 presents a complete methodology for the design of protection systems in LVDC networks, developed within the Shift2DC project under the European Union’s Horizon Europe program. Due to the technical complexity and interdependence of the topics involved, the work has been structured into four complementary parts:

- A) Earthing Systems - The Earthing Systems Sub-Deliverable analyses the specificities of DC stray currents and their link to corrosion of metallic structures. It reviews different earthing configurations and provides recommendations for reducing corrosion risk, such as the use of TN-S or IT systems, along with verification and continuous monitoring.
- B) Protection Plan Methodology – This Methodology provides a structured approach for identifying, detecting, and isolating faults in LVDC networks. It covers protection philosophies, fault types, and selection criteria for protective devices — including both conventional (fuses, breakers) and emerging (solid-state) technologies — tailored to DC-specific challenges.
- C) Short-Circuit Current Calculation – This document introduces a simulation-based approach for determining prospective short-circuit currents in LVDC systems with multiple sources. It presents simplified models for common components and recommends time-domain simulations to support protection design in the absence of comprehensive DC standards.
- D) Selectivity in DC Systems - Finally, this sub-Deliverable explores how to ensure that only the faulted part of a DC network is isolated during a disturbance. It evaluates the applicability of AC selectivity principles, identifies the limitations of conventional methods in DC contexts, and examines emerging technologies like solid-state breakers and advanced protection schemes.

Each part of these deliverable addresses a critical aspect of LVDC protection (earthing, planning, short-circuit calculation, and selectivity) forming a unified, standards-oriented methodology to ensure safety, reliability, and continuity in DC microgrids.

This work contributes to Shift2DC’s goal of advancing interoperable and resilient LVDC systems. By addressing a key standardization gap, D2.2 supports WP5 on three levels: informing standardization efforts (T5.2), providing a validated technical basis for pre-standardization testing (T5.3), and contributing to the development of the strategic roadmap for DC deployment (T5.4). Its methodologies serve as concrete inputs for regulatory dialogue, technology validation, and harmonization activities.

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Executive Summary

This document, prepared as part of the Shift2DC project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe program, provides a comprehensive analysis of system earthing for low-voltage direct current (LVDC) microgrids. The primary focus is on the specificities of Direct Current (DC) system earthing, highlighting potential risks associated with DC stray currents, particularly regarding the corrosion of metallic parts, including the rebar structure of reinforced concrete.

Section 1 provides a brief reminder of the key objectives of a system earthing: protect people against electrical shocks and protect equipment from damage caused by fault currents or overvoltage. It also offers a brief description of all possible system earthing types, emphasizing the specificities of new LVDC applications.

Section 2 explains the origin of DC stray currents and provides examples where issues caused by stray currents are already known. After detailing the electrochemical phenomena involved, it clearly states that *corrosion occurs wherever DC current exits the metal*, leading to structural degradation.

Section 3 elaborates on the compatibility of all system earthing types regarding corrosion risk and concludes that:

- TT and TN-C systems require specific arrangements to manage corrosion risks.
- TN-S, including Alternating Current (AC)-side earthing, and Monolithic IT Systems are effective in mitigating corrosion risks when installed correctly.

Section 4 briefly discusses the importance of using galvanic isolation between AC and DC systems, recommending galvanic separation for most applications.

The document concludes with two main recommendations:

- *Pre-commissioning Verification*: Measure the installation insulation resistance before commissioning to detect abnormal situation.
- *Continuous Monitoring and Maintenance*: Essential to detect variations to maintain safety and reliability.

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Keywords, Acronym

AC	Alternating Current
DC	Direct Current
EMC	Electromagnetic Compatibility
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EV	Electric Vehicle
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ILC	Interlink Converter
IT	Electric system according to IEC 60364-1 where all live parts are isolated from earth, or one live part is connected to earth through a high impedance
L	Line conductor
L-	Negative Line Conductor
L+	Positive Line Conductor
LV	Low Voltage
LVDC	Low-voltage Direct Current
M	Mid-point conductor
NEC	National Electrical Code (United States)
ODCA	Open DC Alliance
PE	Protective Earthing conductor
PEI	Prosumer Electrical Installations
PEL	Protective Earthing and Line conductor
PEM	Protective Earthing and Mid-point conductor
PEN	Protective Earthing and Neutral conductor
PV	Photovoltaic
RCD	Residual Current Device
SELV	Safety Extra-Low Voltage
SRC	System Referencing Conductor
TN	Electric system according to IEC 60364-1 where one live part is directly connected to earth, and exposed-conductive-parts are connected to the earthed point where the live part is connected to earth
TN-C	TN electric system where the function of a live conductor is combined with the function of a protective earthing conductor to form a single conductor
TN-C-S	TN-C electric system from the source becoming a TN-S electric system at a certain point
TN-S	TN electric system where live conductors and protective earthing conductors are separated from each other
TT	Electric system according to IEC 60364-1 where one live part is directly connected to earth, and exposed-conductive-parts are connected to earth, independent of the earthing of the live parts of the electric system
UV	Ultraviolet

Symbols, Subscripts

Cl^-	Chloride ion
Cl_2	Chlorine gas
CO_2	Carbon dioxide
e^-	Electron
Fe	Elemental iron
Fe^{2+}	Ferrous ion
Fe_2O_3	Iron(III) oxide
$FeCl_3$	Iron(III) chloride
H_2	Hydrogen gas
H_3O^+	Hydronium ion
O_2	Oxygen gas
OH^-	Hydroxide ion

1 Introduction

This document provides an in-depth analysis of the specificities of DC system earthing. It outlines the potential risks associated with DC stray currents that cause corrosion in the metallic parts they pass through. An evaluation of the compatibility of various earthing schemes with respect to *stray current corrosion* risks is also provided.

It is important to note that AC system earthing and general considerations regarding system earthing are beyond the scope of this document. Comprehensive resources on AC earthing are widely available, such as the information provided in the Electrical Installation Wiki¹. The primary focus of this document is on low-voltage (LV) DC system earthing.

1.1 Purpose of System Earthing

The objectives of system earthing can be broadly classified into two key areas:

- **Protection Against Electric Shock:** Ensuring the safety of individuals by preventing dangerous touch voltage.
- **Protection of Equipment:** Protecting electrical systems, devices, and infrastructure by reducing the damage caused by electrical fault currents or surges.

1.1.1 Protection Against Electric Shock

As explained in the low voltage electrical installations standard, IEC 60364-4-41, published by the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), the protection against electric shock is ensured by:

- **basic protection** (protection against direct contact to accessible hazardous live parts under normal conditions)
- **AND fault protection** (protection under earth fault conditions, where accessible conductive parts may become hazardous live).
- **Moreover, an additional protection** – that cannot replace the basic and fault protections – may be necessary for certain cases where additional risks are identified. One such example is the implementation of Residual Current Devices (RCDs) with a sensitivity of 30 mA for AC outlets.

Several protective measures can meet these requirements, the widely implemented one being the so-called “automatic disconnection of supply” where:

- **the basic protection is provided by basic insulation of live parts**
- **and the fault protection consists of:**
 - connecting to a common earth all exposed-conductive-parts of electrical equipment in the installation
 - and implementing a **system earthing arrangement** to allow earth faults to be detected and cleared.

For IT systems (isolated or impedant), automatic disconnection upon the first earth fault is not mandatory if no hazardous touch voltage arises. However, in scenarios involving two simultaneous earth faults at different locations, automatic disconnection becomes critical. The fault-clearing time

¹ https://www.electrical-installation.org/enwiki/Selection_criteria_for_the_TT,_TN_and_IT_systems

must comply with the requirements specified in the IEC 60364-4-41 standard, which is applicable to both AC and DC systems.

Thus, system earthing forms the foundation of the automatic disconnection principle to ensure safety. Alternative safety principles, such as Class II, eliminates the relevance of system earthing, even if the system may be connected to earth for operational or other purposes.

For instance, in the DC generation section of photovoltaic (PV) installations, the inherently low short-circuit currents make it impractical to achieve short fault-clearing times. In such cases, the automatic disconnection principle is inapplicable, and safety relies on Class II insulation or reinforced insulation measures. Thus, earthing classifications such as "IT" or "TN" systems are irrelevant for the DC portion of a PV installation, while the AC section remains subject to system earthing considerations.

It is essential to note that the TN, TT, and IT earthing systems provide equivalent safety levels when installation and operational guidelines are correctly adhered to. None of these systems is inherently safer than the others; their effectiveness depends on proper implementation and maintenance.

1.1.2 Protection of Goods

The second key objective of system earthing is the protection of electrical equipment and goods. This is achieved through measures designed to ensure operational reliability and protect assets under both normal and fault conditions.

Under normal conditions

System earthing:

- Limits Potential Rise: Stabilizes the potential of neutral or midpoint conductors, reducing the risk of common-mode voltage fluctuations.
- Mitigates Overvoltage Risks: Controls potential levels to ensure overvoltage do not exceed insulation thresholds of connected equipment, preserving operational integrity and longevity.

Under fault conditions

During fault conditions, system earthing plays a critical role in:

- Managing Thermal Constraints: Controls fault currents and ensures appropriate clearing times to limit thermal stress on electrical equipment.
- Preventing Overvoltage Events: Mitigates risks of overvoltages exceeding equipment insulation levels, protecting devices from damage.
- Facilitating Fault Detection: Enables detection of low earth fault currents, minimizing risks of undetected faults that could escalate into fire hazards or compromise system safety.

1.1.3 Conclusion

The objectives of system earthing underscore its critical role in ensuring safety and protecting both individuals and equipment. Maintaining the integrity of the system earthing is essential for achieving these goals. Addressing challenges such as *stray current corrosion* and other degradation factors is vital to ensure long-term reliability, safety, and operational efficiency.

1.2 Definitions

In low voltage networks, earthing systems are categorized based on their configuration and connection to earth. The nomenclature reflects the relationship between the power system to earth (first letter) and the connection of exposed-conductive-parts to earth (second letter).

Preliminary definitions (as provided by IEC):

- **mid-point:** common point between two symmetrical circuit elements of which the opposite ends are electrically connected to different line conductors of the same circuit.
- **mid-point conductor:** conductor electrically connected to the mid-point and capable of contributing to the distribution of electric energy.
- **Line conductor:** conductor intended to be energized and capable of contributing to the transmission or distribution of electric energy, but which is not a neutral conductor or mid-point conductor.
- **Live part:** conductive part intended to be energized under normal operating conditions, including the neutral conductor and mid-point conductor, but excluding the PEN conductor, PEM conductor and PEL conductor.
- **PE (Protective Earth):** This conductor is used to connect the non-current-carrying parts of electrical equipment to the ground. Its primary purpose is to provide a path for fault currents to ensure safety and prevent electric shock.
- **PEN (Protective Earth and Neutral):** This conductor combines the functions of both protective earthing and neutral. It is used in certain earthing systems (like TN-C) where the neutral and earth functions are combined into a single conductor, providing a return path for current as well as safety earthing.
- **PEL (Protective Earth and Line):** A PEL conductor is a conductor where the function of a protective earthing conductor is combined with the function of a line conductor. By definition, the PEL is not a live conductor but a conductor carrying an operating current.
- **PEM (Protective Earth and Midpoint):** In DC installations, PEM refers to a conductor that combines the functions of protective earthing (PE) with the midpoint (M) conductor. This configuration is used in systems that require a reference point at the midpoint of the AC/DC converter output.
- **System-Referencing-Conductor (SRC):** conductor between a live part and an earthing arrangement, enabling the live part to be substantially at the potential of the earthing arrangement. The SRC is neither a neutral conductor nor a protective conductor.

1.3 Reference Standards

The following reference standards govern system earthing and provide guidelines for ensuring safety, reliability, and operational efficiency in both AC and DC networks:

- **IEC 60364-1**
Defines AC and DC system earthing arrangements.
- **IEC 60364-4-41**
Provides critical rules for maximum disconnection times to ensure safety against electric shock. These rules are based on reference standards addressing the effects of current on humans and livestock, particularly IEC 61140 and IEC 60479.
- **IEC 60364-4-44**
Details rules for protecting equipment against voltage disturbances and electromagnetic interference. It also includes guidelines for managing currents flowing in the PE conductor.
- **IEC 60364-5-54**

Specifies rules regarding earthing arrangements and protective conductors, ensuring proper system earthing for safety and operational efficiency.

- **IEC 60364-8-82**
Focuses on Prosumer Electrical Installations (PEI), covering systems connected to or independent of distribution networks.
 - Includes both AC and DC networks, providing detailed diagrams for implementing system earthing for safety, even in dynamic scenarios such as islanding.
 - Introduces the concept of the system referencing conductor, which connects a live conductor of the power system to an earthing arrangement.
 - **Note:** TC64 is drafting an amendment to this standard to include:
 - A dedicated annex for PEIs with DC systems.
 - Guidance on distributed sources with isolated interlink converters.
- **NFPA 70 (NEC, Ed. 2023)**
Part VIII of this standard offers rules and guidelines for DC systems, addressing critical safety and operational considerations.
- **ETSI EN 301 605**
This standard pertains to earthing in communication networks. Published by the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), it focuses on telecommunications, broadcasting, and electronic communication networks and services.

1.4 Types of System Earthing

Figure keys:

The following common keys apply to the following figures (Figure 1.1 to Figure 1.11) and are used to illustrate system earthing concepts discussed in the subsequent sub-sections:

- 1 source
- 2 earth electrode for earthing of the system
- 3 electrical equipment with exposed-conductive-part
- 4 SRC
- 5 separation of a line conductor from a PEL conductor
- 6 separation of the mid-point-conductor from a PEM conductor
- 7 earth electrode for the earthing of exposed-conductive-part(s)
- 8 high impedance for earthing of the system, if present
- 9 earthing of the impedance at the source

1.4.1 TT System

One live part is directly connected to earth at the supply source. The user's installation has its own separate earth electrode to which the exposed-conductive-parts are connected to. Both earthing arrangements are electrically independent.

Figure 1.1 and Figure 1.2 (extracted from IEC 60364-1-Ed6 project 64/2760/FDIS) illustrate possible TT system earthing for DC microgrids being galvanically isolated from the AC main.

Figure 1.1: Example of a DC TT system without mid-point

Figure 1.2: Example of a DC TT system with mid-point

1.4.2 IT System

All live parts are insulated from earth, or one live part is connected to earth at the source through a sufficiently high impedance, ensuring that protective measures against electrical shocks are not undermined by the presence of the impedance.

The earthing of exposed-conductive-parts is done:

- either at the same source earth electrode
- or at one separated earth electrode (like on Figure 1.3 and Figure 1.4)
- or at several individual separated earth electrodes

Figure 1.3 and Figure 1.4 (extracted from IEC 60364-1-Ed6 project 64/2760/FDIS) illustrate possible IT system earthing for DC microgrids being galvanically isolated from the AC main.

Figure 1.3: Example of a DC IT system without mid-point

Figure 1.4: Example of a DC IT system with mid-point

1.4.3 TN-S System

One live conductor is directly connected to earth at the supply source. Protective conductors connect the exposed-conductive-parts to the earthed point where the live parts are connected to earth. The mid-point conductor and the PE conductors are separated throughout the system.

Figure 1.5 and Figure 1.6 (extracted from IEC 60364-1-Ed6 project 64/2760/FDIS) illustrate possible TN-S system earthing for DC microgrids being galvanically isolated from the AC main.

Figure 1.5: Example of a DC TN-S system without mid-point

Figure 1.6: Example of a DC TN-S system with mid-point

1.4.4 TN-C System

One live part is directly connected to earth at the supply source. Protective conductors (PE) connect the exposed-conductive-parts to the earthed point where the live parts are connected to earth. The mid-point conductor (M) or the earthed line conductor (L) are combined with the PE function in one single conductor throughout the system.

Figure 1.7 and Figure 1.8 (extracted from IEC 60364-1-Ed6 project 64/2760/FDIS) illustrate possible TN-C system earthing for DC microgrids being galvanically isolated from the AC main.

Figure 1.7: Example of a DC TN-C system without mid-point

Figure 1.8: Example of a DC TN-C system with mid-point

1.4.5 TN-C-S System

One live part is directly connected to earth at the supply source. Protective conductors (PE) connect the exposed-conductive-parts to the earthed point where the live parts are connected to earth. The mid-point conductor (M) or the earthed line conductor (L) are combined with the PE function in one single conductor (PEM or PEL) in parts of the system. As soon as this single conductor is separated between PE and M (or L) it must never be recombined.

Figure 1.9 and Figure 1.10 (extracted from IEC 60364-1-Ed6 project 64/2760/FDIS) illustrate possible TN-C-S system earthing for DC microgrids being galvanically isolated from the AC main.

Figure 1.9: Example of a DC TN-C-S system without mid-point

Figure 1.10: Example of a DC TN-C-S system with mid-point

1.4.6 AC-side TN-S System

The star point of the transformer on the AC-side (MV/LV or LV/LV) is directly connected to earth, and the DC-grid is connected to this transformer by a non-isolating converter. On the DC side, neither line conductor (L+ or L-) are allowed to have an additional low-impedance connection to the PE. Connecting the AC-side neutral conductor to a DC midpoint conductor is not allowed as this would result in steady-state direct currents within the AC neutral line. As such, with this form of earthing, there are only two active lines within the DC grid.

This type of earthing is common in Open DC Alliance (ODCA) and has been adopted for industrial applications due to cost benefits that come with a non-isolating Interlink Converter (ILC) in comparison to an isolated solution. It is not covered by the published version of IEC 60364-1:2015 where only DC systems isolated from AC are described.

Figure 1.11, adapted from VDE-SPEC 90037 [1], illustrates a possible AC-side earthing system for a DC microgrid not being galvanically isolated from the AC mains.

Figure 1.11: Example of an AC-side TN-S system without mid-point

1.5 Selection Criteria of System Earthing Arrangements (AC and DC)

All system earthing arrangements are equivalent in terms of safety, provided they are implemented correctly and adhere to relevant standards. The choice of an appropriate earthing system depends on several factors, including:

- Regulatory requirements
- Continuity of service
- Operating conditions (For example, the IT earthing system requires skilled personnel)
- Characteristics of the network and connected loads

The system earthing selection generally involves a trade-off between fault currents and overvoltage levels. For more detailed selection criteria for AC earthing systems, refer to the *Schneider Electric Electrical Installation Guide*².

1.6 What is specific to new LVDC applications?

While many LVDC applications already exist and effectively manage system earthing in compliance with established reference standards, new developments in LVDC systems challenge the system earthing design.

² https://www.electrical-installation.org/enwiki/Selection_criteria_for_the_TT,_TN_and_IT_systems

Existing LVDC applications and practices

Historically, LVDC has been implemented in applications where high service continuity is critical, such as:

- Emergency lighting systems
- Auxiliary systems in power plants and substations
- Railway is another well-known application.

To meet service continuity requirements or decrease stray currents for these applications, the IT system earthing has been predominantly used.

- **TT system** has not been employed in DC installations to date.
- **TN systems** have seen limited use in DC applications (in telecommunications for example).

Emerging LVDC applications and challenges

New LVDC applications are now emerging, characterized by key features with significant implications for system earthing design:

- Integration of multiple distributed sources: These include renewable energy systems (e.g., PV system), battery storage, regenerative braking in motors, and other local sources.
- Current limited sources: Most sources are associated with converters, that may drastically limit short circuit currents.
- Islandable Installations: Some new LVDC systems are designed to operate independently of the grid to leverage local energy sources during outages or grid failures.
- Higher level of earth leakage currents: PV system generation is predominant in new energy landscape. But solar panels first decrease the installation global insulation resistance, and secondly have a high capacitance to earth, that help high-frequency disturbances generated by converters circulate in the circuits.
- Accessibility to non-skilled users: Many of these systems are designed for residential application, or for public access, as electric vehicle (EV) charging stations, where the users may lack technical expertise.

The main consequences are:

- The need for galvanic isolation between the considered LVDC distribution network and any AC public distribution network has to be taken into account, first to avoid DC earth currents injection in the AC environment, that would blind protection and create safety and corrosion issues; secondly to make protection easier by separating AC and DC networks. When the DC network is galvanically isolated from other networks, an independent system earthing can be selected for it.
- A single SRC should be located at the common point between all sources to master earth fault currents direction and selectivity.
- The protection system may be more complex due to multi-direction currents and limited fault currents.

To ensure safety, reliability and performance, it is essential to identify the most appropriate system earthing arrangements for these new cases and address DC-specific issues, including: **corrosion risks due to DC stray currents**.

Unlike AC systems, where stray currents do not pose any corrosion risk, DC systems are more susceptible to this phenomenon. Effective mitigation strategies are required to manage these challenges.

The following sections of this chapter will explore these topics in detail, including a comprehensive analysis of corrosion caused by DC stray currents.

2 DC Stray Currents & Corrosion Risk

This section provides an in-depth analysis of DC stray currents, focusing on their origins, mechanisms, and impacts. Particular attention is given to their consequences on reinforced concrete structures.

The section aims to:

- Define DC stray currents and explain their common sources in electrical systems.
- Provide brief illustrative examples of known applications where DC stray currents pose problems.
- Explain stray current corrosion through the electrochemical perspective.
- Highlight the risks posed to reinforced concrete, including corrosion of steel reinforcements, structural degradation, and the implications for safety and maintenance.

Understanding and mitigating these risks is crucial for ensuring the long-term reliability and safety of DC installations, particularly in applications such as renewable energy systems, electric vehicle charging infrastructure, and DC microgrids.

2.1 Origin of DC Stray Currents

DC stray currents refer to unintended electrical currents flowing through paths outside the designated electrical circuits [2]. These currents often arise due to imperfections in the system's insulation, which, although designed to minimize leakage, is not infinitely resistive and may degrade over time.

Key characteristics

- **System insulation limitations:**
 - Insulation materials are designed to restrict current flow outside the intended circuit. However, all insulation has determinate resistance, which can decrease further due to aging, wear, or environmental factors.
 - Over time, such degradation can create unintended pathways for current flow, resulting in stray currents.
- **Exclusions from DC stray currents:**
 - **Earth faults:** These are distinct from DC stray currents because they represent fault conditions and are typically transient in nature. Properly functioning protection mechanisms ensure that earth faults do not persist in the system.
 - **High-frequency leakage currents in PV systems:** Photovoltaic converters generate high-frequency AC components during operation, primarily due to the switching (chopping) processes inherent in their design. These currents, coupled with the natural capacitance of PV panels, are classified as AC leakage currents and not as DC stray currents.

Understanding the origins of stray currents is essential for accurately identifying their presence and addressing their associated risks in DC systems.

2.1.1 Global Insulation of the Electrical Installation

Insulation in electrical installations is inherently imperfect. Even in well-designed systems, the global insulation resistance is finite and can vary depending on multiple factors, including system size, environmental conditions, and the integration of additional components.

Typical insulation resistance

- In a medium-sized installation, the insulation resistance typically falls within the range of **100 kΩ to 1 MΩ**.

Impact of photovoltaic panels

- When PV panels are integrated into an installation, their insulation resistance contributes to a decrease in the overall insulation resistance of the electrical installation.
- The insulation resistance of PV panels is inversely proportional to their total surface area, with typical values of approximately **50–100 kΩ** for a 100 kW system (indeed, the IEC 61215-2 testing standard mentions that the PV modules insulation resistance in kΩ should not be less than $40000 / \text{surface_m}^2$).
- The insulation resistance of PV panels depends on environmental conditions and significantly decreases with temperature and humidity.
- As a result, larger PV systems inherently reduce the overall insulation resistance of the electrical installation.

2.1.2 Aging of Installations

Even when a newly installed system exhibits adequate insulation levels to manage stray currents, global insulation resistance inevitably deteriorates over time due to various factors.

This decline poses a risk for increased stray currents.

Causes of insulation deterioration:

- **Mechanical stress:**
 - External forces, such as wind-induced friction on outdoor PV cables, can degrade insulation over time.
 - Structural changes or building upgrades may inadvertently damage cables or insulation.
- **Aging of insulation materials:**
 - Prolonged exposure to a continuous electric field can weaken insulation materials, reducing their effectiveness.
 - Environmental factors such as Ultraviolet (UV) radiation, temperature fluctuations, and humidity accelerate material degradation.

Proper maintenance and periodic testing are essential to monitor insulation performance and address aging-related issues.

2.2 Stray Currents in Existing DC Applications

DC stray currents, though unintended, are often unavoidable in DC systems and have been observed to cause various negative effects in many existing applications. These currents, if not properly managed, can compromise the safety, reliability, and longevity of the installation and nearby infrastructure.

2.2.1 Railway

Railway systems run by DC traction systems are particularly susceptible to the effects of stray currents. Standards such as **EN 50122-2** and **IEC 62128-2** provide detailed guidelines for mitigating these effects and ensuring the safety and integrity of nearby infrastructure.

As illustrated in Figure 2.1, the electrical current feeding the train flows as follows:

- **Supply path:** From the nearest substation, the current travels through the catenary to the train.
- **Return path:** The current returns to the substation via the rails.

When the rails lack sufficient insulation from the earth, a portion of the return current may escape into the earth. These stray currents cause corrosion damage at points where they exit metallic structures, such as underground pipelines, steel reinforcements, or building foundations.

Figure 2.1: Stray currents caused by trains can be captured by buried metallic pipes and lead to corrosion issues at points where the current exits the metal.

One mitigation option is known as drainage, which involves connecting nearby pipes to the negative polarity of the substation using specific diodes. This setup allows the current leaving the pipe to return to the substation without exiting the metal, thereby avoiding corrosion risks.

2.2.2 Telecommunication

In 48V telecommunication systems, the initial earthing configuration connected the negative polarity directly to the earth. While this setup seemed adequate at the time, it led to the dissolution of the thin copper wires in the presence of moisture.

Challenges with negative earthing

- Moisture around thin copper wires was absorbed by insulation materials, thus decreasing their global insulation resistance and allowing stray currents flowing through.
- Stray current corrosion occurred at the copper wires themselves.

Shift to positive earthing

To address these issues, the earthing configuration was modified to connect the positive polarity to earth as illustrated in Figure 2.2. This adjustment ensures that:

- the copper wires become the cathode, effectively halting corrosion on the wires themselves.
- corrosion occurs at the earth electrode, allowing for better management through predictive maintenance.

Figure 2.2: Telecom systems are grounded with positive polarity to ensure that corrosion occurs at the ground electrode rather than on the wires.

2.2.3 Pipelines

When the pipeline's protective coating is damaged, pipelines are particularly vulnerable to stray currents, which can originate from surrounding DC sources, such as railway systems (as discussed in Section 2.1.1).

In the same way, they are also affected by potential variations in the soil allowing stray current to flow in. And naturally occurring telluric currents (induced by geomagnetic activity) that travel through metal structures as preferential paths, considering their low impedance.

To address these challenges, cathodic protection is commonly employed as a reliable and effective solution.

2.3 Electrochemical Phenomena

This section addresses the physical phenomenon occurring at the electrode interface when stray currents leave metal. It provides a comprehensive overview of the key knowledge needed to understand why DC stray currents cause corrosion when they exit metal.

2.3.1 AC Stray Currents

Electrical current is defined as the rate of change of electrical charge over time, which indicates that current flows due to the movement of charged particles. All metals possess free electrons that are shared among atoms and can move freely around fixed atomic nuclei. When a voltage difference is applied, these free electrons are displaced by the Coulomb force, allowing current to flow.

In other media, such as electrolytic environments, current flow does not rely on electron mobility; instead, it involves the displacement of ions. However, in the case of AC stray currents, ions oscillate around a fixed position, resulting in current flow without altering the surrounding environment. This is why AC stray currents do not lead to corrosion issues.

2.3.2 DC Stray Currents

Similarly to AC, in DC systems, free electrons move in metals while ions migrate in other media. However, since the electric field in DC systems always points in the same direction, both electrons and ions are continuously pushed in that direction. This means that, for current to keep flowing, new charged particles must be generated, particularly at the interface between metal and the electrolytic medium. At this interface, missing charges are compensated through electrochemical redox reactions, which ultimately leads to the corrosion of the metal.

This is typically what happens in water electrolysis. Figure 2.3 illustrates two iron rods submerged in water, with a voltage difference applied between them.

Figure 2.3: Water electrolysis with 2 iron electrodes ($U_{DC} < 1.2V$)

Figure 2.4 illustrates the oxidation reaction occurring at the positive electrode (anode). Solid iron is dissolved into the solution, forming iron cations Fe^{2+} while two electrons are released in the metallic rod:

At the cathode, reduction occurs. Water is reduced (absorbs electrons) to form hydrogen and hydroxide ions (OH^-):

Figure 2.4: Oxidation of iron at anodic interface showing the creation of new charged particles

While this simplified example provides a simplified view of the process, it captures the essence of what occurs. In reality, the redox reactions can vary significantly depending on several parameters, primarily the pH of the medium and the metal's potential. For instance, water can also be oxidized at the anode, resulting in the formation of oxygen and hydronium ions:

Additionally, chloride ions can be oxidized to produce chlorine:

It's important to note that even if the metal is not directly converted into ions, the products of these alternative reactions are highly corrosive and will inevitably interact with the metal, causing corrosion according to the following reactions:

Key takeaways:

1. Corrosion occurs wherever DC current exits the metal.
2. DC stray currents cause corrosion at the exit point of every metal part through which they pass.

2.4 DC Stray Currents in Reinforced Concrete

This section specifically focuses on the consequences of DC stray current on reinforced concrete, which is widely used in buildings, especially those where DC microgrids may be installed or are in the vicinity of DC microgrids. It first elaborates on properties of reinforced concrete and afterwards discusses the detailed effects of stray current corrosion on the buried steel rebar.

2.4.1 Properties of Reinforced Concrete

2.4.1.1 Composite Material

Reinforced concrete is a composite material that synergistically combines the benefits of concrete and steel to effectively manage both tensile and compressive forces, as illustrated in Figure 2.5. Ensuring proper adhesion between rebar and concrete is crucial for maintaining the structural integrity.

Figure 2.5: Reinforced concrete beam in bending

2.4.1.2 Conductivity

Concrete is porous and permeable, containing moisture, which allows it to conduct electricity with a resistivity on the order of kilohms.

2.4.1.3 pH and Steel Passivation

Concrete starts with a high alkalinity, with a pH around 13, which keeps the buried steel within its protective passivation range, shielding it from corrosion. However, when concrete is exposed to atmospheric carbon dioxide, carbonation occurs. This process involves carbon dioxide reacting with calcium hydroxide in the cement paste, gradually lowering the pH of the concrete. Over time, this natural aging process can bring the pH down to around 9, which is where steel becomes susceptible to corrosion. The rate of carbonation is influenced by various factors such as moisture, temperature, and porosity.

Additionally, another factor contributing to aging is the presence of chlorides, which can corrode the steel reinforcement. This risk is typically associated with specific environments, such as coastal areas or the use of de-icing salts.

2.4.2 Impact of DC Stray Currents on Reinforced Concrete

2.4.2.1 Concrete Spalling

When exposed to DC stray currents, steel reinforcement bars are subjected to corrosion where the current leaves metal. As the corrosion products are larger than the original materials (as shown in Figure 2.6), the concrete is subjected to internal pressures which can lead to cracking and, in some cases, spalling of the concrete [3], [4], as seen in Figure 2.7.

Figure 2.6: Volume of iron atom compared to iron oxides

Figure 2.7: Cracks resulting from internal pressure caused by corrosion products initiated by chlorides [5]

2.4.2.2 Accelerated Aging

As cracks form, atmospheric oxygen (O₂) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) can more easily penetrate the concrete. Oxygen accelerates the natural corrosion of steel when it reaches the rebar, while CO₂ causes carbonation, which lowers the overall pH of the reinforced concrete and may expose the steel to a corrosive environment. Both processes contribute to the accelerated aging of reinforced concrete.

2.4.2.3 Possible Loss of Rebar Adhesion

In addition, as depicted on Figure 2.8, if the corrosion layer on the rebar becomes too substantial, its adhesion to the concrete may be compromised, jeopardizing the overall integrity of the structure.

Figure 2.8: Concept of bond anchorage between steel and concrete showing that efforts are no more transmitted to concrete.

2.5 Risk Assessment

Effective risk assessment is critical in managing corrosion caused by stray currents in DC systems. The standard EN 50162 provides detailed guidelines and measures for protection against stray-current-induced corrosion and offers criteria to evaluate associated risks.

Guidelines from **EN 50162**

- **Section 6:** Defines the criteria for assessing the risk of stray-current corrosion, focusing on potential shifts in metallic structures.
- **Annex C:** Provides additional technical insights and detailed recommendations to support the evaluation and implementation of mitigation measures.

Risk assessment criteria

The risk of stray-current corrosion is determined by measuring the potential shift of steel in reinforced concrete structures. The standard establishes thresholds to classify the level of risk:

- **Acceptable shift:**
 - A potential shift smaller than 20 mV is deemed acceptable.
 - Under this condition, the risk of stray-current corrosion is negligible, and no additional protective measures are required.
- **Unacceptable shift:**
 - A potential shift greater than 200 mV is classified as unacceptable.
 - This level of shift indicates a significant risk of corrosion, requiring immediate mitigation to protect the structure and prevent long-term damage.

3 Compatibility of System Earthing Regarding Corrosion Risk

3.1 TT Systems

In TT system earthing, earth currents inherently circulate through the earth to return to the source, as illustrated on Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: DC TT Earthing Configuration

Risk of corrosion:

- As a voltage drop between the exposed-conductive-parts earth and the source earth electrodes may exist, stray currents may be initiated between the system earthing and the source earthing electrodes.
- As DC stray currents cause corrosion at points where they exit the metal, they may damage either earth electrodes or even intermediate buried metallic structures on the DC current path, such as reinforcements.

Limitations of RCDs

- The use of RCDs in TT systems does not ensure that the potential difference between earthing electrodes will remain within safe limits.
- RCDs are effective for fault detection and disconnection but cannot control or mitigate stray current pathways or associated corrosion risks.

Implementation in DC microgrids

The TT system earthing can then be employed in DC microgrids only with specific and dedicated arrangements designed to manage and minimize corrosion risks.

3.2 IT Systems

Monolithic IT system

If design strictly adheres to standard installation rules, in a monolithic IT system, as illustrated in Figure 3.2, all the leakage currents remain confined to the designated protective pathways and avoid entering the earth. This ensures a reduction in the likelihood of stray currents and lowers the corrosion risk (comparable to TN-S systems, see Section 3.4).

Figure 3.2: DC IT Earthing Configuration

IT systems with several separated earthing electrodes:

- **Multiple earthing electrodes:**
 - Instead of exposed-conductive-parts all earthed at the unique source electrode, as for the monolithic configuration, IT systems may utilize multiple separated earthing electrodes, particularly when distributed across several buildings.
 - The circulation of leakage currents corresponding to the installation global insulation resistance then introduces potential differences between separated earth electrodes.
- **Corrosion risk:**
 - These potential differences may initiate stray current circulation, resulting in corrosion risks similar to those observed in TT systems.

Key considerations

- **Monolithic IT system:**
 - As for TN-S system, this system minimizes corrosion risk provided the design strictly adheres to standard installation rules.
- **IT Systems with several separated earthing electrodes:**
 - As far as possible, the monolithic configuration has to be promoted by making all earth electrodes equipotential.
 - When impossible, the distributed IT system has to be considered like the TT system: it can be employed in DC microgrids only with specific and dedicated arrangements designed to manage and minimize corrosion risks. The monitoring of potential differences between earth electrodes to ensure compliance with EN 50162 standard is highly recommended.

3.3 TN-C Systems

In the TN-C system earthing, a single conductor serves as both the protective earthing and a live conductor (line for a PEL or mid-point for a PEM). While this configuration reduces material requirements, it introduces significant challenges related to electromagnetic compatibility (EMC), safety, and corrosion.

Electromagnetic Compatibility challenges

- **High-Frequency disturbances:**
 - DC microgrids include multiple converters that generate high-frequency disturbances.
 - These disturbances can propagate through the exposed-conductive-parts connected to the shared PEL or PEM conductor, potentially causing electromagnetic fields and interference.
- **Potential differences and cable shielding issues:**
 - Exposed conductive parts may not always be at the same electrical potential due to the shared conductor, leading to circulating currents in cable shields, not sized for this constraint.
 - This can also result in communication issues, equipment malfunctions, or reduced system reliability.
- **Standard recommendations:**

According to IEC 60364-4-44 standard, the TN-C system must not be used in newly constructed buildings containing, or likely to contain, significant amounts of information technology equipment.

Limitation of RCDs

- The use of RCD is prohibited in the TN-C system as the residual principle relies on the separation of protective and live conductors.
- This restriction removes an important layer of protection in multi-source systems with generally limited fault currents, where RCDs may be critical for detecting and disconnecting fault currents.

Corrosion risks

- **Voltage drop in the PEL / PEM conductor:**
 - The resistance of the shared conductor combined with the DC current flowing through it leads to a voltage drop along its length.
 - When the voltage drop is applied to a building's structure, such as through a screwed metallic enclosure, it creates pathways for stray currents to circulate, as illustrated in Figure 3.3.
- **Impact on metallic components:**
 - These stray currents can corrode all metallic components in their path, including screws and fasteners.
 - This corrosion poses a mechanical risk, as deteriorated fixations can compromise structural stability.
- **Reinforced steel structure deterioration:**
 - If the connections within the building's steel structure are not properly made, stray currents can deteriorate it, potentially compromising the building's structural integrity.

Figure 3.3: DC TN-C Earthing Configuration

- **Implementation in DC Microgrids**
 - Due to its inherent disadvantages in DC, including corrosion risk, the TN-C system cannot be implemented without measures mitigating these challenges, which may be impossible in large installations, the reason why it should not be recommended in DC microgrids.

3.4 TN-S Systems

In the TN-S system, illustrated in Figure 3.4, leakage currents are directed into the dedicated protective conductors, supplemented by additional bonding conductors, and in the metallic electrode in the foundation. This design ensures that electrical currents follow defined paths, significantly reducing the likelihood of stray currents.

Figure 3.4: DC TN-S Earthing Configuration

Advantages of the TN-S system:

- **EMC**
 - The TN-S system earthing is considered as being the best one for EMC (this is why, according to IEC 60364-4-44 standard, it must be implemented in installations containing significant amounts of information technology equipment).
- **Prevention of stray currents:**
 - Under normal operating conditions, the separation of the protective conductor from the live conductors, as well as the connection of exposed-conductive-parts to the

source earth at a unique point, ensures that leakage currents remain confined to the designated protective pathways.

- This effectively prevents stray currents from taking alternative routes, such as through metallic structures or buried reinforcements.
- **Lower corrosion risk:**
 - Preventing DC stray currents naturally helps to prevent *stray current corrosion*.

Critical installation requirements

For a TN-S system to meet its low corrosion risk and high reliability, installation rules must be strictly adhered to:

- **Earthing of exposed conductive parts:** Properly earth all equipment and structures to provide a reliable path for fault and leakage currents.
- **Equipotential bonding:** Achieve uniform potential across the system.
- **Connection of reinforced concrete steel:** Ensure the steel reinforcement in concrete structures is properly bonded and integrated into the earthing system to avoid potential corrosion risks.

3.5 AC-side TN-S System

Risk of corrosion:

- As all solidly earthed systems, AC-side TN-S earthing is susceptible for leakage currents in case installation requirements are not properly followed.
- The DC System voltage must be kept above the rectified mains voltage to limit leakage currents (no 150 Hz ripple at PE).

Limitations of RCDs:

- During single line earth faults, DC currents can be supplied to the AC grid. As such, RCDs on the AC side between ILC and transformer need to be suitable for DC currents (Type B), and selective with earth fault protective devices installed on DC side.

4 Galvanic Isolation between different systems (AC/DC or DC/DC)

As mentioned in Section 1.6, systems that integrate both AC and DC distribution can be challenging to manage in terms of earth fault protection, particularly due to the risk of protection devices blinding. Additionally, high-frequency disturbances may be transferred between the two systems, complicating management with respect to EMC.

For industrial settings, system following the ODCA [1] specification oftentimes realize grids that are not isolated from the AC mains (refer to Section 1.4.6), since all associated risks are consciously managed by experienced designers and technical teams. For general purpose grids, Current/OS³ recommends employing isolated systems through galvanic separations, explicitly using TN-S system earthing.

Additionally, depending on the application, connecting specific parts of the DC grid may require the mandatory use of isolating converters for various reasons:

- Safety Extra-Low Voltage (SELV)-zones must be galvanically isolated from higher voltages.
- EV charging: the EV-side of the charging converter needs to be an IT-system, as such isolating converter is needed here.
- To decouple specific parts (for example large PV-installations with high Y-Capacitances), using an isolating converter might be the better idea.

Furthermore, the use of galvanic isolation enables the establishment of a distinct earthing system for the DC grid, separate from that of the AC grid. For instance, in situations where service continuity is critical, IT systems are utilized, necessitating isolation from the main AC grid.

Note: The specific risks and mitigation strategies related to earth faults are discussed in more details in the "Protection Plan Methodology" deliverable.

³ <https://currentos.foundation/>

5 Conclusion

Stray currents in DC microgrids pose significant corrosion risks compared to their AC system counterparts. Particular attention must be given to the choice of earthing arrangements, as different systems exhibit varying levels of susceptibility to corrosion:

TT and TN-C systems:

These configurations require careful consideration due to their inherent potential for corrosion.

TN-S and monolithic IT systems:

- When installed in compliance with established standards, these systems effectively mitigate corrosion risks by confining earth leakage currents to the PE and bonding conductors.
- The choice between TN-S and monolithic IT arrangements can then be guided by traditional criteria, such as regulatory requirements, continuity of service, operating conditions, and characteristics of the network and connected loads.

Key recommendations:

- **Pre-commissioning verification:**
Conduct comprehensive insulation resistance measurements before commissioning to ensure the correctness and reliability of the installation.
- **Continuous monitoring and maintenance:**
Because installations may experience reduced insulation resistance over time, resulting in the development of stray currents that can severely impact the integrity of building structures, continuous monitoring of stray currents is essential to ensure ongoing safety and reliability. Additionally, predictive maintenance practices should be adopted to identify and proactively address potential issues, thereby reducing the risk of long-term damage.

Careful selection of earthing arrangements, along with verification, monitoring, and maintenance, ensures that DC microgrids achieve reliability, safety, and operational efficiency, meeting the demands of modern applications.

6 Applicable standards

IEC Standards:

- **IEC 60364-1:2005** – Low-voltage electrical installations - Part 1: Fundamental principles, assessment of general characteristics, definitions.
- **IEC 60364-4-41:2005** – Low voltage electrical installations - Part 4-41: Protection for safety - Protection against electric shock.
- **IEC 60364-4-44:2024 RLV** – Low-voltage electrical installations - Part 4-44: Protection for safety - Protection against voltage disturbances and electromagnetic disturbances.
- **IEC 60364-5-54:2011** – Low-voltage electrical installations - Part 5-54: Selection and erection of electrical equipment - Earthing arrangements and protective conductors.
- **IEC 60364-8-82:2022** – Low-voltage electrical installations - Part 8-82: Functional aspects - Prosumer's low-voltage electrical installations.
- **IEC 61140:2016 RLV** – Protection against electric shock - Common aspects for installation and equipment.
- **IEC 60479-1:2018** – Effects of current on humans and livestock - Part 1: General aspects.
- **IEC 61215-2:2021 RLV** – Terrestrial photovoltaic (PV) modules - Design qualification and type approval - Part 2: Test procedures.
- **IEC 62128-2:2013** – Railway applications - Fixed installations - Electrical safety, earthing and the return circuit - Part 2: Provisions against the effects of stray currents caused by d.c. traction systems.

NFPA / NEC (U.S.):

- **NFPA 70 (NEC, Ed. 2023)** – National Electrical Code. (Part VIII deals with DC systems, critical safety and operational rules).

ETSI Standard:

- **ETSI EN 301 605:2013** – Earthing and bonding of 400 VDC data and telecom (ICT) equipment.

EN Standards:

- **EN 50122-2:2022** – Railway applications - Fixed installations - Electrical safety, earthing and the return circuit - Part 2: Provisions against the effects of stray currents caused by DC traction systems.
- **EN 50162:2004** – Protection against corrosion by stray current from direct current systems.

National/Industry Specifications:

- **VDE SPEC 90037:2024** – System Description DC-INDUSTRIE

7 References

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Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

This document, prepared as part of the Shift2DC project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe program, is part of a series of four interrelated deliverables that reference each other:

- D2.2.A, Earthing Systems for DC Microgrids.
- D2.2.B, Protection Plan Methodology.
- D2.2.C, Short-Circuit Current Calculation Methodology.
- D2.2.D, Selectivity in DC systems.

This deliverable D2.2.B, offers a comprehensive framework for protecting Low Voltage Direct Current (LVDC) power systems against various fault conditions to ensure safety and reliability.

The document begins in **Chapter 1** by emphasizing the importance of a well-structured **protection plan**, which involves identifying potential faults, detecting them effectively, and isolating them to restore safe operation.

Chapter 2 outlines typical **LVDC system architectures and topologies** introducing the concept of a “**bus grid**” **topology**, which better reflects the nature of LVDC prosumer installations that do not strictly follow radial configurations. Loop and meshed topologies are not covered due to their absence in Shift2DC demonstrator projects. The document focuses on two-wire distribution.

Chapter 3 presents the **protection philosophies**, highlighting key objectives such as safeguarding people and assets, maintaining system stability, and ensuring service continuity. It also addresses the complexity of electrical protection in multi-sources microgrids, especially in the context of varying power flows and converter-based systems.

Chapters 4 to 7 explain how to protect against various faults. These sections reflect **current standard requirements** and indicate where these may evolve as technologies and practices develop. Firstly, how to protect against **overcurrents** is covered, explaining the coordination required between conductors and protective devices for **overload and short-circuit** conditions. Then, how to protect against **earth faults** is described, particularly with respect to the capability of protective conductors and how to protect against **electric shock**. The constraints associated to power converters are investigated regarding overcurrents and earth faults. Subsequently, methods to protect against **thermal effects** and **overvoltages** are described.

Chapter 8 reviews **protective devices technologies**, including traditional solutions (fuses, electromechanical circuit breakers & Residual Current Devices (RCDs)) and emerging technologies like **semiconductor and hybrid circuit breakers**, which are expected to play a key role in future LVDC systems. This chapter provides guidance on **how to select** appropriate devices, and on **how to set** them correctly to ensure effective protection. The selection of **surge and overvoltage protections** (SPDs) is also covered.

Finally, **Chapter 9** discusses the role of **monitoring devices**, such as insulation monitoring devices (IMDs), insulation fault locators (IFLs), and residual current monitoring devices (RCMs).

This document is a practical guide that facilitates those responsible for electrical network design to formulate a protection plan to ensure the network is sufficiently protected, considering various types of faults, as well as the constraints that power converters impose. It provides key criteria to select and set the appropriate protective devices, meeting current standards requirements and sometimes anticipating upcoming changes.

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Keywords, Acronym

AC	Alternating Current
ACB	Air Circuit Breaker
ACS	Assemblies for Construction Sites
AFDD	Arc Fault Detection Devices
CSA	Cross-Sectional Area
DBO	Distribution Board for use by Ordinary persons
DC	Direct Current
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
di/dt	Current rate-of-rise
EESS	Electrical Energy Storage System
EMCB	Electromechanical Circuit-Breaker
ESD	Electrostatic Discharge
ESL	Equivalent Series Inductance (of a capacitor)
ESR	Equivalent Series Resistance (of a capacitor)
EV	Electric Vehicle
EVSE	Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment
GDT	Gas Discharge Tube
GTO	Gate Turn-Off Thyristor
HRG	High Resistance Grounding
HV	High Voltage
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IFL	Insulation fault location
IFLS	insulation fault location system
IGBT	Insulated-Gate Bipolar Transistor
ILC	Interlink Converter
IM	Insulation Monitoring
IMD	Insulation Monitoring Device
I_{out}	Output current
IT	Electric system according to IEC 60364-1 where all live parts are isolated from earth, or one live part is connected to earth through a high impedance
L	Line conductor (also a live conductor)
L-	Line conductor, negative polarity (also a live conductor)
L+	Line conductor, positive polarity (also a live conductor)
LPS	Lightning Protection Systems
LV	Low Voltage
LVDC	Low Voltage Direct Current
M	Mid-point conductor (also a live conductor)
MCB	Miniature Circuit breaker
MCCB	Moulded Case Circuit breaker

MOSFET	Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor Field-Effect Transistor
MOV	Metal Oxide Varistor
MV	Medium Voltage
MVDC	Medium Voltage Direct Current
NEC	National Electrical Code (United States)
OCPD	OverCurrent Protective Device
OVC	Over Voltage Categories
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
PD	Protective Device
PE	Protective (earthing) conductor
PEL	Protective Earth and Line
PEM	Protective Earth and Mid conductor
PEN	Protective Earth and Neutral
PSC	Power switchgear and controlgear
PSS	Power Semiconductor Switch
PV	Photovoltaic
RCD	Residual Current Device
RMS	Root Mean Square
SAD	Silicon Avalanche Diode
SCCB	Semiconductor Circuit-Breaker
SCHCB	Semiconductor Hybrid Circuit-Breaker
SLD	Single Line Diagram
SPD	Surge Protection Device
SRC	System Referencing Conductor
SSCB	Solid-State Circuit-Breaker
TC	Technical Committee
TCC	Time-Current Characteristics
TN	Electric system according to IEC 60364-1 where one live part is directly connected to earth, and exposed-conductive-parts are connected to the earthed point where the live part is connected to earth
TN-S	TN electric system where live conductors and protective earthing conductors are separated from each other
TN-C	TN electric system where the function of a live conductor is combined with the function of a protective earthing conductor to form a single conductor
TT	Electric system according to IEC 60364-1 where one live part is directly connected to earth, and exposed-conductive-parts are connected to earth, independent of the earthing of the live parts of the electric system
TVS	Transient Voltage Suppressors
VCC	Voltage Clamping Circuit
V _{OUT}	Output voltage
WP	Work Package

Symbols, Subscripts

Overcurrent & Short-Circuit Protection

I_B	Circuit design current
I_n	Rated current of the protection device
I_r	Adjustable threshold of the overload protection device
I_2	Current that ensures device operation within conventional time
I_Z	Continuous current-carrying capacity of the conductor
S	Cross-sectional area of the conductor
k	Material constant (related to resistivity, heat capacity, etc.)
$E_{conductor}$	Energy the conductor can thermally withstand
I_{SC}	Short-circuit current (rms value)
t	Duration of short-circuit
I^2t	Joule integral (let-through energy of protective device)
I_{nA}	Rated current of an assembly
I_{ng}	Group rated current of a main circuit within the assembly
I_{nc}	Rated current of a main circuit when used alone in a section
I_{cc}	Conditional short-circuit current
I_{cp}	Prospective short-circuit current
I_{cw}	Rated short-time withstand current (thermal limit)
I_{pk}	Rated peak withstand current (dynamic limit)
$n = \frac{I_{pk}}{I_{cw}}$	Peak-to-RMS short-circuit current ratio (standardized value for DC)
V_{drop}	Voltage drop in conductor

Earth Fault Protection

I_{ef}	Earth fault current
S	Cross-sectional area of protective conductor
k	Material constant (resistivity, temp. coefficient, etc.)
t	Fault duration
Z_s	Impedance of the fault loop
I_a	Current causing operation of disconnecting device (earth fault)
U_0	Nominal voltage between line and earth
U	Nominal voltage between conductors or line to mid-point/neutral
U_0	Nominal line-to-earth voltage
$L \cdot \frac{di}{dt}$	Voltage surge caused by switching operations (inductive energy release)

Earthing System Types / Network Topologies

U_0	Nominal line-to-earth voltage
I_n	Rated current of protective device

U1 – U6	Defined voltage levels (IEC TR 63282)
B1 – B7	Voltage bands based on U1–U6
R1 – R4	Time-based operating ranges (IEC TR 63282)
A1 – A7	System/equipment operational states based on voltage and time

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & scope of the document

The purpose of this document is to outline LVDC power system architectures and explain how these systems can be protected to ensure safety. The main scope of this document includes:

- Describing system protection philosophies with specific LVDC concepts
- Explaining what components shall be protected and for what types of faults
- Describing the main rules to ensure protection (against overcurrent, earth faults, thermal effects and overvoltage)
- Describing constraints that power converters, which are dominant in Direct Current (DC) power systems, put on the protection requirements
- Describing how to choose and set protection and monitoring devices

It should be acknowledged that the parts relating to the rules to ensure protection against different types of faults are mainly based on the existing applicable International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) standards. Where necessary, it is mentioned when the topic is, or should be, under consideration for improvement at the IEC level.

Furthermore, the part relating to choosing and setting protection devices includes the topic of semiconductor circuit-breakers which is currently under development and standardisation at the IEC level.

Ultimately, this document will allow those responsible for electrical network design to develop a plan for protecting against various types of faults.

Selectivity, which is associated with protection, is not covered in this document. Please refer to the Shift2DC deliverable D2.2.D which deals with Selectivity in DC systems [1].

1.2 Purpose of electrical protections

The most fundamental requirement of a power system, or any electrical installation, is that it should operate in a safe manner. However, no matter how well the system is designed, operated, and maintained, faults will still occur. Faults present risks to life (e.g. people) and assets (e.g. wiring systems, etc.), and therefore protection against these faults is of paramount importance.

The development of a protection plan for an electrical network is a critical task to ensure safe and reliable operation of the system, however it can be complex and demanding. It involves the identification of possible faults within the electrical network and defining methods for detecting and eliminating these faults.

The protection plan is often influenced by the system architecture and other constraints, such as those imposed by power converters. The protection plan must consider what to protect, such as the protection of people and protection of assets, and what to protect against, such as overloads, short-circuits, deterioration of insulation, loose connections, and overvoltage; all of which can have severe consequences. The following key sections are given in this document:

- Section 3: Protection system philosophies
- Section 4: How to protect against overcurrents

- Section 5: How to protect against earth faults
- Section 6: How to protect against other thermal effects
- Section 7: How to protect against overvoltage

Moreover, the protection plan must consider the type of protective devices used, and how to select and set the protection that is needed to eliminate faults. The technology (which may be existing or emerging) and performance of protective devices is one important aspect, as well as the selection criteria to ensure the device is suitable for the application and will function as desired. Please refer to:

- Section 8 How to select and set protection devices.

Section 8 specifically covers:

- Selecting protective devices according to the type of circuit and earthing system
- Overcurrent protection in the form of fuses, electromechanical circuit-breakers, semiconductor and hybrid circuit-breakers
- Residual overcurrent protection
- Surge and overvoltage protection

The selection and setting of insulation monitoring devices are included in this deliverable (Section 9) as they complement and play an important role in the safe operation of a DC installation.

2 DC network architecture

This chapter provides definitions of the DC distribution systems and topologies.

2.1 DC distribution systems

According to IEC 60364-1, systems and the classification of live conductors in DC distribution can be:

- either two-wire, with two-line conductors, with negative and positive polarity, (L+ and L-, respectively), that can be illustrated by Figure 2.1:

Figure 2.1: Two-wire DC system (Based on: IEC 60364-1)

- or three-wire, with two-line conductors (L+ and L-) and a mid-point conductor (M), that can be illustrated by Figure 2.2:

Figure 2.2: Three-wire DC system (Based on: IEC 60364-1)

Three-wire distribution systems lead to additional complexity to balance currents. The document mainly focuses on two-wire distribution.

2.2 Grid topologies

Three types of grid structure (See Figure 2.3) are usually described in the literature: radial, loop, and mesh structure. These structures are represented below, in the general case of a public grid.

Figure 2.3: Type of grid structure: (a) radial structure, (b) loop structure and (c) mesh structure. Blue nodes represent sources and red nodes represent users.

Radial structure: multiple feeders extend outward from a central power source—typically a transformer station in Alternating Current (AC) systems or an Interlink Converter (ILC) in DC systems—to supply power to various users. This setup is often referred to as a “star” topology in private installations, where each feeder serves an individual load. In public distribution grids, however, the structure is more accurately described as a tree topology: a main bus extends radially from the central source, with several feeders (branches) connected to it. Multiple users (leaves) can be connected along each feeder (branch).

This configuration, illustrated in Figure 2.3 (a), is widely used in low-voltage distribution grids due to its cost-effectiveness and ease of operation. It is particularly well-suited for implementing selectivity, allowing faults to be isolated efficiently. However, a key limitation is its lack of redundancy: if a feeder fails, all users connected to it lose power, as there is no alternative supply path. While the availability of radial grids is inherently low, this is gradually improving with the integration of distributed energy resources (DERs) and the development of advanced control algorithms for islanding and resilience, albeit at the cost of increased investment.

It must be underlined that traditionally, the term “radial” implies a single-source system with unidirectional power flow. However, with the growing penetration of distributed low-voltage generation, most AC and DC grids no longer fit this strict definition. Despite this, the term continues to be used. A more accurate description of today’s grid architecture might be the bus topology, where a central backbone interconnects multiple users. Each user still has a single connection path to the others, but power flows can be bidirectional, and the system may include multiple sources.

Loop structure: the different users can be connected to power sources by two different feeders. These feeders can come from the same power source, in which case we talk about a ring structured grid. If the sources are different, the grid is referred to as looped.

This loop structure is represented in Figure 2.3 (b) and is mainly used in medium voltage distribution grids, in order to ensure availability of the grid. To mitigate the challenges of fault detection and isolation, the loop structure is often operated radially with a switch opening the grid, allowing to select the power source feeding the grid.

Mesh structure: the different users can be connected to power sources by more than two different feeders. Mainly used by systems requiring high continuity of supply, such as the transmission grid, the meshed structure provides a high level of security of supply. However, this solution comes at the price of challenges for voltage regulation, protection strategies and high initial investment.

As this report focuses on low-voltage grid, only the protection of a radial grid, or more precisely bus grid, will be studied later, although other structures may be relevant for sensitive applications such as data centres.

2.3 System Earthing Types

To reduce the corrosion risks, only the following system earthing types are considered as described in “Shift2DC – Earthing Systems for DC Microgrids”[2]

- TN-S with and without ILC galvanic isolation between the main AC and DC systems
- IT with a unique earth electrode for source and exposed-conductive-parts.
 - o with no disconnection at the first earth fault
 - o with disconnection at first fault.

For system earthing types whose source is connected to earth (TN-S and IT connected through impedances), the location of the system-referencing conductor (link between a live part and the earthing arrangement) is key, especially in a multi-source context. As there cannot be several earthing points at sources, two options do exist:

- the most logical earthing point location is at the source's common connection point, which is at the DC bus, as the earthing point can then be permanent, with no need to manage it. In that case, any earth fault in the system is flowing in the system-referencing conductor, where a fault detection should be implemented to detect any earth fault on the DC bus, and make all sources disconnect in that case (see Figure 2.5). When sources are disconnected from the common connection point (typically by operation of associated protective devices), the source itself may become isolated from earth if the earthed polarity is switched and must be carefully managed.
- the second option is an earthing at the main source. Indeed, sources may be dispersed, and the main DC Bus of a certain length. In that configuration, the system-referencing conductor may be disconnected from the bus during certain switching operations, and another System Referencing Conductor (SRC) has then to be re-created in coordination with the first one. This has to be managed carefully. A SRC modification has impacts on the detection of earth faults.

The IEC 60364-8-82, dedicated to prosumer installations, describes how to deal with this kind of configurations in AC and DC.

The protection of circuits depends on:

- the system earthing type,
- the circuit type (supplied from one end or both ends, connected to more than two sources).

The IEC TR 63282 provides two-wire configurations figures for TN-S and IT earthing system types:

Figure 2.4: Two-wire LVDC distribution earthing system

2.4 Typical example

Figure 2.5 gives an example of a typical hybrid prosumer network, where the InterLink converter is bidirectional and isolated, and the system referencing conductor located at the bus common to all sources.

Figure 2.5: Example of a typical hybrid prosumer network with an isolated interlink converter (in blue DC, in black AC).

* **For IT systems:** System-referencing conductor and impedance (for certain IT systems)
+ Insulation Monitoring Device (IMD)

For TN-S system: System-referencing conductor + Residual current detection

** Additional protection in DC systems is under consideration in IEC 60364-4-41. It may be specified in case of additional risk, just as for socket outlets in AC networks.

OCPD= OverCurrent Protective Device

C1: circuit supplied from one end

C2: circuit supplied from both ends

C3: circuit connected to more than two sources

3 Protection system philosophies

This section provides a general overview of protection systems used in electrical installations.

3.1 Protection system objective

The normal operation of an installation may be disturbed by a certain number of incidents:

- **deterioration of insulating materials (earth faults)**
- **overloads**
- **short circuits**
- loose connections (arcing faults)
- over / under voltages
- over / under frequency
- ...

It is the purpose of the protection systems to:

- protect people against electrical shock hazards (in case of earth fault) and fire,
- limit thermal, dielectric and mechanical stress on equipment,
- help maintain stability in the power system,
- protect adjacent installations (for example, by reducing induced voltage in adjacent circuits),
- improve continuity of service.

In order to reach these objectives, the protection system shall be a fast, reliable and coherent assembly that ensures protection and selectivity by isolating the faulty part of the network as quickly as possible while preventing the healthy parts from deterioration.

Protection, however, has its limits as it generally¹ cannot prevent faults and disturbances; it can only limit their effects and their duration. Furthermore, the choice of a protection system is often a technical and economic compromise.

The design of the Protection System consists in the selection of a consistent, overall scheme suited to the power system and user requirements, in the choice of selectivity principles according to the needs, and in the selection of the protection components, which includes:

- the **nature of the devices** in charge of clearing faults: circuit breakers or fuses (combined with switches or contactors);
- the protection functions (phase overcurrent, earth fault overcurrent, undervoltage, directional overcurrent, etc.);
- the selectivity principles: current-based, time-based, energy-based, logic, directional, etc.;
- the measurement sensors (current and voltage) supplying the data required to detect faults;
- the LV trip units in charge of continuously monitoring the electrical status of the power system up to and including the formulation and emission of orders to the trip circuit to clear the faulty parts.

¹ On an isolated system, an insulation monitoring device (which is not a protective device) allows the user to do preventive maintenance in case of decreasing insulation level

This does not include the setting of protection-units, nor selectivity curves. Protection against overvoltages is not the main part of the protection system, except concerning the fundamental selection of the system earthing (temporary overvoltage is supposed to be higher in IT systems). However, it is necessary to take it into account to ensure the reliability of the system.

3.2 Usual approach

The approach for selecting protection systems strongly depends on the power system architecture and the requirements of the end-user. Various aspects are normally considered when determining a suitable protection scheme, including the size of the power system, different operating modes, earthing systems, characteristics of sources and their contributions in the event of a short-circuit, and load types. Furthermore, continuity of service is another factor which can influence the protection scheme. The focus of this section is protecting life and assets from the effects and consequences of overload and short-circuit currents.

Architecture-related protection schemes

In conventional low-voltage power systems, there is typically one main source supplying loads (see Figure 3.1). The source is usually strong, resulting in high and unidirectional short-circuit currents. In this case, protection schemes are straightforward with thermal overload (ANSI code 49) and phase overcurrent (ANSI code 50/51) protection normally being deployed to protect the system from the effects of overcurrents. Moreover, this protection can typically be used to detect earth faults in solidly earthed systems, resulting in automatic disconnection of the supply (which is a common protective measure) to protect against electric shock. If earth fault currents cannot be detected, then more sensitive protection, such as a residual type, is required. Other common protective measures are described in Section 1.1.1 [1].

Figure 3.1: Conventional power system with some typical protection functions.

In contrast, power systems consisting of several – and sometimes distributed – sources (see Figure 3.2), such as microgrids, can complicate the protection scheme and device selection process. This is due to the number of different power flow scenarios, modes of operation with respect to grid-connected and

islanded states, and the increasing presence of power converters (e.g. for PV, battery, EV, etc.); all of which lead to highly varying short-circuit currents which are bidirectional in some cases.

For this type of system, two different kinds of protective devices based on local measurements may be used for overcurrent protection:

- Devices as conventional trip units (ANSI code 49/50/51), but including new functions, such as:
 - Directional detection (ANSI code 67)
 - Voltage Controlled Overcurrent (ANSI code 51V)
 - Time or logic selectivity discrimination
 - Setting groups according to operating modes (adaptable settings)
- Devices with differential (or zone) detection and real time communication between trip units at the border of the protected zone (line ANSI code 87L or busbar ANSI code 87B).

Figure 3.2: Multiple-source power system with some typical protection functions.

The above figures illustrate the increased complexity when several sources are distributed. The realisation of protection schemes in multiple-source DC microgrids is a challenge. Potential innovative protection solutions which focus on improved continuity of service are described in *Shift2DC D2.2.D - Selectivity in DC Systems* document [1].

Protection verification process

The protection scheme selection along with the desired settings are coordinated with the system design and equipment selection (refer to Section 4 and 5). In general, the overall process leading to the verification of protection involves:

- Calculating design currents
- Selecting conductor cross-sections and considering external influencing factors
- Calculating the maximum and minimum short-circuit currents, including earth fault currents, considering different operating modes and source contributions (refer to *Shift2DC D2.2.C - Short-Circuit Current Calculation Methodology* document [3])
- Selecting protection scheme and protective devices

- Assessing if the circuit/system is protected against overload current
- Assessing if the circuit/system is protected against short-circuit current
- Assessing if the protective device and protection scheme protects against electric shock (for example, in a TN-S system, if the disconnection time requirements are achieved) and if other protection, such as an RCD, is needed.

If all the assessments ensure protection, then the protection settings and protection scheme can be modified to optimise selectivity and continuity of service (refer to *Shift2DC D2.2.D - Selectivity in DC Systems* [1]).

In multiple-source power systems, such as DC microgrids, it can be a complicated and difficult task to determine the short-circuit currents, select the most appropriate protective devices and protection schemes, and verify protection. A key aspect regarding the protection is that short-circuit detection in a DC microgrid could rely on detecting the current from capacitor discharge. This presents various challenges as this discharge current depends on the network and component parameters which could be highly varying (see *Shift2DC D2.2.C - Short-Circuit Current Calculation Methodology* [3]).

3.3 Current/OS Zoning concept

In order to ease design and operation of DC installations, circuits or a group of circuits are classified according to the available fault energy and the protection means in the Current/OS zoning system. There are six DC zones which are described in Table 3.1 [4].

Table 3.1: DC Zones according to Current/OS System Reference Design.

Zone	Main characteristics of circuits	Over Current Protection
Zone 0	High short-circuit current source	None
Zone 1	Most sources have high prospective short-circuit current. Multiple sources, all connected to a common distribution board.	Overcurrent protection devices (OCPD) on the DC bus have breaking time < 50ms (e.g.: EMCBs and fuses).
Zone 2.1	Multiple sources connected to a single distribution board. Sources cannot deliver a current significantly higher than its nominal current, by design. Energy stored in capacitors does not exceed 600 J.	OCPD with breaking time < 50ms (e.g.: EMCBs and fuses) on the DC bus.
Zone 2.2	Multiple distributed sources. Sources (or inductor) that limit the fault current rise and peak.	OCPD with breaking time < 1ms (e.g.: SCHCBs) on the DC bus.
Zone 3	Multiple distributed sources.	OCPD with breaking time < 10 μs (e.g.: SSCBs) on the DC bus.
Zone 4	Single source	OCPD with breaking time < 10 μs (e.g.: SSCBs) on the DC bus.

Current/OS recommends that DC Zones 0 and 1 shall be not distributed in accessible spaces and segregated in restricted areas only accessible to skilled persons. Current/OS recommends that only DC Zones 2.2, 3 and 4 are distributed, due to the lower fault energies and consequent risks. DC Zone 2.1 can be distributed with some limitations (see official document for details).

While all DC zones require the same level of design attention as standard AC installations (e.g., short-circuit calculations for selecting appropriate OCPDs), the design of DC Zones 3 and 4 can be simplified.

Thanks to their ultra-fast protection mechanisms, these zones typically do not require advanced fault current calculations and can often be designed based on nominal current considerations alone. Furthermore, DC Zone 3 allows easy implementation of loop or mesh topologies.

An illustrative example of the zoning concept is given in the following diagram:

Figure 3.3: Current/OS zoning example [4].

For more details, refer to Current/OS System Reference Document [4].

3.4 ODCA sectors concept

ODCA utilizes a sector concept. A DC sector is a group of DC devices that are directly connected to each other electrically, while being connected to the rest of the grid by a common smart breaker. As an example, a battery system with a DC/DC-converter is regarded as a DC sector, or a motor drive, together its inverter and auxiliary power supply, connected to the DC grid with one shared smart breaker. As such, they form logical and functional units and due to the common connection via the smart breaker, the entire DC sector will be disconnected from the DC grid during fault conditions within the sector. Power flow between a sector and the grid is generally bidirectional, although specific applications can result in unidirectional sectors (for example PV generation will only supply energy to the grid).

The ODCA system specification also allows hierarchical sectors. One example for this is a sub-distribution in industrial grids for a specific production line with internal battery storage. As such, within ODCA, selectivity is achieved on a sector level. Figure 3.4 depicts the sector concept for a standard bus-topology, with one two-level setup with two dc-sectors and an additional single-level dc-sector. Refer to the ODCA System Description [5] for further details.

Figure 3.4: ODCA sector concept

3.5 Inter-tripping of multisource system

Prosumer installations typically include a plurality of power sources, which are usually distributed along the installation (typical example is given in Figure 2.5).

A system shall provide means to coordinate the disconnection of all sources in case of faults, when it is not possible to demonstrate that each protective device between the multisource bus and any source will operate:

- in the time defined in IEC 60364-4-43:2023, 431.5.4.2 and 431.5.4.3, for short-circuits.
- according to disconnection times defined in IEC 60364-4-41 for electrical shocks where automatic disconnection of supply is used.

This mechanism is called “*inter-tripping*”.

Protective devices operated by inter-tripping shall open on de-energization of coils, or other equivalent failure-to-safety techniques. After operation of the inter-tripping function, an unintended re-energizing of the relevant circuit shall be avoided.

Other considerations where inter-tripping may be used:

- In case of maintenance (operator must be sure that all sources are disconnected, and the grid is in safe conditions)
- To implement emergency stop, effectively disconnecting all sources, when required.

4 How to protect against overcurrent

For installations, the protection against overcurrent consists in:

- the protection of wiring systems,
- the selection of equipment (switchboards, circuit breakers...) thermal and electrodynamic withstands (in the data sheet) according to short circuit currents,
- the coordination between protections and other devices (switches...), according to manufacturer information.

Equipment is supposed to care with their own protection, according to their product standards. However, some coordination constraints may arise, especially with converters.

4.1 Protection of wiring systems (include cables, busways...)

The temperature limit of a conductor's insulation should never be exceeded:

- neither during normal operation
- nor in case of overcurrent.

Protection against overcurrent mainly relies on the principle of **automatic disconnection of the supply**, where an overcurrent protective device disconnects the circuit before currents can cause damage on the conductors or their insulation. Any short circuit current must be automatically disconnected within 5 seconds. This is a defined short-circuit clearance time according to IEC 60364-4-42 to protect the installation against fire due to fault currents, except for a first earth fault in an IT installation. In some specific cases automatic disconnection of the supply may not be necessary to protect the wiring system because the thermal withstand of cable cannot be exceeded, for example thanks to the limitation of current delivered by the source.

Protective devices for overcurrent protection are generally installed at the point of the circuit, where there is a reduction in the value of current-carrying capacity of the conductors.

How the detection of overcurrents has to be implemented on conductors is detailed in IEC 60364-4-43:

- the detection of overcurrent must be provided **for all line conductors** (except for a Protective Earth and Line (PEL) conductor in DC circuits) and cause at least the disconnection of the conductor where the overcurrent is detected;
- **for the neutral (or Protective Earth and Neutral (PEN)) and mid-point (or Protective Earth and Mid conductor (PEM)) conductors:**
 - the detection of **short circuit** current is not necessary if the protection is already achieved by devices on line conductors;
 - the need for providing an **overload** detection depends on the neutral or mid-point conductor cross-sectional area, on its current, on triplen harmonics rate (in AC). Especially, for a mid-point conductor whose cross-sectional area is equivalent to that of the line conductors, and the current is expected not to exceed the value in the line conductors, it is not necessary to provide overload current detection or a disconnecting device for that conductor.
 - when mandatory, the detection causes at least the disconnection of the line conductors;
 - **special rules apply for IT systems overcurrent detection,**
 - Particularly, the detection is mandatory on the mid-point conductor and causes the disconnection of all live conductors of the circuit, including the mid-point conductor.

If, in a LVDC TN-S system, the same rules as for a mid-point could be applied for a **L+ or L- conductor connected to earth**, is a point of discussion at standardization level.

Several steps allow the AC or DC wiring system sizing and its protection against overcurrent to meet the conductor's temperature limit:

- first the selection of the overload protective device current rating I_n (see Section 4.1.1);
- then the sizing of the wiring system live conductors (which includes line conductors, neutral and mid-point conductors) and PEN/PEM/PEL conductors, according to I_n , to the conductors nature and installation mode (see Section 4.1.2);
- finally, the checking of the wiring system thermal withstands in case of short circuit currents (see Section 4.1.3).

It may sometimes be necessary to increase the conductors cross-sectional area.

4.1.1 Rated current of the protective device against overload

To protect conductors against overload, the rated current I_n of the protective device (circuit breaker or fuse), or its settable threshold I_r , has to be selected according to IEC 60364-4-43 (Section 431.4.2):

$$I_n \geq I_B, \quad (3.1)$$

where I_B is the circuit design current.

Note: This I_n value may have been derated, for example, due to harsh installation conditions of the protective device in its switchboard.

4.1.2 Wiring systems sizing

According to IEC 60364-4-43, to ensure the protection against overload, the continuous current-carrying capacity of the AC or DC wiring system, named I_z , must satisfy the following condition:

$$I_z \geq \max [I_n; I_2 / 1,45] \quad (3.2)$$

where I_2 is the current ensuring effective operation in the conventional time of the protective device. I_2 and the conventional time are defined in products standards. For example:

- $I_2 = 1.3.I_n$ for 1 hour for industrial circuit breakers with $I_n \leq 63A$ (IEC 60947-2 & IEC 60947-10)
- $I_2 = 1.6.I_n$ for 1 hour for fuses with $16A \leq I_n \leq 63A$ (IEC 60269-1:2024 - Low-voltage fuses).

It should be underlined that this formula implies that no sustained overcurrent higher than I_n and less than I_2 occurs. However, in certain applications with current limiting sources, like photovoltaic (PV) installations, this condition may not always be met. It is then necessary to select a higher current-carrying capacity, like:

$$I_z \geq I_2. \quad (3.3)$$

As soon as the minimum I_z value is defined thanks to above rules, the standard IEC 60364-5-52 gives the method to calculate the corresponding minimum cross-sectional area S by taking into account the installation mode and the conductors nature. The minimum cross-sectional area must guarantee that the wiring system can withstand permanent currents (after derating) and offers acceptable voltage drops.

Even if the reference standard IEC 60364-5-52 is the same for AC and DC, some differences may be highlighted:

- For DC, there is no need for applying any configuration of parallel cables and unbalance coefficient (like for AC according to Annex H IEC 60364-5-52).
- In small and in medium power applications, the skin depth for copper and aluminium conductors is generally much larger than the radius of the low voltage cables; for copper, for example, the skin effect is not effective under a calculated cross-sectional area of 267 mm². So theoretically, there should not be any difference in current carrying capacity between AC and DC for a given copper conductor cross-section less than 300 mm² standardized size.

More details of comparison of current carrying capacity under AC and DC for different conductor cross section can be found in *APPENDIX A: Current carrying Capacity under DC and AC*.

4.1.3 Protection against short-circuits

A conductor is able to withstand the following energy:

$$E_{conductor} = (k \cdot S)^2 \quad (4.1)$$

where S is the cable cross-section [mm²] and k is a factor taking into account the resistivity, temperature coefficient, heat capacity of the conductor material, and the appropriate initial and final temperatures (see IEC 60364-4-43, Table 2 for live conductors).

A conductor is protected against a short-circuit current I_{sc} if, for any short-circuit current *rms* value:

- either, for a short-circuit duration t up to 5s:

$$I_{sc}^2 \cdot t \leq E_{conductor} \quad \Rightarrow \quad S(\text{mm}^2) \geq \frac{I_{sc}(A)}{k} \cdot \sqrt{t(s)} \quad (4.2)$$

- or its overcurrent protection is a current limiting device, tripping in less than 0.1s, and whose let-through energy meets the following condition:

$$Energy_{let-through \text{ by the protective device}} \leq E_{conductor} \quad (4.3)$$

(the value of limited energy should be provided in protection devices datasheets or by the protection manufacturer).

4.2 Protection of LV switchgear and controlgear assemblies

The IEC 61439 standard series give rules concerning Low-Voltage (LV) switchgear and controlgear assemblies.

It deals with the integration of devices into an assembly:

- IEC 61439-1: General rules
- IEC 61439-2: Power switchgear and controlgear assemblies (Power switchgear and controlgear (PSC)-assemblies)
- IEC 61439-3: Distribution boards intended to be operated by ordinary persons (DBO)

- IEC 61439-4: Particular requirements for Assemblies for Construction Sites (ACS)
- IEC 61439-5: Assemblies for power distribution in public networks
- IEC 61439-6: Busbar trunking systems (busways)
- IEC 61439-7: Assemblies for specific applications such as marinas, camping sites, market squares, electric vehicle charging stations
- IEC TR 61439-0: Guidance to specifying assemblies

For each type of LV switchgear and controlgear assembly, only two standards are necessary:

- the IEC 61439-1 (basic standard),
- the IEC 61439-x (specific) relevant for the assembly type.

The main principle is that the characteristics of the assembly (declared by the manufacturer) must be compatible with the ratings of the circuits to which they are connected to, taking into account installation conditions.

The following subsections describe the rated performances of the assembly that must be considered to ensure a safe and robust design of the system. Calculations must be carried out to verify that these performances are in line with the system constraints and to select the appropriate protections.

4.2.1 Protection against overload

The IEC 61439-1 defines the following rated currents:

- **rated current of a main circuit (I_{nc})**
rated current which a main circuit can carry when it is the only main circuit within a section of an assembly that is carrying current.
- **group rated current of a main circuit (I_{ng})**
rated current which a main circuit can carry considering the mutual thermal influences of the other circuits that are simultaneously loaded in the same section of the assembly.
- **rated current of an assembly (I_{nA})**
rated current which can be distributed by an assembly without the temperature-rise of any of the parts exceeding specified limits.

The rated current has to meet the following rule to ensure that the assembly can withstand steady-state currents:

$$I_{nA} = \text{Min}[\sum(I_{ng}) \text{ of the incoming circuit(s) in parallel; total current the main busbar can distribute}] \quad (4.4)$$

4.2.2 Protection against short-circuit

According to IEC TR 61439-0, assemblies should be capable of withstanding the mechanical, thermal and dynamic stresses resulting from short-circuit currents available from the power source(s) which they are connected to.

Design verification has to be performed either by testing or comparison with a tested reference design.

According to IEC 61439-1, the assembly characteristics declared by the manufacturer and related to short-circuit withstand, and the rules associated with them, are the following:

- **rated conditional short-circuit current (I_{cc})**
value of the maximum prospective short-circuit current, that can be withstood for the total operating time (clearing time) of the short circuit protective device under specified conditions.
=> $I_{sc} \geq I_{cp}$ (prospective value of the short-circuit current) for a duration limited by the operation of the short-circuit protective device that protects the assembly. The assembly manufacturer declares the breaking capacity and current limitation characteristics (energy Pt and cut-off current I_{te}), of the specified short-circuit protective device (data from the device manufacturer).
Note that according to the standard, the maximum prospective short circuit current in the neutral conductor and in the protective circuit used for design is 60% I_{cp} .
- **rated short time withstand current (I_{cw})**
Root Mean Square (RMS) value of AC or mean value of DC short-time current, that can be withstood under specified conditions, defined in terms of current and time (e.g. 0,2 s; 1 s; 3 s).
=> $I_{cw} \geq I_{cp}$ (prospective value of the short-circuit current at each point of connection to the supply). This value is related to thermal withstand.
- **rated peak withstand current (I_{pk})**
value of peak short-circuit current that can be withstood under specified conditions.
=> $I_{pk} \geq \text{peak value(s)}$ of the prospective short-circuit current of the supply system(s) to which the circuit(s) is (are) designed to be connected. This value is related to dynamic withstand. For DC applications, the value of $n = I_{pk}/I_{cw} = 1.42$ can typically be used according to the standard. In LVDC networks, where high capacitive currents discharges may occur, the maximum short peak value should be much higher. But capacitive discharge currents, which are generally much shorter and not so energetic, should have a lower impact than with the conservative standardized approach. Thus, in case the max prospective peak short-circuit current exceeds I_{pk} because of the capacitor discharge, one should contact the switchgear manufacturer to check if the performance is acceptable or not.

Some circuits are exempted from the verification, like assemblies whose I_{cw} or $I_{cc} \leq 10$ kA mean average for DC. Coordination between protections included in the assembly and external protective devices has to be ensured.

4.3 Additional constraints related to converter withstand

There is no specific regulatory requirement mandating the external protection of power converters, as these devices are governed by their own product standards and are equipped with internal protection designed to prevent fire hazards.

However, given the importance of ensuring service continuity and preserving the integrity of converters—which are critical components in LVDC systems—it is advisable to implement additional protective measures within the system to safeguard these devices.

Indeed, power electronic converters are fundamental components in modern electrical and energy systems, enabling efficient energy conversion between different forms (AC-DC, DC-AC, DC-DC, and AC-AC). A critical aspect of their design and operation is the capability to detect and manage overcurrent

conditions. Overcurrent, which may result from faults, abnormal loads, or control failures, can severely damage semiconductors, degrade system performance, or lead to catastrophic failure if not properly mitigated. Converters can be categorized not only by their function but also by their ability to inherently limit fault currents or not. This classification significantly influences the protection strategies adopted during their design and deployment and the selection of overcurrent protections in the system. In fact, replacing a single converter in a similar grid may require a complete redesign of the protection system.

For example, during short-circuit events, the system voltage may drop low enough to trigger the converters' internal undervoltage protection, causing them to shut down. This may necessitate a black start procedure to restore normal operation. Therefore, source converters may require pre-charging capability along with coordination with dc protection devices to ensure a black start. Additionally, certain converter topologies—such as diode bridges or boost converters—may not be capable of limiting fault current and can allow upstream energy to flow through their freewheeling paths. These diodes are often not rated for short-circuit conditions and may fail, leading to irreversible damage to the converter.

To enhance system behavior under faulty conditions, specific protective devices may be required. In such cases, an effective protection plan should be developed, ensuring coordination between protective devices and converter requirements. Manufacturers of power electronic converters should provide clear, standardized, and application-relevant specifications, such as maximum continuous current, peak transient current, short-circuit withstand ratings (e.g., peak fault current and duration that converter can tolerate without damage), and Joule integral (integral of the square of the current over a given time) (I^2t) withstand ratings. They could also recommend or pre-qualify compatible overcurrent protection devices.

5 How to protect against earth faults

The protection against earth faults concerns:

- the protection of assets
- and above all the protection of people against electric shock (in case of “indirect” contact to an exposed-conductive-part)

The purpose of the system earthing, closely associated to the automatic disconnection of supply, has been explained in the *Shift2DC System Earthing For DC Microgrids* document [2], Section 1.1.

5.1 Protection of assets

This part focuses on the protection against earth faults of assets such as wiring systems and converters.

5.1.1 Wiring systems

For line conductors, the same sizing as explained for line conductors in Section 4.1.2 and 4.1.3 applies.

Protective conductors, only submitted to earth faults, are sized in a similar way for an earth fault (I_{ef}) duration t up to 5s:

$$S(\text{mm}^2) \geq \frac{I_{ef} (A)}{k} \cdot \sqrt{t(s)} \quad (5.1)$$

where S is the cable cross-section and k is a factor taking into account the resistivity, temperature coefficient and heat capacity of the conductor material, and the appropriate initial and final temperatures (see IEC 60364-5-54, Annex A).

5.1.2 Converters

In electrical installations using an IT earthing system, particular attention must be given to the protection of power electronic converters such as inverters, rectifiers, and variable frequency drives. vems, the IT system features an unearthed or impedance-earthed neutral point, allowing the system to continue operating during the first insulation fault. While this enhances continuity of service, it introduces challenges for insulation coordination and fault detection, especially in sensitive equipment like converters.

Under an earth fault condition in an IT system, the potential of the healthy phases with respect to earth can rise significantly. This situation places additional stress on the insulation systems of both the power and control circuitry, increasing the risk of dielectric breakdown, component failure, or unsafe touch voltages.

To mitigate these risks and ensure reliable operation of converters in IT environments, a combination of protective measures must be implemented. One of the fundamental elements is the use of Insulation Monitoring Devices (IMDs). These devices continuously supervise the insulation resistance between live conductors and earth, providing early warnings when resistance drops below a predefined threshold. This is crucial in IT systems, where the first earth fault does not immediately result in system shutdown, and monitoring is essential to prompt corrective actions before a second fault leads to more severe consequences.

In addition to IMDs, the installation of Surge Protection Devices (SPDs) at both the input and output sides of converters is recommended. These devices protect against transient overvoltages that can

occur due to switching operations or lightning strikes. Furthermore, the insulation level of the converter components should be carefully evaluated and rated for possible line-to-earth overvoltages, ensuring the system remains within safe operating limits even under fault conditions. This is not specific to IT systems; it also applies to TN-S.

Earth fault detection relays or RCDs, tailored for IT systems, also play an essential role. While conventional RCDs may not function effectively in IT configurations due to the absence of a low-impedance return path, specially designed earth fault relays can detect leakage or unbalanced currents and signal maintenance personnel or initiate a controlled shutdown.

From a design perspective, it is beneficial to implement galvanic isolation through isolation transformers or opto-isolated signal interfaces, especially where converters are interfaced with control systems or data acquisition units. This breaks potential fault current paths and minimizes the risk of common-mode voltage affecting sensitive equipment.

Additionally, protective coordination between upstream protection devices and the converter's internal fault-handling mechanisms must be ensured. This coordination guarantees that the appropriate section of the system disconnects in the event of a fault, thus preserving overall system integrity and minimizing downtime.

In summary, protecting converters in IT systems requires a comprehensive strategy involving insulation monitoring, overvoltage protection, proper insulation rating, earth fault detection, and thoughtful system design. These measures not only enhance safety and reliability but also ensure compliance with international standards governing the operation of electrical equipment in isolated earthing environments.

5.2 Protection of people

5.2.1 Protective measures against Electric Shock

The protection of people against earth faults is developed in [1]. Different protective measures can be implemented:

- Separation
- Class II
- SELV / PELV
- Automatic disconnection

When it uses the “automatic disconnection” principle, the maximum disconnection time shall comply with the IEC 60364-4-41:2017. For TN systems and for IT systems (with a unique earth electrode for source and exposed conductive parts) at the second earth fault the requirements are given in Table 5.1 for AC and Table 5.2 for DC systems. The values of disconnection time currently listed in the standards are presented here, but those values are subject to change with future revisions of the standard.

Table 5.1: Maximum disconnection times in TN & IT at second earth fault in AC

Nominal line-to-earth AC voltage U_0	$U_0 \leq 50$ V	$50 V < U_0 \leq 120$ V	$120 V < U_0 \leq 230$ V	$230 V < U_0 \leq 400$ V	$U_0 > 400$ V
Final circuits with at least one socket-outlet $I_n \leq 63A$ (and $\leq 125A^*$) (or $>125A$ for ordinary persons) *	5 s*	0.8 s	0.4 s	0.2 s	0.1 s
Final circuits supplying only fixed connected equipment $I_n \leq 32A$ (or $>32A$ if no skilled persons) *					
Distribution circuits & others	5s				

Table 5.2: Maximum disconnection times in TN & IT at second earth fault in DC

Nominal line-to-earth DC voltage U_0	$U_0 \leq 120$ V	$120 V < U_0 \leq 230$ V	$230 V < U_0 \leq 400$ V	$U_0 > 400$ V
Final circuits with at least one socket-outlet $I_n \leq 63A$ (and $\leq 125A^*$) (or $>125A$ for ordinary persons) *	5 s*	1 s*	0.4 s	0.1 s
Final circuits supplying only fixed connected equipment $I_n \leq 32A$ (or $>32A$ if no skilled persons) *				
Distribution circuits & others	5s			

* Standardization draft in work in TC64

In some cases, identified as likely to offer special safety hazards, an additional protection may be required on the circuit to prevent misuse. For example, sensitive RCD are required on AC socket outlets. Additional protection in DC systems (DC-RCD 80 mA) is under consideration. An additional protection does not replace the above protection against earth faults, but compensates in case of failure or misuse, against indirect and even direct contact.

5.2.2 Automatic disconnection in TN-S

As indicated in IEC 60364-4-41 Section 411.4.4), the characteristics of the protective device and the circuit impedances shall fulfil the following requirement:

$$Z_s \times I_a \leq U_0 \quad (5.2)$$

where:

- Z_s is the impedance of the fault loop.
- I_a is the current causing the automatic operation of the disconnecting device within the maximum disconnection time given in Section 5.2.1.
- U_0 is the nominal AC or DC line to earth voltage.

This equation, which is relevant when the system is fed by (constant) voltage sources, ensures there is enough current generated during the fault to trip the device.

The principle widely applied in AC networks considers that the line overcurrent protective device can also manage earth fault protection if the earth fault current is high enough. If not possible (in case of high fault loop impedance), then another protection principle is necessary.

The residual current detection principle, where a current sensor embraces all live conductors (or where currents in live conductors are summarized), excluding Protective Earthing (PE), is widely used in AC networks. It allows the faulty circuit to be automatically detected.

When a RCD is used, the current I_a in the above formula is the residual operating current causing the automatic operation of the disconnecting device within the maximum disconnection time given in Section 5.2.1.

DC-RCD standardization is still in work (it can be referred to IEC 60755-1 for the general safety requirements for RCD in DC systems).

A RCD must disconnect all live conductors in the circuit protected, except in a TN-S system with a neutral conductor considered as reliably connected at earth potential.

Attention should be paid at the detection of earth faults on the main DC bus, where the system reference conductor can be located (see Figure 2.5): the natural location of a current sensor is on this conductor, with an inter-tripping of all sources. This kind of solution does not exist yet.

The fundamental difference between AC and DC fault current nature should be here questioned. In AC, the network is not capacitive like in DC. As a result, the earth fault impedance has less influence on its magnitude, the reason why short-circuits, and earth fault currents are often similar. In DC, the network capacitance and the earth fault impedance generate a delay. The protection should be able to trip in those conditions.

5.2.3 Automatic disconnection in IT with no tripping at first earth fault

In case of a first earth fault current in IT, the permanent current magnitude is very low depending on the earthing impedance HRG—and even null in case of isolated system. This is why it is generally not mandatory to automatically trip at first fault. In case of a second fault on another polarity, however, the current magnitude may be similar to a pole-to-pole short-circuit current, the reason why the automatic disconnection principle applies with rules similar to TN (thanks to the unique earth electrode as assumed in Section 2.3 according to Shift2DC Earthing Systems in DC Microgrids document [2]), except for the requirement to be met (see Section 5.2.2), as the impedance of the fault loop is doubled, and U can be either the voltage between line conductors or between line conductor and neutral/mid-point conductor:

$$2 \cdot Z_s \times I_a \leq U \quad (5.3)$$

When an RCD is necessary, it must disconnect all live conductors in the circuit protected.

For continuous operation after the first fault, stronger requirements for the insulation coordination (creepage distances) apply in comparison to tripping at first fault.

The objective of implementing an IT system designed not to disconnect in the event of a first fault, is to have a continuity of service, that should not be jeopardized at the occurrence of a second fault. The first insulation fault has then to be monitored, generally by an insulation monitoring device (IMD), generating an alarm. It can theoretically also be monitored by a residual current monitor (RCM), but RCMs are first less sensitive and secondly cannot detect symmetrical insulation faults. In IT systems, the quick localization of the first earth fault by skilled people is mandatory, and a challenge. This

localization can be made thanks to an Insulation Fault Location System (IFLS) associated with the insulation monitoring device.

This is why it may be useful sometimes to divide large installations into smaller isolated parts. For example, PV installations usually have a low insulation resistance and high capacitance towards earth. For larger installations, PV sectors might be required to be connected with isolating DC/DC converters, in order to keep leakage currents low enough.

5.2.4 Automatic disconnection in IT with tripping at first earth fault

The IT-system usually offers the possibility to continue operation after the first fault, and as such is often used when the application requires high availability. But it can also be realised if the focus is on safety, as two faults are required for continuous earth currents. In order to prevent this, disconnection can happen at the first fault. In order to not overloading the creepage distances, disconnection of the faulty sector is required within 10 s according to the ODCA. For personal safety, time limits of IEC 60364-4-41 apply.

While it is sufficient to disconnect the faulty sector, localisation of the fault can be challenging. Residual Current Monitoring devices within the sectors can be used but are costly especially for larger installations. General ground faults can be detected (but not located) by an IMD, which is mandatory according to IEC 60364-4-41 (VDE 0100-411).

For an IT-system with tripping at the first fault, disconnection devices in all poles are required. Yet, fast short circuit disconnection can be realized in just one pole.

6 How to protect against other thermal effects

This chapter deals with fire hazard risks especially in sensitive plants and applications. It is covered by IEC 60364-4-42.

A first recent rule applies to protect AC and DC installations against fire due to fault currents: Except where IEC 60364-4-43:2023, Annex A, Annex B or Annex E apply and for a first earth fault in an IT installation, any short circuit current shall be disconnected within 5s.

Beyond the coordination between overcurrent protective devices and conductors thermal withstand (see Sections 4 and 5), other protective measures are required or recommended to reduce the risk of fire due to electrical installation, especially arc faults. Indeed, an arc fault creates a localized hot spot which carbonizes the insulating materials in the vicinity of the conductor. Carbon being a conductive material, it enables flow of the current which becomes excessive at various points.

This is why additional protections are required for locations where consequences of fire are severe:

- locations intended for people to sleep in:
 - facilities for the elderly and people with disabilities;
 - elementary educational establishments and kindergartens;
 - hotels and guest houses;
 - dwellings (e.g. houses, apartment blocks);
- locations intended to be occupied by a group of persons in:
 - facilities for the elderly and people with disabilities;
 - elementary educational establishments and kindergartens;
 - workplaces in high-rise buildings.
- locations with risks of fire due to the nature of processed or stored materials (classified BE2) in:
 - facilities for the elderly and people with disabilities;
 - hotels and guest houses;
 - elementary educational establishments and kindergartens;
- locations intended for storing of irreplaceable goods in the following buildings:
 - museums;
 - historical buildings;
 - libraries, archives and documentation centres;
- agricultural premises where livestock are kept.

In AC installations, protections against arc faults are based on two main different protection principles, not equivalent:

- **Residual Current Devices**, able to detect earth leakage currents which are too low (for example: 300 mA) for the other overcurrent protective devices, but sufficient to cause a fire;
- **Arc Fault Detection Devices (AFDD)**, which detect the presence of dangerous electric arcs:
 - in series (due to damaged conductor or connection not properly tightened)
 - in parallel (between two different conductors)

Figure 6.1: Arc in series and in parallel in a circuit

The synthesis of protective/ detection measures against arc faults for AC installations is the following:

Table 6.1: Protective/ detection measures against arc faults for AC installations

In locations where consequences of fire are severe	RCD	AFDD or other method minimizing the possibility of an arc fault	IMD & fault locators
For resistive load (heating element)	≤ 30 mA		Alternative for IT installations galvanically separated from a distribution system
Other circuits	≤ 300 mA		
Final circuit with at least one socket outlet		required	
Other final circuits		recommended	

Even if standard IEC 60364-4-42 is for the moment mainly AC oriented due to the lack of corresponding DC products/ solutions, its main approach and recommended solutions are relevant to take into account the fire hazard linked to DC arc fault currents. A future standard update concerning DC should be considered.

7 How to protect against overvoltage

This section provides a general overview of overvoltages and the methods used to protect electrical systems from them. It introduces different types of overvoltages, explains how equipment is categorized for protection purposes, and outlines key protection devices and concepts used in modern systems.

7.1 Introduction to overvoltages

According to IEC 60664-1, overvoltage refers to any voltage (between one phase conductor and earth or between phase conductors) having a peak value exceeding the corresponding peak value of maximum steady-state working voltage at normal operating conditions.

An overvoltage can disrupt equipment operation and emit electromagnetic radiation. Additionally, its duration may lead to a surge of energy within electrical circuits, potentially damaging equipment, impacting commercial activities and public services, or even endangering people (at hospital, or in structures with explosive atmospheres).

Several categories of overvoltage phenomena can be identified from their origin:

- Switching surges, for example, caused by the release of inductive energy stored in cables when current is suddenly interrupted during switching operations. The resulting voltage surge, proportional to the cable inductance and the rate of current change ($L \cdot di/dt$), adds to the nominal system voltage.
- Overshoots resulting from system instabilities, triggered by changes in network conditions, such as those occurring after fault clearance.
- Electrostatic discharge (ESD)-induced overvoltages, typically caused by the sudden release of static charge accumulated on the human body.
- Atmospheric overvoltages, originating from lightning strikes or other weather-related electrical disturbances.

But two main kinds of overvoltage are considered for protection:

- **Temporary overvoltage** (IEV 614-03-13), power frequency of relatively long duration. This definition obviously refers to phenomenon arising in AC networks during High-Voltage (HV) faults. When HV and LV earthing systems are all interconnected, there is no overvoltage constraint on equipment. For other cases, according to IEC 60364-4-44, the installation earthing design has to limit temporary overvoltage under the equipment permissible power-frequency stress voltage:
 - $U_0 + 1200$ V for a duration of fault less than 5s
 - $U_0 + 250$ V for a duration of fault higher than 5s.

For LVDC networks, the reference for temporary overvoltage levels and equipment withstand is the voltage bands principle described in IEC TR 63282 (see Section 11).

- **Transient overvoltage** (IEV 614-03-14), with a max duration of a few milliseconds, oscillatory or not, usually damped. The protection against this kind of overvoltage (of atmospheric origin or due to switching) is described in IEC 60364-4-44 (clause 443), and takes into account equipment impulse withstand voltage, that depends on their Overvoltage Category.

For LVDC networks, the reference for transient overvoltage levels and equipment withstand is the voltage bands principle described in IEC TR 63282 (see Section 11).

7.2 Introduction to Overvoltage Categories

"Overvoltage categories" (OVC) (also known as installation categories) are classifications used to define the level of transient overvoltage that electrical equipment is able to withstand.

Four different categories are defined in IEC 60664, that have to be selected depending on where and how equipment is installed in an electrical system:

- Category IV: For equipment at the origin of the electrical installation (e.g., electricity meters, main breakers). Exposed to the highest overvoltages, including those from lightning or utility faults.
- Category III: For fixed installation downstream and including the main distribution board. Must withstand higher surges due to proximity to the supply.
- Category II: For equipment connected to an electrical installation (for example appliances, portable tools, loads with pluggable or permanent connection to the electrical installation). Subject to moderate surges from switching.
- Category I: For equipment not directly connected to the mains supply (e.g., electronic devices) or connected with specific measures. Exposed to the lowest overvoltages.

7.3 Surge Protection Devices

Equipment must be selected according to the appropriate OVC based on location and exposure risk. When necessary, additional protection must be provided to mitigate both externally and internally generated transient overvoltages.

The standard IEC 60364-4-44, clause 443, specifies requirements for protection of electrical installations against transient overvoltages of atmospheric origin transmitted by the supply distribution system (including direct strikes to the supply system) and against switching overvoltages, particularly in:

- Public buildings,
- Industrial or commercial facilities,
- Installations with sensitive equipment (typically OVC I or II).

This standard underline that in general, switching overvoltages have lower amplitude than transient overvoltages of atmospheric origin. This is correct in the usual LV AC installations connected to the grid but may not be the case in an LVDC network with lots of converters.

Installation and selection guidelines are detailed in IEC 60364-5-53, especially Section 534, which:

- defines when and how SPDs should be installed,
- recommends optimal placement (e.g., at the service entrance, downstream in distribution panels),
- provides selection criteria based on the required protection level, coordination with other protective devices, and network characteristics.

However, the standard for DC SPD for power networks (IEC 61643-41) is still under development.

Proper coordination between SPDs installed at different levels of the installation is essential to ensure effective protection and avoid overstressing downstream devices.

7.4 Voltage coordination of LVDC microgrid equipment

LVDC microgrid equipment often relies on semiconductor-based architectures, which are inherently more sensitive to overvoltage than traditional electromechanical systems. For example, as illustrated in Figure 7.1, pre-charge circuits may use power semiconductors instead of mechanical relays. In such cases, standard semiconductors—typically rated for breakdown voltages around 1.2 kV for 700 V-class devices—must be protected against transient overvoltage. This is commonly achieved using input-stage protection components such as Metal Oxide Varistors (MOVs) or Transient Voltage Suppressors (TVS).

Figure 7.1: Equipment with integrated precharge circuit and overvoltage protection.

Conversely, switching devices within the microgrid can be a source of overvoltages. This creates a dual dynamic: while some equipment generates voltage transients, others are designed to suppress them. To prevent cross-interference and ensure system-wide reliability, voltage coordination must be addressed at the system level.

Another important consideration for enhancing system robustness is the coordination of clamping thresholds across all equipment. In the event of a surge, if the overvoltage protection thresholds are harmonized, the surge energy is distributed among multiple clamping devices. Without such coordination, the device with the lowest clamping threshold may absorb the entire energy, increasing the risk of failure.

In summary:

- Overvoltages from external sources (e.g. lightning) must be mitigated using appropriately rated SPDs, at a system level.
- Overvoltages generated by internal switching operations must be mitigated using appropriate equipment-level protection.
- Load-side overvoltage protection should be coordinated to ensure energy sharing and avoid overstressing individual components.

The reader can refer to [6] for more detailed information about the effects of switching overvoltages in LVDC microgrids.

7.5 Voltage Bands

This section presents how voltage levels are organized into bands to help manage system performance and protection.

7.5.1 According to IEC TR 63282

IEC TR 63282 defines:

- 6 voltages levels (U1 to U6) for temporary and continuous operation, with for example:
 - U2, as the minimum voltage for continuous operation with full functionality.
 - U3, as the maximum continuous operating voltage.
 - U4, as the maximum temporary operating voltage.
- 7 corresponding voltage bands, labelled B1 to B7 to:
 - Define acceptable voltage ranges for normal operation. $B3 = [U2; U3]$ is the nominal band.
 - Identify dead bands or critical thresholds where protective actions (like clamping or disconnection) may be required.
 - Support voltage coordination and EMC strategies.
- 4 Operation ranges with respect to time, from the Transient range R1 to the Continuous operating range R4.
- 7 system states depending on voltage ranges and bands.
 - A3 is the normal state.

These definitions are illustrated on **Figure 7.2** (extracted from IEC 63282:2024):

Figure 7.2: Voltage bands, time ranges and operation states according to Figure 3 in IEC 63282:2024

7.5.2 ODCA approach

ODCA does not define a fixed grid voltage, but works with voltage bands, in order to allow control of the load flow and load sharing with droop control. As nominal voltage, the ODCA system concept does specify two different values: 540 V and 650 V. Those values stem from ordinarily used components and global AC grids, in order to utilize existing devices without fundamental changes.

The overall voltage bands within ODCA are based on the IEC TR 63282 standard, with specific voltage values and times. The voltage levels and the respective band and function are depicted in Figure 7.3. While all voltage bands from B1 to B6 are acceptable, all but B3 must only be reached temporarily. As a deviation from IEC TR 63282, operating state S3 is divided into two parts: S3a and S3b, with different time ranges. The operating states as a function of voltage bands and time duration is shown in Figure 7.3. Depending on the operating state, equipment might be required to turn off, reduce its performance, or overarching grid actions (load shedding) is required. For details, refer to the ODCA system specification [5].

Band	Nominal voltage: 540 V	Nominal voltage: 650 V
B7	Forbidden band - Damage of devices is very likely	
U6	2000 V	
B6	Overvoltage protection band - Switching operations can cause this voltage range - Surge protection devices (SPDs) operate and try to protect devices	
U5	880 V	
B5	Temporary overvoltage band - Surge protection devices (SPD) are not active - Breakers disconnect in this band - Insulation and components shall withstand this for up to 5 s - Devices may lose functionality in order to protect themselves	
U4	800 V	
B4	Overvoltage band - Devices may reduce their power - This shall not last longer than 60s - Measures to reduce the voltage must be taken (e.g. charge storage, switch-on power resistors)	
U3	750 V	
B3	Nominal band - Normal operating range - Devices shall be operated permanently - Devices perform with their rated power	
U2	485 V	620 V
B2	Emergency band - Overload condition - Loads have to be reduced - AIC must only be operated for a few milliseconds	
U1	400 V	
B1	Blackout Band - Smart Breakers disconnect - Band will be used during pre-charging - Occurs briefly during short-circuit conditions	

Figure 7.3: ODCA Voltage bands (Source: ODCA System specification)

Upper voltage limit U_x in DC grid for nominal voltage 540 V / 650 V		Voltage band	S1: $t < 50 \mu s$	S2: $50 \mu s \leq t \leq 1 ms$	S3a: $1 ms \leq t \leq 5 s$	S3b: $5 s \leq t \leq 60 s$	S4: $t > 60 s$
Voltage ↑	U6: 2000 V →	B7	A7				
	U5: 880 V	B6	A6	A7			
	U4: 800 V	B5	A4	A5	A5	A7	A7
	U3: 750 V	B4	A3	A3	A3	A4	A5
	U2: 485 / 620 V	B3	A3	A3	A3	A3	A3
	U1: 400 V →	B2	A4	A4	A2	A2	A2
		B1	A4	A2	A1	A1	
Time →							

Figure 7.4: Operating states and duration according to ODCA (Source: ODCA System specification)

7.5.3 Current OS approach

The current OS approach [4] is fully aligned with IEC TR 63282 concerning voltage bands. More specifically, current OS explicitly specifies voltage coordination at system level:

- SPDs can be used to prevent entering the dead band above U6.
- In Current/OS Zones 3 and 4, switching devices must not generate overvoltage exceeding U5.
- In Current/OS Zones 3 and 4, clamping devices integrated into equipment must be coordinated, with clamping thresholds greater than U5 and lower than U6.

Figure 7.5: Current/OS defined voltage bands for 48 V, 175 V, 350 V, 700 V and 1400 V systems.

8 How to select & set protection devices

This section introduces general considerations for choosing and adjusting protection devices in electrical systems.

8.1 Selection of protective devices according to type of circuit and type of system earthing

The choice of protection device and the need for disconnection of conductors can differ depending on the system earthing and the type of circuit. The type of circuits is described Section 2.4, Figure 2.5:

- C1: circuit supplied from one end
- C2: circuit supplied from both ends
- C3: circuit supplied by multiple ends

The requirements for detection and disconnection of L+ and L- conductors for a TN-S system and for an IT system are mentioned in Section 4.1 and Section 5.2. They are analysed in this chapter in case of overload, pole-to-pole and pole-to-earth faults. As far as the document is focusing on 2-wire systems, the case of M is not fully considered in this chapter.

For information, extracts from the IEC 60364-4-43 July 2023 are given hereafter as they quoted several times in this section:

IEC 60364-4-43 July 2023

431.1.1 *Detection of overcurrent shall be provided for **all line conductors**, except where 431.1.2 applies. It shall cause the disconnection of the conductor in which the overcurrent is detected but not necessarily the disconnection of the other live conductors.*

431.1.2 *Detection of overcurrent is not required for a PEL conductor in DC circuits.*

431.2 Protection of neutral or mid-point conductor

431.2.1 AC circuits without triplen harmonics and DC circuits

*Where the cross-sectional area (CSA) of the neutral or mid-point conductor is at least equivalent to that of the line conductors, and the current in the neutral or mid-point conductor is expected not to exceed the value in the line conductors, **it is not necessary to provide overload current detection for the neutral or mid-point conductor or a disconnecting device for that conductor, except for IT systems where 431.2.2 applies.***

(...)

The neutral or mid-point conductor shall be protected against short-circuit currents. This protection may be achieved by the overcurrent protective devices in the line conductors. In case it is not necessary to provide short-circuit current detection for the neutral or mid-point conductor or a disconnecting device for that conductor. Except for disconnection, the requirements for a neutral conductor apply to a PEN conductor in AC systems, and the requirements for a mid-point conductor apply to a PEM conductor in DC systems.

431.2.2 Additional requirements for IT systems

(...)

*Where a circuit in an IT DC system includes a mid-point conductor, **overcurrent detection shall be provided for the mid-point conductor, causing the disconnection of all the live conductors of the corresponding circuit, including the mid-point conductor.***

8.1.1 Two-wire TN-S system with L- earthed at source

Table 8.1: Detection and disconnection rules for a two-wire TN-S system with L- earthed at the source. summarizes the detection and disconnection rules for L+ and L- conductors in a two-wire TN-S system. A quick synthesis of detection and disconnection rules concerning L+ and L- conductors for circuit C1, C2 & C3 is provided in this section.

Table 8.1: Detection and disconnection rules for a two-wire TN-S system with L- earthed at the source.

	Overcurrent detection	Disconnection
L+	X	L+ & L- if RCD L+ only possible if no RCD
L-	X *	L+ & L- if RCD L+ only possible if no RCD
M	Not necessary as $M_{csa} = L_{csa}$ * (csa : cross-sectional area)	

* As mentioned in Section 4.1, the question if L- connected to earth should be considered as a Mid-conductor is under consideration at IEC level.

To sum-up this part, there are three possible approaches:

- either to disconnect L+ with 1P protection and keep the L- conductor permanently solidly earthed, which requires implementing a reliable method to shut down the sources (Inter-tripping),
- or disconnect both poles, with the associated risk of leaving a part of the network in an unmonitored IT configuration; an inter-tripping would reduce this risk,
- or implement the SRC at the common point between sources (instead of at one source) and disconnect both poles; then only the limited parts connected to sources could be in IT system earthing without IMD.

8.1.1.1 Selection of protective devices of "C1" circuit – Earth fault in TN-S

If the protection against electric shocks is achieved by automatic disconnection of the supply, the following rules apply according to IEC 60364-4-41 Ed5.1. Figure 8.1 presents the situation of a fault between L+ and an exposed conductive part. In this case, the earth fault current circulates and can generate a dangerous touch voltage.

Figure 8.1: “C1” circuit in TN-S – protection against earth fault

The use of a **2P protective device** (Figure 8.2 left) is possible according to IEC 60364-4-41 Ed 5.1 and required if an RCD is used that disconnect all live conductors (Section 531.2.3.1). Only the M conductor is allowed not to be disconnected in TN, but today the L- in this TN-S configuration is not considered as a M conductor. **This is under consideration at the IEC committee.**

Use of a **1P Protective device** (Figure 8.2 right) is possible according to IEC 60364-41 Ed 5.1 if only an OCPD is used.

In both cases, the touch voltage is not dangerous, as the earth fault loop has been interrupted as shown in Figure 8.2.

Figure 8.2: “C1” circuit in TN-S – 2P & 1P earth fault protection

Figure 8.3 illustrates potential issues related to the non-disconnection of L- with RCDs in TN-S for a « C1 » circuit. A DC source S1 is feeding two loads L1 and L2.

Figure 8.3: “C1” circuit in TN-S – 1P protection with RCD

In case of L- to earth fault at Load 1, the protection device (RCD) L1 trips and disconnects only L+

- If L- is not disconnected, the TN-S system becomes a TN-C system. If this faulty circuit is not disconnected it will create an alternate return path to source(s), a permanent current in the PE may circulate, leading to a **risk of fire** (the PE conductor being not sized for this permanent constraint) and **risk of corrosion** if no upstream RCD detects the fault.
- A part of the Load 2 current can flow through the PE. Any **other RCD** protection between the SRC and the faulty circuit may **see the earth fault and trip**, which corresponds to a lack of selectivity.

In case of RCD protection, both polarities shall be disconnected when a spurious trip can happen. If the SRC is located inside a source, the disconnection of this source shall be studied carefully to keep L-referenced to earth or to ensure protection if the system earthing is changed to IT by the source disconnection.

8.1.1.2 Selection of protective devices of “C1” circuit – Short-circuit

In case of short-circuit between L+ and L- the overcurrent protection will detect the short-circuit current ($I_{Prot} = I_{sc}$), the residual current protection won't detect the fault as $I_{\Delta Prot} = 0 A$.

Figure 8.4: “C1” circuit in TN-S – protection against short-circuit

The use of **2P protection** is possible according to IEC 60364-4-43 Ed4, see Figure 8.5-left.

The use of **1P protection** (Figure 8.5 right) on L+ is not clearly mentioned in the IEC 60364-4-43 Ed4 (2023.07), except if L- is considered as a Neutral conductor. In this specific case, in a 2-wire circuit it could be considered that detecting and disconnecting one polarity is adequate, but it is not clearly written. **This is under consideration at the IEC committee.**

Figure 8.5: “C1” circuit in TN-S – 2P & 1P short-circuit protection

8.1.1.3 Selection of protective devices of “C1” circuit – Overload

This paragraph describes the case of an overload, in this configuration L+ and L- conductors have the same cross-section.

Figure 8.6: “C1” circuit in TN-S – protection against overload

The use of **2P protection** is possible according to IEC 60364-4-43 Ed4, see Figure 8.7-left.

The use of **1P protection** (Figure 8.7 left) on L+ is not clearly mentioned in the IEC 60364-4-43 Ed4 (2023.07), except if L- is considered as a Neutral conductor. In this specific case, in a 2-wire circuit it could be considered that detecting and disconnecting one polarity is adequate, but it is not clearly written. **This is under consideration at the IEC committee.**

Figure 8.7: “C1” circuit in TN-S – 2P & 1P overload protection

8.1.1.4 Selection of protective devices of “C2” circuit – Earth fault TN-S

This paragraph concerns the earth fault protection in the case of a circuit supplied from both ends: C2 circuit, typically Electrical Energy Storage Systems (EESS) or bidirectional Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment (EVSE) applications.

Figure 8.8 presents the case of an earth fault located between the two sources S1 and S2, the SRC is earthed at source 1. In this system, the protection device 1 could be able to trip the protection device 2 thanks to a reliable inter-tripping system.

Figure 8.8: “C2” circuit in TN-S – protection against earth fault (fault between protective devices)

2P and 1P protection scenarios are presented. First, the protection scheme without inter-tripping is considered.

The use of 2P protective device is possible in accordance with IEC60364-4-41 Ed 5.1 and required if RCDs are used that disconnects all live conductors (IEC 60531 Section 531.2.3.1), the only exception being Neutral in TN.

Protection Device 1 can detect the fault either by overcurrent protection as

- I_{Prot1} on L+ = I_{f1} , short-circuit current contribution from source S1
- I_{Prot1} on L- = I_{f2} , short-circuit current contribution from source S2 or by residual current detection if any ($I_{\Delta Prot 1} = I_{f1} + I_{f2}$).

Protection Device 2 may detect the fault only by overcurrent protection because $I_{\Delta Prot 2} = 0$.

- $I_{Prot2} = I_{f2}$, short-circuit current contribution from source S2 on both polarities

If the Protection 1 trips and disconnects the two polarities first, the circuit is fed by S2 under IT system earthing without Insulation Monitoring device. The system is now in IT with a first fault (Figure 8.9).

Figure 8.9: “C2” circuit in TN-S – 2P protection against earth fault without inter-tripping

An inter-tripping system could trip the protection device 2 and stop the source S2. In this case, only the limited part connected to the source 2 could be in IT system earthing without insulation monitoring (IM) (Figure 8.10).

Figure 8.10: “C2” circuit in TN-S – 2P protection against earth fault with inter-tripping

1P protective device without inter-tripping could be unsafe (Figure 8.11).

If the protection 1 detects the fault and disconnects L+ first, the source S2 still supplies a dangerous touch voltage. It may be difficult for protection 2 to detect an earth fault, if S2 is a PV source with low short-circuit current contribution or the earth loop impedance is high for instance. In this case, L- & PE conductors could be damaged by overcurrent (Figure 8.11).

Figure 8.11: “C2” circuit in TN-S – 1P protection against earth fault issue without inter-tripping

If the system is not equipped with an inter-tripping mechanism, and there is no way to detect the fault on S2 protection ($ID2 = 0$) the system is not well protected. An inter-tripping system is necessary to trip the protection device 2 and disconnect the source S2 as presented Figure 8.12.

Figure 8.12: "C2" circuit in TN-S – 1P protection against earth fault issue with inter-tripping

To conclude this part, there are three possible approaches:

- either to disconnect L+ with 1P protection and keep the L- conductor permanently solidly earthed, which requires implementing a reliable method to shut down the sources (Inter-tripping),
- or disconnect both poles, with the associated risk of leaving a part of the network in an unmonitored IT configuration; an inter-tripping would reduce this risk,
- or implement the SRC at the common point between sources (instead of at one source) and disconnect both poles; then only the limited parts connected to sources could be in IT system earthing without IMD.

8.1.1.5 Selection of protective devices of "C2" circuit –Earth fault in TN-S at a Source

The situation of a fault inside the source S2 is described Figure 8.13.

Figure 8.13: "C2" circuit in TN-S – 1P protection against earth fault issue (fault at the source side)

Protection Device 1 can detect the fault either by overcurrent protection as

- I_{Prot1} on L+ = I_{f1} , short-circuit current contribution from source S1
 - I_{Prot1} on L- = I_{f2} , short-circuit current contribution from source S2
- or by residual current detection if any ($I_{\Delta Prot 1} = I_{f1} + I_{f2}$).

Protection Device 2 can detect the fault either by overcurrent protection.

- I_{Prot2} on L+ = I_{f1} , short-circuit current contribution from source S1
 - I_{Prot2} on L- = I_{f2} , short-circuit current contribution from source S2
- or by residual current detection if any ($I_{\Delta Prot 2} = I_{f1} + I_{f2}$).

1P protective device without inter-tripping is not possible for the same reason as in Section 8.1.1.4 with the same consequences: dangerous touch voltage and potential overcurrent of L- and PE conductors.

Figure 8.14: “C2” circuit in TN-S – 1P protection against earth fault issue (fault at the source side)

An inter-tripping mechanism could resolve this issue by disconnecting the source S2 (see Section 8.1.1.4). The source S2 must be stopped to fully erase the fault.

The use of 2P protective device is possible and required if RCD are used that disconnects all live conductors (IEC 60364-5-53 Section 531.2.3.1), the only exception being Neutral in TN.

Figure 8.15: “C2” circuit in TN-S – 2P protection against earth fault issue (fault at the source side)

As soon as one protection detects and disconnects both polarities the system is safe as the earth fault current cannot flow back through the L- anymore. A part of the network remains in IT without IM (Figure 8.15).

8.1.1.6 Selection of protective devices of “C3” circuit

For “C3” circuits that can be supplied from more than two ends, the same outcome as for “C1” and “C2” circuits apply in case of short-circuit or earth-fault. The overload protection could be more complex, but this case is not covered in this revision of the document.

8.1.2 IT System

For the IT system, only second earth fault situations are covered in this section.

The main outcome of this section implies that **the protective device (associated with the “C1”, “C2”, or “C3” circuit) shall be able to detect and disconnect both polarities (L+ and L-)** This is required particularly when the L+ polarity has an earth fault on the source-side of the protective devices.

Note: Although only second earth fault situations are described in this section, the same outcome applies if disconnecting at the occurrence of the first earth fault.

8.1.2.1 Selection of protective devices of “C1” – Second earth fault in IT

Figure 8.16 illustrates that when a first earth fault occurs in an IT system, the fault current is considered negligible i.e. very low and doesn't present an electric shock risk. This is acknowledged in IEC 60364-4-41 Ed5.1, which implies there is no touch voltage limitation due to the negligibly low fault current in DC systems.

Figure 8.16: “C1” circuit in IT – first fault situation with limited touch voltage

Figure 8.17 shows an IT system with two earth faults and the fault current paths. On the left, the first earth fault occurs at the load on L+ and the second earth fault occurs on the other side of the protective device on L-. Conversely, on the right, the second earth fault occurs at the load on L- and the first earth fault occurs on the other side (i.e. the source-side) of the protective device on L+. In both situations, this can lead to dangerous touch voltages and therefore automatic disconnection of the supply is necessary.

Figure 8.17: “C1” circuit in IT – protection against second earth fault (with different second fault locations)

As shown in Figure 8.17, the earth fault current, depending on the location of the earth faults, can either flow through only the L+ or L- pole of the protective device. For this reason, **the protective device shall be able to detect and disconnect both polarities (L+ and L- as shown in Figure 8.18). This situation can be detected by overcurrent protection and residual current protection.**

Figure 8.18: “C1” circuit in IT – protection against second earth fault (with disconnection of all live conductors)

8.1.2.1 Selection of protective devices of “C2” – Second earth fault in IT

As for the “C1” circuit, Figure 8.19 illustrates for a “C2” circuit that when a first earth fault occurs in an IT system, the fault current is considered negligible and there is no dangerous touch voltage.

Figure 8.19: “C2” circuit in IT – first fault situation with limited touch voltage

If a second earth fault is considered between the two protective devices on the L- polarity (with the first earth fault being on the L+ polarity), the fault current paths are shown in Figure 8.20 .

Figure 8.20: “C2” circuit in IT – protection against second earth fault

Protection Device 1 can detect the fault only by overcurrent protection because $I_{\Delta Prot1} = 0$.

- $I_{Prot1} = I_{s1}$, short-circuit current contribution from source S1 on both polarities

Protection Device 2 can detect the fault either by overcurrent protection as

- I_{Prot2} on L+ = I_{s1} , short-circuit current contribution from source S1
 - I_{Prot2} on L- = I_{s2} , short-circuit current contribution from source S2
- or by residual current detection if any ($I_{\Delta Prot2} = I_{s1} + I_{s2}$).

In this example, if disconnection of only one (L+) polarity is done, the resulting touch voltage remains dangerous as shown in Figure 8.21. This is due to the earth fault loop associated with source 2 not being interrupted. However, if both polarities are disconnected, the dangerous touch voltage is mitigated, although source 2 remains in IT but without monitoring due to the disconnection of this source from the IMD.

Figure 8.21: “C2” circuit in IT – protection against second earth fault (1P and 2P disconnection)

For this reason and aligning with the conclusion of “C1” circuits, **the protective device (at both ends) shall be able to detect and disconnect both polarities (L+ and L-)**. This is required particularly when one polarity has an earth fault on the source-side of the protective devices.

8.1.2.2 Selection of protective devices of “C3” – Second earth fault in IT

For “C3” circuits that can be supplied from more than two ends, the same outcome for “C1” and “C2” circuits apply. **The protective device (at all ends) shall be able to detect and disconnect both polarities (L+ and L-)**.

8.2 Overcurrent protection

This part gives an overview of how overcurrent protection devices work and introduces different technologies used for this purpose.

8.2.1 Technologies & performances

This subsection outlines the main types of overcurrent protection devices and compares their functional characteristics, typical applications, and performance capabilities.

8.2.1.1 Fuses

Fuses have been widely used since the early 1900s and are still adopted today for protecting against overload and short-circuit currents. They are reliable and economical protective devices and are used in a variety of DC applications including solar PV, battery systems, distribution grids and systems with semiconductor devices.

Fuses are typically comprised of four main components: the fuse-link, the filler, the insulating body and the connection electrodes. Typical fuse constructions are shown in Figure 8.22 [7].

The fuse-link is commonly referred to as the fuse, as this includes an element that is designed to melt due to an overcurrent i.e. a current exceeding some value for some time. The element that is designed to melt is often made of flat silver or copper with restrictions (or weak spots) in the cross-section. Sometimes "M-effect" materials are added primarily for controlling operation in the overload range (IEC TR 60269-5:2014/AMD1:2020). The "M-effect", also known as the Metcalf effect, involves using a small amount of low-melting point alloy (often solder) attached to the fuse element. In case of low-level overcurrents, the fuse element heats up, causing the M-effect alloy to diffuse into the metal of the element increasing the resistance and shortening the time it takes for the fuse to blow compared to a fuse without the M-effect. A material referred to as a filler – which is typically graded quartz or similar – surrounds the melting element and helps to extinguish the arc, forcing and maintaining zero current [7]. Regarding the insulating body, it is generally in ceramic to ensure the mechanical protection of the fuse-link and filler material, as well as to contain the electrodynamic effects of the electrical arc. The connection electrodes allow the insertion of the fuse in the system, generally through a fuse-carrier.

Figure 8.22: Typical fuse constructions, left: square body, right: round body.

When a fuse is subjected to an overcurrent, two stages describe the fuse operation. The pre-arcing (melting) phase involves the heating of the fuse element to a point at which it melts. The duration of this phase will depend on the magnitude of the overcurrent, as well as the composition of the fuse. This is then followed by an arcing phase in which an arc forms at the weak-spot(s) of the element, opposing the source voltage and effectively bringing down the current up to the interruption. The sum of these phases is the fuse total operating time, also referred to as the total clearing time. An example of these phases for a short-circuit current is shown in Figure 8.23 [7].

Figure 8.23: Example of pre-arcing and arcing phases of a fuse.

Fuse manufacturers normally provide values of pre-arcing (melting) I^2t which is typically a minimum value, and total operating I^2t which is a maximum value. This helps in the fuse selection and protection assessment process.

To illustrate this further, an example of a 16A gPV fuse with a pre-arcing I^2t of 30 A²s breaking a short-circuit current is provided in Figure 8.24. The transition from the pre-arcing (melting) stage to the arcing stage is indicated by the fuse voltage measurement (yellow trace), which occurs in this instance when the I^2t exceeds 30 A²s. The arcing phase remains until the current is forced to zero, at which the voltage across the fuse equals the system (bus) voltage.

Figure 8.24: Example of a fuse breaking a short-circuit current (primarily a capacitor discharge)

IEC 60269 is the applicable standard for low-voltage fuses, which incorporate current-limiting fuse-links. There are several parts to this standard. Some key parts relating to DC systems are:

- Part 1: General requirements
- Part 4: Supplementary requirements for fuse-links for the protection of semiconductor devices
- Part 6: Supplementary requirements for fuse-links for the protection of solar photovoltaic energy systems
- Part 7: Supplementary requirements for fuse-links for the protection of batteries and battery systems

One fundamental aspect of fuse-links according to this standard (Edition 5.0 2024-08) is the **utilisation class**, such as “gM”, involving the **breaking range** and **utilisation category**. The first letter of the utilisation class – “g” in this example – indicates the breaking range. The second letter – “M” in this example – indicates the utilisation category.

The **breaking range** is indicated by two letters:

- “g” means the fuse has a full-range and therefore is suitable for overload and short-circuit protection.
- “a” means the fuse has a partial-range and therefore is only suitable for short-circuit protection and are usually characterised with a minimum breaking current, that is to say is a minimum current value which causes the fuse to blow and break the current. Below this value and the nominal current, the fuse will blow but may not break the current as arcing continues until an external event interrupts the current.

If “a” type fuses are used, an additional protective device is required for protection against overload current, provided overload can occur. As a general guideline, 10 times the fuse rating is typically regarded as the critical point between the classification of an overload or short-circuit current. At or above 10 times the fuse rating is a short-circuit current, and below this (but above the fuse rating) is an overload current (IEC TR 60269-5).

The **utilisation class** letter generally defines the time-current characteristics, including time-current gates and conventional times and currents. The conventional times are long duration (e.g. ≥ 1 hour) and the gates are of shorter duration. The utilisation category letter(s) indicates the area of application as shown in Table 8.2.

Table 8.2: Overview of common fuse-links for DC systems (non-exhaustive list)

Utilisation class	Application	Breaking range	Time constant
gG	General purpose	Full-range	15 to 20 ms
gM	Motor circuit protection	Full-range	15 to 20 ms
aR	Semiconductor protection	Partial-range	10 to 15 ms
aR + VSI	Semiconductor protection	Partial-range	1 to 3 ms
gPV	Solar photovoltaic protection	Full-range	1 to 3 ms
gBat	Battery protection	Full-range	1 to 3 ms
aBat	Battery protection	Partial-range	1 to 3 ms

Fuses used for semiconductor protection are required to operate more rapidly than fuses for other applications. Semiconductors such as Insulated-Gate Bipolar Transistors (IGBTs), diodes, MOSFETs (Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor Field-Effect Transistor), and Gate Turn-Off Thyristors (GTOs) are not capable to withstand the level of thermal stress (I^2t) that other components of comparable ratings, such as cables and busbars, can typically withstand. Fuse-links for semiconductor protection are covered by IEC 60269-4 and have utilisation categories of “aR”, “gR”, or “gS”. “aR” fuses have primarily been used to protect semiconductors against the effects of short-circuits, however full-range fuse-links are available that are either optimised for low I^2t (“gR”) or low power dissipation (“gS”).

The term “VSI fuse-link” is proposed by the IEC 60269-4 standard to describe fuses that can break the discharge current of a Voltage Source Inverter (VSI) DC-link capacitor. Indeed, the current supplied by the capacitor is usually characterised by a very high rate-of-rise and low equivalent time constant (usually in the range of 1 to 3ms), leading to additional tests for DC applications. For this reason, the manufacturers must clearly state that the fuse is for VSI protection, when the required tests of IEC 60269-4 have been successfully performed. For protection of VSI semiconductors, only fuses that are marked by the manufacturer as suitable shall be used.

The key performance metrics of fuses, other than the **breaking range** and **utilisation class**, include:

- **Rated voltage:** The maximum voltage the fuse is designed to operate at.
- **Rated current:** The maximum sustained current that can be carried (without damage); derating factors may need to be applied depending on the installation conditions.
- **Breaking capacity:** The maximum prospective current that can be safely interrupted without damage. This is linked with the rated voltage and the time constant (L/R) of the short-circuit loop.
- **Current-limiting capability:** Fuses to IEC 60269 are current-limiting, meaning they can significantly reduce the peak prospective current and the let-through energy (I^2t) during a fault. This enhances protection performance and minimizes thermal and mechanical stress on downstream components.

8.2.1.2 Electromechanical Breaker

An EMCB is a mechanical switching device designed to make, carry, and interrupt current of an electrical circuit. EMCBs offer reliable protection and are available with a wide range of performance characteristics, meeting the needs of diverse and demanding applications. There are several types of EMCBs, including miniature circuit-breakers (MCBs) for small-power applications, and moulded-case circuit-breakers (MCCBs) and air circuit-breakers (ACBs) for medium- and high-power applications. Figure 8.25 shows examples of three types of low-voltage circuit breakers.

Figure 8.25: MCB (left), MCCB (middle), and ACB (right) circuit-breakers

Low-voltage circuit-breakers typically have an embedded trip unit. The purpose of the trip unit is to detect overcurrent conditions and initiate the tripping of the EMCB. Furthermore, opening of the EMCB can be initiated by manual control (and sometimes remote control) and by auxiliary control on the mechanism, such as an undervoltage release. Unlike fuses, once the fault that caused tripping has been resolved, EMCBs don't require replacing and are immediately ready for re-closure (providing service capacities are respected).

Typically, an EMCB consists of the following components:

- The breaking system, with the fixed and moving contacts and the arc chamber
- The latching mechanism which is unlocked by the action of the trip device if abnormal currents are detected. This mechanism is also linked to the operation of the circuit-breaker handle.
- The trip unit acting on the breaking mechanism:
 - Either a thermal-magnetic trip unit in which
 - a "thermomechanical" element, generally a bimetallic strip, responds to an overload condition, and
 - a magnetic circuit actuates a paddle from a current threshold in a short-circuit condition,
 - or an electronic trip unit comprising sensors, processing and control electronics, and an actuator
- Upstream and downstream power circuit terminals
- An external casing ensuring the mechanical fixation of the different components and protection against shocks

The primary performance requirements for low-voltage electromechanical circuit-breakers are specified in two main standards: IEC 60898 and IEC 60947. While IEC 60898 is related to household and similar applications, IEC 60947, in particular Section 1 and 2, governs circuit-breakers for industrial applications and will therefore be the focus of this section. This standard is applicable for circuit-breakers in systems up to and including 1000 Vac or 1500 Vdc.

In DC systems, it is common for the current to flow both ways through an EMCB. Whether the circuit-breaker is polarised or not is a very important point regarding the device technology. Polarised circuit-breakers are not designed for this case. Therefore, a non-polarised circuit-breaker is required if there can be a change in the current direction.

The performance characteristics of EMCBs for DC application are provided in manufacturer's literature. Some key performance metrics include:

- **Rated voltage:** The maximum voltage the circuit-breaker is designed to operate at.
- **Rated current:** The maximum sustained current that can be carried (without tripping); derating factors may need to be applied depending on the installation conditions.
- **Tripping limits, characteristics, and response time:** The speed at which the circuit-breaker detects and responds to overcurrent conditions.
- **Current-limiting capability:** Some circuit-breakers are designed to be current-limiting, meaning they can significantly reduce the peak prospective current and the let-through energy (I^2t) during a fault. This enhances protection performance and minimizes thermal and mechanical stress on downstream components.
- **Ultimate breaking capacity:** The maximum prospective current that can be safely interrupted without damage. This is linked with the rated voltage and the time constant (L/R) of the short-circuit loop for DC EMCBs.
- **Service breaking capacity:** The ability to interrupt a short-circuit multiple times while retaining all or part of its pre-fault operational characteristics.

It is important to acknowledge that not all circuit-breakers are designed to interrupt DC current. For example, the use of an AC circuit-breaker may not be suitable for DC application, even when poles are connected in series, and could pose series safety risks. For protection of DC circuits or DC applications, only EMCBs that are marked by the manufacturer as suitable for direct current shall be used.

8.2.1.3 Semiconductor Circuit-Breaker

Terminology

The terms "**Semiconductor Circuit Breakers**" and "**Solid State Circuit Breakers**" are often used interchangeably, but there are subtle differences in their usage and implications.

Semiconductor Circuit Breakers refer to circuit breakers that utilize semiconductor devices to control and interrupt the flow of electrical current. These devices include power semiconductors like IGBTs, MOSFETs, and thyristors. This terminology also covers **SCHCBs**, which combine semiconductor and mechanical switching elements. On the other hand, **SSCBs** specifically denote circuit breakers that rely entirely on semiconductor components for switching and breaking and not on mechanical parts.

The term "**Solid State Circuit Breaker**" is more commonly used and recognized in academia and literature to describe circuit breakers that use semiconductor devices exclusively for switching and protection. This term emphasizes the absence of mechanical components and highlights the use of solid-state technology.

However, according to PT 60947-10, the most suitable name is **Semiconductor Circuit Breaker**. PT 60947-10 is a project team within the IEC (International Electrotechnical Commission) that is responsible for drafting and developing the standard IEC 60947-10. This terminology is recommended to ensure consistency and clarity in the industry standards. While "**Solid State Circuit Breaker**" is also commonly used, PT 60947-10 specifically refers to these devices as Semiconductor Circuit Breakers.

In summary, while both terms refer to circuit breakers that use semiconductor devices, "**Semiconductor Circuit Breaker**" is the more appropriate terminology to describe breakers that rely entirely on semiconductor components for their operation.

Standards

Some standards related to Solid-State Circuit Breakers are the below:

IEC 60947-10 is a standard being developed by the IEC within SC 121A for low-voltage switchgear and control gear, specifically focusing on semiconductor circuit-breakers. The standard aims to provide global alignment on key standardization issues related to these devices. The scope of IEC 60947-10 includes semiconductor circuit-breakers for protection, isolation, and switching intended to be connected to circuits with a rated voltage not exceeding 1,000 V AC or 1,500 V DC.

The standard covers various aspects of semiconductor circuit-breakers, including their classification, performance requirements, and testing procedures. It distinguishes between unidirectional and bidirectional protection, as well as unidirectional and bidirectional current flow. The standard also specifies the use of mechanical switching elements connected in series with semiconductor switching elements for isolation functions.

UL 489I offers a certification path for solid-state circuit breaker manufacturers, becoming an important industry standard. The requirements cover solid-state molded-case circuit breakers (SSCB) and solid-state hybrid molded-case circuit breakers (SSHCB) rated up to 1,000 VAC and 1,500 VDC. These devices switch using semiconductors and have an integral air gap for isolation. The requirements assume that these devices may provide service entrance, feeder, or branch circuit protection per the National Electrical Code® (NEC), ANSI/NFPA 70®.

Additionally, **UL 489I** covers solid-state molded-case switches and solid-state hybrid molded-case switches also rated up to 1,000 VAC and 1,500 VDC. The requirements assume that the devices may need auxiliary control power to function. The document is under review at UL Standards and Engagement to attain the status of a consensus standard.

Technology description

SSCBs are designed to replace traditional electro-mechanical circuit breakers, offering advanced and intelligent solutions for modern power distribution systems. These innovative devices integrate multiple functionalities into a single unit, including protection, actuation, load control, diagnostics, metering, and secure communication. SSCBs utilize power semiconductors, such as IGBTs and MOSFETs, to make and break electrical circuits. This allows for faster switching times, typically in the range of microseconds, compared to the milliseconds required by traditional mechanical circuit breakers.

Apart from semiconductor devices, other key components in SSCBs include the gate driver circuit, control unit, current and voltage sensors, heat sink or cooling system, auxiliary power supply, communication interface, clamping and energy absorption circuits. These components work together to monitor and control electrical parameters, ensuring the SSCB operates efficiently and safely, even in the absence of main power.

One of the key advantages of SSCBs is their ability to provide noise-less and wear-free load switching. Unlike mechanical circuit breakers, which rely on physical contacts that can degrade over time, SSCBs use semiconductor components that do not suffer from contact erosion or electric arcs. This results in

a longer lifespan and reduced maintenance requirements regarding the number of electrical operations.

Unidirectional/Bidirectional SSCBs

SSCBs can be distinguished based on their ability to handle unidirectional or bidirectional power flow and static protection. Unidirectional power flow in SSCBs refers to the movement of electrical energy in a single direction, typically from the power source to the load. These SSCBs are designed to handle power flowing in one direction and are marked to indicate the line and load terminals. They must be connected correctly to function properly. Unidirectional SSCBs are commonly used in applications where power only needs to flow from the source to the load, such as in traditional power distribution systems.

Bidirectional power flow, on the other hand, allows electrical energy to move in both directions, enabling energy exchange between the power source and the load. Bidirectional SSCBs do not have markings to indicate line and load terminals and can handle power flow in either direction without causing damage. These SSCBs are essential for systems with bidirectional power flow, such as energy storage systems and EVSE.

Performances & potential limitations

In a semiconductor circuit breaker, bidirectional power semiconductors are responsible for both providing continuous current flow and switching it on and off. Since no mechanical parts need to be moved, these breakers operate very quickly, typically in less than ten microseconds after a fault current is detected. This sometimes allows to trigger and switch within the capacitive discharging phase of a short circuit, which is something an EMCB is (usually) way to slow for. This rapid operation results in significantly less fault energy compared to electromechanical or hybrid breakers. Furthermore, SSCBs operation presents no bouncing and no arc. This makes a frequency-based arc-fault detection easier.

Besides, SSCBs present specific limitations related to the properties of semiconductor components. Due to their thermal and electromechanical withstand limits, these components are highly sensitive to abnormal current conditions. As a result, SSCBs often propose low trip current thresholds as they are unable to tolerate prolonged overloads, short circuits, or inrush currents. This sensitivity imposes strict constraints on system design, particularly regarding protection coordination and startup procedures. Effective pre-charge systems must be implemented to limit inrush currents. Some SSCB topologies embed an inductor to limit the slope of current, to guarantee a safe operation of the semiconductor.

Another drawback of semiconductor breakers is greater power loss at rated current due to the forward voltage drop of the semiconductors. Steps must be taken to dissipate this power loss, especially at higher rated currents. One approach to improve both loss performance and overcurrent withstand capability is to increase the amount of silicon used, which, however, leads to a significant cost increase.

The basic structure of a semiconductor breaker is shown Figure 8.26 [8]. This topology includes a clamping system to absorb and dissipate the breaking energy (here a varistor), and current measurement (here a shunt). The design of the clamping system determines the maximum switching overvoltage of the device. It also includes serial isolation contacts to reliably separate the two poles. Back-to-back transistors are needed to set up a bidirectional circuit-breaker. The switching operations are completely arc-free, and the possible number of switching cycles is virtually unlimited. The current-carrying capacity can be increased and power loss reduced by connecting semiconductor modules in parallel.

An example of a characteristic tripping curve for a semiconductor breaker with a rated current of 16A is shown in Figure 8.27. Figure 8.27 shows that current/time profiles below the curve are permissible, while the breaker trips above the curve. The area at the upper left (< 2 times the rated current) is the overload range, where the breaker trips significantly faster at higher currents.

Figure 8.26: Schematic circuit diagram of a single-pole bidirectional semiconductor breaker.

Figure 8.27: Typical tripping curves of a semiconductor breaker

While electromechanical circuit breakers and fuses sometimes struggle to interrupt DC currents when the system voltage is high, SCCBs offer reliable DC current interruption.

However, depending on the topology of the clamping system, SSCBs like presented Figure 8.26 may generate significant overvoltage during the interruption process. As overvoltage may damage surrounding equipment and disturb system operations, the current draft version of IEC 60947-10 standard requires SCCB manufacturers to specify the maximum switching overvoltage of the device.

To limit the switching overvoltages, alternative SCCB topologies exist, such as the bidirectional surge-less topology presented in Figure 8.28. In this configuration, when the circuit-breaker operates, the capacitor absorbs the inductive energy of the healthy part of the network, while the energy of the faulty section is freewheeled through the corresponding diode. This significantly reduces the switching overvoltage and its potential impact on the system. Additionally, the embedded capacitor can contribute to selectivity (see [1]).

Figure 8.28: surge-less SCCB topology

8.2.1.4 SemiConductor Hybrid Circuit-Breaker

In a hybrid breaker, a mechanical low-impedance contact is connected in parallel with a semiconductor module for interruption. This configuration combines the benefits of low power loss and faster interruption than is the case with an exclusively mechanical breaker. Figure 8.29, from [9], shows a schematic diagram of a hybrid breaker with mechanical contacts (highlighted in yellow) for continuous current and power semiconductors (highlighted in orange) for interrupting the current. Parallel to both devices, a varistor limits the voltage and dissipates the remaining energy in the circuit after the semiconductor module is switched off.

To achieve two-pole isolation, both poles are always disconnected in the event of a fault; in the Figure 8.29 this is shown by the isolation contacts (green). A coil (rated for to the current-carrying capacity of the switching elements) is typically installed in series with the hybrid breaker to slow-down the increase of current if a fault occurs. The coil, in turn, adds to power loss and requires additional installation space.

Figure 8.29: Schematic circuit diagram of a single-pole hybrid breaker.

The hybrid breaker is switched off as follows (both during normal operation and in the event of a fault):

- A signal is sent to the mechanical contact's actuator to open it and put the semiconductor module in a conductive state.
- When the mechanical contact first opens, a short arc is formed with a typical voltage of about 20 volts (with the breakers used in DC-INDUSTRIE², this occurred about 250 μ s after the switch-off signal). This voltage is significantly larger than the forward voltage of the semiconductor module (approximately three volts).
- The current commutates from the mechanical contact to the semiconductor module. A low inductance in the current loop between the two current paths is essential to ensure a fast commutation and rapid extinction of the arc.
- The mechanical contact continues opening. When it has opened sufficiently to withstand the returning voltage, the semiconductor is switched off and the current commutes to the parallel-connected varistor, which limits the voltage and reduces the current to zero.

Finally, the insulation contacts are opened without any current flowing, thus completing the procedure. The sequence is reversed at power-up. First the insulation contacts close, then the semiconductor is switched on, and finally the mechanical contacts close.

² Available on: https://dc-industrie.zvei.org/fileadmin/DC-Industrie/Praesentationen/DC-INDUSTRIE2_Project-overview_en_E.pdf

SCHCBs offer several advantages over traditional circuit breakers, making them a preferred choice in many applications. Here are the main advantages:

1. **Fast Fault Interruption:** SCHCBs can interrupt a fault current in a few tens of microseconds once the fault has been detected by an electronic current measurement unit. This rapid response time is significantly faster than traditional electromechanical circuit breakers, which helps in minimizing damage to sensitive equipment.
2. **Overcurrent and Thermal Limits:** The overcurrent and thermal limits of SCHCBs are comparable to traditional electromechanical circuit breakers. This means they can handle similar levels of current and thermal stress, ensuring reliable protection.
3. **Efficient Energy Clearing:** The voltage clamping circuit (VCC) in SCHCBs is connected in parallel to the power semiconductor switch (PSS), and its clamping voltage is selected to be lower than the breakdown voltage of the semiconductor switches used in the PSS. This ensures that the remaining energy can be cleared quickly, enhancing the overall efficiency of the breaker.
4. **Safe Isolation:** SCHCBs provide mechanical switching contacts connected in series for safe isolation purposes, similar to electromechanical circuit breakers. This ensures that the breaker can safely isolate the circuit when needed.
5. **Ultra-Fast Switching and High Efficiency:** SCHCBs offer ultra-fast switching and high efficiency during normal operation. This makes them suitable for protecting sensitive equipment from long-period overload and instant short-circuit conditions.

Potential Limitations:

1. **Interruption Speed:** While SCHCBs are faster than traditional electromechanical breakers, their interruption speed is slower than that of SCCBs. This may limit their effectiveness in certain high-speed applications.
2. **Complexity and Cost:** SCHCBs are more complex and may be more expensive to manufacture and maintain compared to traditional electromechanical breakers. The integration of both mechanical and semiconductor components adds to the complexity.
3. **Leakage Current:** After the remaining energy has been cleared, there is still a leakage current flowing through the VCC for a few tens of milliseconds until the mechanical switching contacts (MSCs) open their contacts, switching off the leakage current. This may affect the overall performance in certain applications.

Similarly to SCCBs, SCHCBs are also classified based on their ability to handle unidirectional or bidirectional power flow and static protection.

Unidirectional SCHCBs: These circuit breakers have a single main semiconductor valve that is able to interrupt current in one direction only. If the current is high in the opposite direction, the DC CB will be permanently closed.

Bidirectional SCHCBs: These circuit breakers are designed to interrupt current in both directions. They retain the performance of hybrid DC CBs with bidirectional current interruption while reducing semiconductor count, DC CB size, and weight.

8.2.2 Selection criteria

The common criteria that have to be considered are:

- Technical characteristics
Some characteristics like system earthing, rated current, rated voltage, breaking capacity, di/dt and max switchable inductance may not be (yet?) available for certain technologies.

- Capacity of the system to deal with inrush currents
Fast technologies are more sensitive to inrush currents, which can jeopardize the system resilience. It is then necessary to implement a pre-charging system, at the most relevant level (load, protection, bus, converter...)
- Selectivity between protections in the system
Selectivity is highly important to ensure optimized system availability. However, the requirement for selectivity highly depends on applications. The selectivity topic is in the scope of Shift2DC D2.2.D Selectivity in DC systems [1].
- Reference interoperability rules:
The system may be submitted to a reference of rules to be considered as a whole (COS, ODCA...) and including the protection devices technology.
- Usual constraints
Habits, cost, size, maintenance may be other constraints to take into account.

A key criterium is also the converter technology with respect to short-circuit behaviour: limiting or non-limiting (also called “fault feeding”):

- With a non-limiting converter, there should be an internal rapid protection, protecting the converter against high fault currents and the installation against fire. However, an additional rapid breaking external protection may be needed to protect the converter by avoiding uncontrolled input-to-output current and recharging of the internal capacitors. In case of fault in the LVDC system, it may not be acceptable that the internal protection melt/trip before the external protection nearer to the fault as it would generate a maintenance task. So only very rapid breaking technologies (static) are relevant for fault protections in the system be coordinated with converter internal protection. Protection devices then react on capacitive discharge currents.
- With a limiting converter, there is no need for an internal rapid protection, so this coordination issue does not exist, which allows all protection technologies. However, the limited current output of converters has an impact on the capacity of protection devices to detect fault currents. Slower breaking technologies which may not be able to detect capacitive discharge currents could be used, but they must be able to detect steady-state low fault currents.

8.2.3 Selection & setting

8.2.3.1 Fuses

Fuses do not have settings and thus can't be adjusted. The performance and behaviour of a fuse in a system is determined only by the fuse selection and the system characteristics. For a given system, to alter the behaviour, the fuse-link must be replaced with another type. Thus, to select fuses for DC application, it is critical to understand several aspects:

- **Type of overcurrent protection required:** For the selection of the fuse breaking range i.e. full-range or partial-range.
- **Nature of the system to protect:** For the selection of the fuse utilisation category.
- **System operational voltage:** For the selection of the fuse rated voltage, while considering the permitted voltage ranges.
- **System operational current:** For the selection of the fuse rated current i.e. the maximum current that can be carried without deterioration.
- **System earthing:** For the selection of the number of protected conductors.

- For example, in an IT (isolated) system, a second earth fault situation can result in insufficient automatic disconnection if protective devices are not installed on all line conductors, subjecting conductors to excessive overcurrents and stress.
- It shall be noted that if disconnection of several conductors is necessary, additional switching will be required in combination with fuses.
- **Prospective maximum and minimum short-circuit current:** For the selection of the fuse breaking capacity and assessment of the time-current characteristics including minimum breaking current.
- **Installation conditions and specificity of the circuit/equipment being protected:** For the selection of any applicable fuse derating factors (such as temperature), consideration of current magnitudes (such as inrush currents and cyclic loadings), and consideration of equipment withstand (such as I^2t energy withstand).

The next paragraphs propose general guidelines to select a fuse for a given application. The guidelines must be adapted for each application, as described in IEC TR 60269-5 and manufacturer recommendations, if any.

Fuse type

The first step is to select a fuse corresponding to the application to protect. If a complementary device is used to protect against overload, “a” type fuses can be used, otherwise “g” type must be used. The reader can refer to Table 8.2 for an overview of commonly used fuse types for DC systems, as well as IEC TR 60269-5:2014/AMD1:2020.

Voltage rating

The selection of the fuse must ensure that the following equation is valid:

$$V_n \geq U_4 \quad (8.1)$$

Where V_n is the fuse nominal voltage and U_4 is the system maximal temporary operating voltage.

Current rating – Without overload

The most basic criteria to cover by the fuse is that the maximal steady-state load current I_B , passing through the fuse, is lower or equal to the maximum permissible continuous fuse current. To determine this value, [7] propose to use the following formula:

$$I_{DC,max} \leq I_n \times K_t \times K_e \times K_v \times K_a \times K_b \quad (8.2)$$

Where I_n is the fuse rated current [A], K_t the ambient temperature correction factor, K_e the thermal connection factor, K_v the cooling air correction factor, K_a the high altitude correction factor, and K_b the fuse load constant.

This last parameter normally has a value of 1.0 for porcelain body fuses and 0.8 for fibre body fuses. The different coefficients are usually provided by the fuse manufacturer and/or their literature.

Overload capability

In case of expected transient overload and/or pulsed current, it is necessary to make sure that the fuse-element cannot be damaged. The maximum overload current $I_{overload,max}$ that can be imposed on a fuse depends upon the duration and frequency of occurrence. To determine this value, [7] proposes to use the following formula:

$$I_{overload,max} \leq \alpha \times I_t \quad (8.3)$$

where α is an attenuation factor provided by Table 8.3, I_t is the melting current corresponding to the duration t of the overload event as read from the time-current curve of the fuse.

Table 8.3: Attenuation factor for fuse

Frequency	Overloads ($\geq 1s$)	Impulse loads ($< 1s$)
Less than one time per month	0.8	0.7
Less than twice per week	0.7	0.6
Several times a day	0.6	0.5

Short-circuit protection

Special attention shall be given to the fuse breaking range when selecting fuses for short-circuit protection. As previously mentioned, partial-range fuses have a minimum breaking current which must be respected to avoid thermal risk. This minimum breaking current is provided by the fuse manufacturer and is normally identified on the time-current characteristic curve. A typical curve from IEC 60269 is provided in Figure 8.30, where the minimum breaking current is defined as $k_2 I_n$ at the extremity of the fuse operating characteristic.

If protection against overcurrents lower than the minimum breaking current ($k_2 I_n$ in this case) is required, another suitable overcurrent protective device is needed illustrated by the additional time-current characteristic (bold dashed line) in Figure 8.30 [10]. In summary, it shall be ensured that the prospective minimum short-circuit current exceeds the minimum breaking current for partial-range fuses.

Figure 8.30: Time-current characteristic of an "a" type fuse link (see Section 11).

Coordination with the protected system

From an overcurrent point of view, it is critical that the fuse limits the thermal stress on the system to be protected, while ensuring that the current limits of the system are not exceeded. These different criteria are described in Section 4.

For fuses, the let-through thermal constraint is commonly referred to as the “operating” or “clearing” I^2t (i.e. the I^2t integral extended over the fuse total clearing time) and shall be provided by the fuse manufacturer. Additionally, the fuse current limitation characteristics, describing the limited peak current, shall also be provided by the manufacturer. However, this can also be estimated by computing the RMS prospective short-circuit current (i.e. the current that will flow through the fuse), compare it with the pre-arcing Time-current Characteristics (TCC) of the fuse and check that the maximal ratings of the system are not exceeded (see Figure 8.31). This not only estimates the limited peak current, but also indicates when the fuse starts arcing. This method may be required in the case of capacitor discharge for example, where the L/R time constant is not known or obvious. This transformation can be done using the equation:

$$I_{RMS}(t_1) = \sqrt{\frac{\int_0^{t_1} i^2 dt}{t_1}} \quad (8.4)$$

where I_{RMS} is the RMS current, i is the actual instantaneous current signal, and t_1 is the evolving time [5]. An example of this is shown in Figure 8.31, where the melting point shall be derived using the RMS of the actual current signal. It shall be acknowledged that in some DC applications, the actual and RMS currents can differ significantly, hence it is important to consider this.

Figure 8.31: Fuse pre-arcing time-current characteristic with prospective short-circuit current

The coordination of the fuse with the protected system, includes to check that the overvoltage generated during the arcing phase, if any, can be withstood by the system. The arc voltage can be estimated empirically by doing tests, or analytically by using the manufacturer datasheet, as presented in [7] where the arc voltage is mainly dependent on the system time constant and voltage.

8.2.3.2 Electromechanical Breaker

Most DC EMCBs, specifically MCCBs and ACBs, typically offer both overload and short-circuit protection with the ability to adjust the overload and/or short-circuit protection settings. This is beneficial for the user, to optimise the design of the power system and offers the opportunity to fine-tune the settings once the installation is energised. Therefore, the performance and behaviour of an EMCB in a system is a function of the EMCB selection and settings, as well as the system characteristics.

To ensure protection when setting the device, the rules given in Sections 4 and 5 regarding overcurrent (overload and short-circuit) protection and earth fault protection, respectively, should be followed. Thus, to select EMCBs for DC application, it is critical to understand several aspects:

- **Type of overcurrent protection required:** For the selection of a circuit-breaker offering overload and/or short-circuit protection.
- **Nature of the system to protect:** To determine if the EMCB must be non-polarised or not due to a unidirectional or bidirectional current flow.
- **System operational voltage:** For the selection of the EMCB rated voltage and number of poles required in series to participate in the current interruption, while considering the permitted voltage ranges.
- **System operational current:** For the selection of the EMCB rated current i.e. the maximum current that can be carried without deterioration.
- **System earthing:** For the selection of the number of protected conductors.
- **Prospective maximum and minimum short-circuit current:** For the selection of the EMCB breaking capacity (included tested time constant, L/R) and assessment of the trip unit and time-current characteristics.
- **Installation conditions and specificity of the circuit/equipment being protected:** For the selection of any applicable EMCB derating factors (such as temperature), consideration of current magnitudes (such as inrush currents and cyclic loadings), and consideration of equipment withstand (such as I^2t energy withstand).

Manufacturers of EMCBs typically provide selection guidance to assist designers and ensure correct application. Figure 8.32 [11] is one example of selection guidance with respect to system voltage, earthing system, and number of switched poles.

It is recommended to contact the manufacturer for clarification on the expected operational response of the EMCB during capacitive discharge events. Furthermore, the current supplied from capacitors can be very high and even exceed the ultimate breaking capacity, and the manufacturer should be consulted to verify the choice of the EMCB. Manufacturer input is essential to determine the behaviour and assess any implications for system safety and compliance.

Type of distribution system			
Type	Earthed		Isolated
Source	One polarity (negative here) connected to earth (or exposed conductive parts)	Mid-point connected to earth	Isolated polarities
Protected polarities	1 (disconnection of 1P)	2 (disconnection of 2P)	2
Diagrams (and types of faults)			
Selection of circuit breaker and pole connection			
ComPacT NSX DC			
24 V <math>U_n <math>\le 250 V			
NSX100-600 250 V <math>U_n <math>\le 500 V			
NSX100-500 500 V <math>U_n <math>\le 750 V			

Figure 8.32: Typical EMCB manufacturer’s selection guide with respect to system voltage, earthing system, and number of switched poles.

As previously mentioned, the system voltage directly relates to the number of poles that are required to be connected in series (in accordance with the manufacturer’s guidelines). Connecting poles of an EMCB in series could divide the system voltage by the number of poles and optimise the breaking capability. One of the main desired outcomes of this, is that each individual pole will generate an arc voltage during the current interruption process, so when poles are connected in series, the total arc voltage developed is that of all poles, which opposes the system voltage and assists in forcing the DC current to zero to guarantee interruption.

8.2.3.3 SCCB & SCHCB

Selecting a SCCB or a SCHCB for a DC application involves several critical aspects to ensure reliable and efficient operation. According to the ongoing IEC 60947-10 standardization project, key selection criteria are:

1. Electrical Ratings

Rated Voltage:

- The SCCB or SCHCB must be capable of handling the maximum system voltage, including transient overvoltage conditions. This ensures the breaker can operate safely without insulation breakdown.

Rated Current:

- The SCCB or SCHCB should sustain the maximum expected current under normal operating conditions without tripping. This involves considering continuous current ratings and peak current capabilities.

2. Thermal Management

Heat Dissipation:

- Effective thermal management systems are essential to dissipate heat generated during both normal operation and fault conditions. This includes the use of heat sinks, cooling fans, or liquid cooling systems.

Temperature Derating:

- The SSCB's current rating must be adjusted based on ambient temperature conditions. Higher operating temperatures necessitate derating to prevent thermal overload and ensure reliable performance.

3. Fault Current Handling

High di/dt Capability:

- SCCBs or SCHCBs must be designed to handle rapid changes in current (high di/dt) typical in DC fault conditions. This requires fast detecting and fast-acting semiconductor devices capable of interrupting high fault currents within microseconds.

Interrupting Capacity:

- The SCCB or SCHCB must have a sufficient interrupting capacity to safely interrupt the maximum fault current expected in the system. This involves robust design and testing to ensure reliable fault interruption.

4. Efficiency and Losses

Low On-State Losses:

- Semiconductor devices within the SCCB or SCHCB should exhibit low on-state losses to maintain high efficiency during normal operation. This minimizes energy loss and improves overall system performance.

Switching Losses:

- Although switching losses are less critical in SCCBs or SCHCBs compared to power converters, they should still be minimized to enhance performance and reduce thermal stress.

5. Protection and Control

Gate Drive Circuit:

- The design of the gate drive circuit is crucial for precise control of the semiconductor devices in the SSCB. This includes ensuring proper voltage and current levels for reliable switching.

Voltage Clamping:

- Effective voltage clamping mechanisms are necessary to protect the SCCB or SCHCB from overvoltage conditions. This involves using components such as varistors or transient voltage suppressors.

6. Environmental Considerations

Altitude:

- The performance of the SSCB can be affected by altitude due to changes in air density, which impacts cooling and insulation. Derating factors must be applied to ensure reliable operation at higher altitudes.

Vibration and Shock:

- SCCBs or SCHCBs must be designed to withstand mechanical stresses such as vibration and shock, especially in industrial environments. This involves robust mechanical design and testing to ensure durability.

Rated Voltage and Derating Factors

Rated voltage is the maximum voltage that SCCB & SCHCB can handle without experiencing insulation breakdown or failure. Several derating factors can affect this rating. **Temperature** is a significant factor; higher ambient temperatures can reduce the dielectric strength of materials used in the SSCB, necessitating a lower rated voltage to prevent breakdown. For instance, a circuit breaker rated at 1000V at 25°C might need to be derated to 900V at 60°C. **Altitude** also plays a crucial role; at higher

altitudes, the air density decreases, which impacts cooling and insulation properties. This requires derating the voltage to ensure reliable operation. For example, a circuit breaker rated for 1000V at sea level might be derated to 950V at 2000 meters. These adjustments are essential to maintain the safety and reliability of the SSCB under varying environmental conditions.

Rated Current and Derating Factors

Rated current is the maximum current that a semiconductor circuit breaker can carry continuously without tripping. **Temperature** is a primary derating factor; increased ambient temperatures lead to higher thermal stress on the semiconductor devices, necessitating a reduction in the rated current to prevent overheating. For example, a circuit breaker rated at 40A at 25°C might be derated to 30A at 60°C. **Altitude** affects cooling efficiency due to reduced air density, requiring current derating to prevent thermal overload. For instance, a circuit breaker rated for 40A at sea level might be derated to 35A at 3000 meters. **Frequency** variations, although more relevant for AC systems, can impact the thermal performance and efficiency of the circuit breaker, requiring adjustments to the rated current. These derating factors ensure that the SSCB operates safely and efficiently under different environmental and operational conditions.

System Earthing & Breaking One or Two Polarities Under Full Voltage: refer to Section 8.1.

Breaking Capacity: di/dt , L_{max}

di/dt refers to the rate of change of current over time. In the context of SCCBs or SCHCBs, this parameter is crucial because it determines how quickly the breaker can respond to a fault condition. High di/dt values indicate rapid changes in current, which are typical in DC fault scenarios. Semiconductor-based circuit-breakers are designed to ensure protection up to a specified maximum di/dt . This value must be provided by the SCCB or SCHCB manufacturer in accordance with IEC 60947-10. The system's maximum di/dt must be lower than the SCCB's maximum di/dt withstand capability.

- **Importance:** High di/dt capability is essential for protecting sensitive semiconductor devices and preventing thermal runaway, it refers to the withstand of the SCCB or SCHCB.
- **Design Considerations:** SCCBs must incorporate fast-acting semiconductor devices, such as IGBTs or MOSFETs, and advanced gate drive circuits to handle high di/dt values effectively. Some topologies include an inductance to limit the system's di/dt and ensure effective protection under high di/dt operating conditions.

L_{max} represents the maximum inductance in the circuit that the SCCB or SCHCB can safely interrupt. Inductance in a circuit can cause significant voltage spikes when the current is interrupted and represents the fault inductive energy, which can be damaging to both the breaker and the system. Semiconductor-based circuit-breakers are designed to absorb a maximum amount of inductive energy. This value must be provided by the SCCB or SCHCB manufacturer in accordance with IEC 60947-10. The system's maximum inductance must be lower than the SCCB's maximum withstand capability. The system inductance includes the cables, busways and the inductances of the equipment if any.

- **Importance:** Managing L_{max} is critical to prevent overvoltage conditions that can lead to insulation breakdown and equipment failure and to guarantee the effective energy absorption of the breaker.
- **Design Considerations:** SCCBs must include voltage clamping mechanisms, such as snubber circuits or varistors, to safely dissipate the energy stored in the inductance and limit the voltage spikes.

In summary, the breaking capacity of SCCBs and SCHCBs according to IEC 60947-10 involves ensuring that the breaker can handle high di/dt values and manage the maximum inductance (L_{max}) in the circuit. These parameters are critical for the safe and reliable operation of SCCBs and SCHCBs in DC

applications. High di/dt capability ensures rapid fault interruption, while managing L_{max} prevents damaging overvoltage conditions. By incorporating advanced semiconductor devices and protective mechanisms, SCCBs and SCHCBs can meet the stringent requirements of IEC 60947-10 and provide robust protection for DC systems.

Settings for Semiconductor & Hybrid Circuit Breakers

To ensure protection when setting the device, the rules given in Sections 4 and 5 regarding overcurrent (overload and short-circuit) protection and earth fault protection, respectively, should be followed.

Cable Overcurrent Protection

The rated current as well as long-time and short-time curves settings are defined according to rules of Section 4.1.

Potential Inrush Currents

Inrush Current Management:

- **Soft-Start Mechanisms:** Implementing soft-start or slew rate control to minimize inrush currents during startup.
- **Load Switches:** Using load switches with controlled slew rates to limit inrush currents and prevent damage to connectors and Printed Circuit Board (PCB) traces.
Example: If a load switch has a slew rate of $0.1 \text{ V}/\mu\text{s}$ and the supply voltage is 12 V , the inrush current can be calculated as $I_{inrush} = V/R$ where R is the resistance of the load. For a load resistance of 10Ω , the inrush current would be $I_{inrush} = 12\text{V}/10\Omega = 1.2 \text{ A}$.

Isc Calculation Study: Isc mini

Short-Circuit Current Calculation (Isc):

- **Methodology:** Calculating I_{sc} involves determining the total impedance of the circuit and using the formula $I_{sc} = V/Z$, where V is the system voltage and Z is the total impedance.
- **Example:** For a system voltage of 400V and a total impedance of 0.1Ω , the short-circuit current (I_{sc}) would be $I_{sc} = 400\text{V}/0.1\Omega = 4000\text{A}$

Earth Fault Protection:

- **Earth Fault Settings:** Configuring the SSCB to detect and disconnect earth faults within the maximum disconnection time specified in Section 5.2.1.

Converter Protection

Withstand Capability:

- **Design Considerations:** Ensuring the converters can handle the maximum expected fault currents and voltage transients without damage.

8.3 Residual overcurrent protection

Residual overcurrent protection devices may sometimes be specified (see Section 6); how to select them is explained in this section.

8.3.1 Technologies & performances

This section outlines the main technologies used for residual overcurrent protection in DC systems and summarizes key performance considerations.

8.3.1.1 Residual current and detection methods

The primary reason to deploy residual overcurrent protection is to provide earth fault protection and/or additional protection to protect against electric shock. The residual current characterises the earth fault or leakage current flowing from live parts of the installation to earth. However, the term “residual current” should not be mistaken for the “earth fault current”. The residual current, I_{Δ} , is the algebraic sum of current values in all live conductors i.e. except the protective earth conductor, at the same time and given point of a circuit. Whereas the earth fault current is the current flowing through the short-circuit between the live conductor and earth or earthed conductor. Therefore, the residual current is not the same for each circuit in the network during earth fault conditions as shown in Figure 8.33 (for a TN-S system), but it is approximately the same under healthy network conditions if leakage current is considered negligible.

Figure 8.33: Illustration of the residual current (I_{Δ}) in two branches and fault current in a TN-S system

Several sensing methods have traditionally been adopted to identify earth fault and leakage currents, some of which are shown in Figure 8.34. Methods which detect the residual current, I_{Δ} , are shown in (a) and (b) of Figure 8.34. Furthermore, the detection of the earth fault or leakage current can be achieved by the application of sensors located at the system referencing conductor (SRC), shown in (c) of Figure 8.34.

Figure 8.34: Methods to detect current flowing from a live conductor to earth (in a TN-S system)

This section focuses on RCDs for the detection and protection against residual currents and their consequences. As shown in Figure 8.34, a residual sensor must be located between the system earthing point and the earth fault to be detected.

8.3.1.2 Residual overcurrent protection for DC systems

Residual overcurrent protection for DC supply systems is a relatively new concept, with IEC 60755:2017 – the standard of safety requirements for RCDs – not considering RCDs for DC supply systems. It only considers RCDs for AC supply systems, with or without the presence of DC components. Hence, there are limited products and information available today regarding technologies and performances in relation to DC systems.

Residual current operated protective devices for DC supply systems are referred to as “DC-RCD” according to IEC 60755-1:2022. A DC-RCD can detect a residual current in a DC system, compare it to a threshold value, and open the circuit when the residual current exceeds the threshold. The main operating principle of a DC-RCD is the same as RCDs for AC supply systems; that is to detect a residual overcurrent and trip to ensure safety and minimise hazards.

One of the main differences of DC-RCDs compared to RCDs for AC supply systems, are some values of the rated residual operating current, $I_{\Delta n}$ (see Table 8.4). In particular, the introduction of an 80 mA DC-RCD. According to IEC 60755-1:2022 [11], DC-RCDs with a rated voltage $\leq 440\text{V}$ (for two pole devices) and having an $I_{\Delta n} \leq 80\text{ mA}$ are used as a provision for additional protection. Therefore, DC-RCDs with an $I_{\Delta n} \leq 80\text{ mA}$ could be considered equivalent to RCDs in AC supply systems with an $I_{\Delta n} \leq 30\text{ mA}$ [12]. It should be acknowledged that the value of 80 mA is a result of a calculation regarding the effects of direct current on humans and thresholds for ventricular fibrillation and is still regarded as provisional in some cases (IEC 60755-1).

Product standards for DC-RCD are written with reference to IEC 60755:

- IEC 60947 series: Low-voltage switchgear and controlgear (parts 2 and 10)
- IEC TS 63053: General requirements for residual current operated protective devices for DC systems

8.3.1.3 Residual overcurrent protection for AC systems

As mentioned in Section 8.3.1.2, IEC 60755:2017 considers RCDs for AC supply systems, with or without the presence of DC components. When non-isolated AC/DC converters are installed and earthing is realised on the AC system, DC components can appear in the residual current detected on the AC system. Therefore, the technology and performance of RCDs for AC supply systems is also relevant when considering DC installations interfaced with AC systems.

There are various types of RCDs for AC supply systems (IEC 60755), including type AC, type A, type F, and type B. These different types of RCDs define the operating characteristics with the presence of DC components, or not, in the residual current as shown in Figure 8.35 [12].

Figure 8.35: RCD types depending on the residual current components.

Expanding upon this:

- **RCD type AC:** Detect residual sinusoidal alternating currents.
- **RCD type A:** In addition to type AC, they detect residual pulsating direct current superimposed, or not, on a smooth direct current of maximum 6 mA.
- **RCD type F:** In addition to type A, they detect composite (multi-frequency) residual current and residual pulsating direct current superimposed on a smooth direct current of maximum 10 mA.
- **RCD type B:** In addition to type F, they detect residual sinusoidal alternating currents up to 1 kHz and residual smooth direct current.

To ensure reliable and effective operation of the RCD, the correct type must be selected for the application as well as the tripping characteristics. The standard values of rated residual operating current ($I_{\Delta n}$) range from 6 mA up to 30 A (see Table 8.4).

Further technology aspects include Voltage Dependent and Voltage Independent RCDs. The type of technology describes how the RCD will behave in the event of an accidental break in a live conductor or a drop in voltage and relates to how the RCD electronics are powered. If powered from the circuit being protected, the RCD is Voltage-dependent, and may not trip under such circumstances. If the RCD

electronics are not connected to the network and power is provided by the leakage current itself, the RCD is Voltage Independent, allowing the RCD to trip in such a situation.

8.3.2 Selection criteria

In selecting an RCD, various aspects must be considered to ensure suitability and proper functioning of the device. As DC-RCDs are not yet established like RCDs for AC supply systems, this section summarises some of the main criteria that should be considered when choosing an RCD for a specific application.

- **Type of protection to be provided:** To determine the rated residual operating current, which depends on the purpose of the protection, such as protection against faults, protection against fire hazards, or additional protection.
- **System earthing:** To determine if an RCD is suitable or not for the system. In addition, if the AC system is interfaced to the DC system without galvanic isolation and earthing is realised on the AC system, specific RCDs (if required) are needed on the AC side.
- **Immunity requirements:** For harsh environments, RCDs may trip due to transient surges and interference, therefore they should be resistant to unwanted tripping.
- **Selectivity:** First, the implementation of RCDs throughout the system to discriminate faulty feeders may be necessary. Then, only the upstream protection nearest to the fault must trip, which should be achieved thanks to optimum settings (rated residual operating current and associated time-delays) between residual overcurrent protective devices, or between a residual overcurrent protective device and overcurrent protective devices able to trip on earth faults.
- **Coordination:** The placement of RCDs in the network must be considered, especially if required near the source in the installation. For example, surge protection devices should ideally be placed upstream of RCDs, otherwise the RCD should be time delayed.

8.3.3 Selection & setting

This section outlines key considerations for selecting and configuring residual overcurrent protection devices. It addresses appropriate current settings, adjustment options, and coordination with the overall protection strategy.

8.3.3.1 Rated residual operating current

The main parameter with respect to selection and setting (for adjustable RCDs) is the rated residual operating current for RCDs for AC supply systems or rated residual operating *direct* current for DC-RCDs, referred to as $I_{\Delta n}$ in this section. RCDs may have a single value of $I_{\Delta n}$, or it could have multiple settings by fixed steps, or it can be continuously adjustable. According to IEC 60755:2017 and IEC 60755-1:2022 (Section 11), the standard values of $I_{\Delta n}$ are given in Table 8.4.

Table 8.4: Standard values of rated residual operating current

Standard values of $I_{\Delta n}$	AC-RCD	DC-RCD
0.006 A	x	
0.01 A	x	
0.02 A		x
0.03 A	x	
0.08 A		x
0.1 A	x	
0.3 A	x	x
0.5 A	x	
0.6 A		x
1 A	x	x
2 A	x	x
3 A	x	x
5 A	x	x
10 A	x	x
20 A	x	x
30 A	x	x

This selection of $I_{\Delta n}$ is determined by the purpose of the RCD, for example, if it is providing protection against faults, protection against fire hazards, or additional protection.

When providing protection against faults in a TN or in an IT system (where exposed-conductive-parts are interconnected by a protective conductor collectively earthed to the same earthing system), the residual fault currents are significantly higher than $I_{\Delta n}$. Therefore, the disconnection times in accordance with IEC 60364-4-41 are generally fulfilled.

An RCD can also be used to protect against thermal effects and fire hazards. The required selection/setting then becomes a function of the location and circuit to be protected. Generally, the $I_{\Delta n}$ shall be $\leq 30\text{mA}$ for resistive load circuits, otherwise it shall be $\leq 300\text{mA}$.

DC-RCDs having an $I_{\Delta n} \leq 80 \text{ mA}$ are used as a provision for additional protection according to IEC 60755-1:2022, however this is still considered provisional in some cases.

Note: Other types of IT, TT, and TN-C earthing systems are not mentioned due to the risk of corrosion as per *Shift2DC Earthing Systems For DC Microgrids* document [1].

8.3.3.2 Selection of RCDs for the AC side of non-isolated converters

As explained in Section 8.3.1.3, DC components can appear in the residual current detected on the AC system. To ensure reliable and effective operation of the RCD, the correct solution must be selected.

Figure 8.36 illustrates this situation utilising a basic non-isolated three-phase full-bridge rectifier, with earthing realised on the AC system supplying the converter. The earth fault on the DC side of the rectifier is applied as shown in (a) at 100ms, with the phase currents and residual current (i.e. vector sum of the phase currents) shown in (b) and (c), respectively, before and after the fault is applied. The residual current suddenly increases after the fault is applied and is of DC nature, meaning it does not alternate across zero.

Figure 8.36: Illustration of AC system residual current with DC component from AC/DC rectifier

The standard IEC 60755:2017, Annex B, gives an overview of possible fault current waveforms in systems with semiconductors.

Type B RCDs must generally be used in a scenario where non-isolated converters interface the AC and DC systems, as they are able to ensure tripping for a variety of residual currents, which may be suddenly applied or slowly increased.

However, in some cases, the converters are supposed to limit the let-through DC current component (see for example IEC 62109-1 for safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems). If the DC current limited value declared by the manufacturer is compatible with type F or even type A RCDs, they could be used.

It should be acknowledged that without galvanic isolation between the AC and DC systems, as per IEC 60364-8-82:2022, DC currents will impact the AC side and vice-versa which could lead to several issues including transformer saturation and corrosion.

8.4 Surge and overvoltage protection

This section outlines the technologies and implementation of protection devices designed to mitigate transient overvoltages from external (outdoor) and internal sources.

8.4.1 Technologies

Surge Protection Devices (SPDs) are designed to protect electrical and electronic systems from transient overvoltage caused by lightning strikes, switching operations, or electrostatic discharge. The most common SPD technologies include:

- **MOV:** Non-linear resistance that decreases sharply when voltage exceeds a threshold.
- **TVS Diode:** Semiconductor diode that clamps voltage spikes by entering avalanche breakdown.
- **Gas Discharge Tube (GDT):** Gas-filled tube that becomes conductive when ionized by a high voltage.
- **Triggered Spark Gap / Triggered GDT (T-GDT):** Similar to GDT but includes a triggering mechanism for more precise activation.
- **Zener Diode:** Conducts in reverse breakdown to clamp voltage, only suitable for low energy applications.
- **Hybrid SPD Designs:** Combine multiple technologies (e.g., MOV + TVS + GDT) for layered protection.

Typical I-V characteristics are given on the figure bellow (extracted from [13]).

Figure 8.37: V-I characteristics of voltage switching elements

Figure 8.38: V-I characteristics of voltage limiting elements

8.4.2 Performances comparison

Table 8.5 gives an overview of overvoltage protection technologies performances with respect to several criteria.

Table 8.5: Overvoltage protections performance comparison

	MOV	TVS Diode	GDT	Triggered GDT	Zener Diode	Hybrid SPD
Leakage Current	Low	Very low	Very low	Very low	Low	Optimized
End of Life Behavior	Degrades over time with repeated surges	Stable over time	Stable over time	Stable over time	Stable over time	Stable over time
Energy Handling Capacity	High energy absorption capacity	Lower energy handling than MOVs	Very high surge current capability	High energy handling capacity	Not suitable for high-energy surges	Optimized for high energy absorption
Response Time	Moderate response time (microseconds)	Extremely fast response (nanoseconds)	Slower response time (microseconds)	Moderate response time (microseconds)	Moderate response time (microseconds)	Optimized response time
Clamping Threshold	Moderate precision, varies with energy rating	High precision, well-defined clamping voltage	High energy threshold, less precise	Controlled clamping threshold, more precise	Precise clamping voltage, limited energy handling	Optimized clamping threshold, combines precision and capacity
Impact of Ambient Temperature on Clamping Behavior	Clamping voltage may increase with temperature	Clamping voltage may vary slightly with temperature	Performance may degrade at extreme temperatures	Performance may degrade at extreme temperatures	Clamping voltage may vary with temperature	Clamping behavior optimized for stability; performance may vary with temperature
Impact of Aging on Clamping Behavior	Aging leads to increased leakage and reduced effectiveness	Generally stable over time	Generally stable over time	Generally stable over time	Generally stable over time	Generally stable over time
Suitability for DC	Not suitable for DC without additional circuitry	Suitable for DC	Not suitable for DC without additional circuitry	Not suitable for DC without additional circuitry	Suitable for DC	Suitable for DC
Cost	Cost-effective	Moderate cost	Moderate cost	Higher cost	Low cost	Higher cost

Typical Applications	Power supplies, industrial equipment, consumer electronics	Communication interfaces, USB, Ethernet, sensitive circuits	Telecommunications, industrial equipment, power lines	High-energy applications, industrial systems	Signal-level protection, small circuits	Tailored to specific needs, high-performance systems
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Remarks:

- Technologies relying on gas breakdown voltage (such as GDTs) are generally unsuitable for DC applications, as the arc generated during conduction does not self-extinguish due to the absence of a natural current zero-crossing. Additional circuitry is required to manage arc extinction effectively.
- Usual MOVs degrade with each surge, and over time, leading to increased leakage currents. This can be problematic in IT earthing systems, where cumulative leakage may reduce overall insulation resistance; and potentially causing nuisance tripping of RCDs in TN-S systems.
- MOV-based SPDs must be equipped with disconnection devices in series to safely manage their end-of-life condition, which typically results in a short-circuit failure mode. The associated overcurrent protection must be properly coordinated with upstream line protection devices—this can be challenging when ultra-fast circuit breakers are used.
- PV-specific SPDs should not be used in LVDC microgrids unless their I_{SCPV} rating exceeds the prospective short-circuit current at the point of installation. This is because the SPD I_{SCPV} rating is usually low aligning with the inherent low short-circuit current of PV systems without battery.

8.4.3 Focus on system-level SPDs

This subsection details the performance requirements, selection criteria, and installation practices for SPDs used at the system level.

8.4.3.1 SPD performance requirements

Performance requirements of SPD are identified in IEC 61643-11. Selection and applications principles of SPD are described in IEC 61643-12. The general principles, risk management and protection devices against lightning are identified and described in IEC 62305 standards. The Surge Protection Handbook [13], performs detailed identification of the needs for overvoltage protections and detailed description of the procedures and techniques to implement these protections looking for the standard requirements. Current peaks are generated from overvoltage surges and lightning discharges. The standardised shapes of typical current peak evolutions from overvoltage surges and lightning discharges are represented by Figure 8.39 [13].

Figure 8.39: Standard shapes of (a) current peaks from overvoltage surges and (b) lightning discharges [13].

Table 8.6 shows typical electrical parameter values of SPDs for protection of PV generation (LVDC). The maximum operating voltage represents the value of maximum RMS or DC voltage that may be applied continuously between the terminals of SPD. The voltage protection level characterizes the performance of the SPD in limiting voltage across its terminals during surge occurrences. Typical nominal and maximum discharge current values on application of overvoltage surge 8/20 μ s and lightning discharge 10/350 μ s waveforms during class II testing are also presented.

Table 8.6: Typical discharge and protection levels of SPDs for PV in different LVDC nominal voltages

Nominal voltage [V _{dc}]	350	600	1000	1500
Maximum operating voltage [V _{dc}]	460	720	1200	1500
Nom - Max current surge 8/20 μ s [kA]	20 - 40	20 - 40	20 - 40	20 - 40
Nom - Max Lightning 10/350 μ s [kA]	5 - 12.5	5 - 12.5	5 - 12.5	5 - 12.5
Protection level [kV]	1.4	2.5	3.8	5

The values presented in this table are based on typical electrical parameter values of SPDs for PV protection from different providers. Typical nominal voltages of Shift2DC demonstrators are considered.

8.4.3.2 Selection criteria

According to IEC 61643-11, SPDs are classified into three main types based on their installation location and protection function. While IEC 61643-12 provides guidance on the selection and coordination of SPDs in general low-voltage systems, IEC 61643-32 focuses specifically on SPD application in PV systems, particularly on the DC side.

Type 1 SPD – Lightning Current Arresters

Type 1 SPDs are the first line of defence in a multi-stage protection scheme and are designed to withstand direct lightning strikes (10/350 μ s shape) or high-energy surges.

They are installed at the origin of the electrical installation (e.g., where the microgrid connects to external sources like PV arrays or the utility grid).

Characteristics:

- High surge current capacity (e.g., $I_{imp} \geq 10$ kA per pole).
- Used in areas with external lightning protection systems (LPS).
- Generally including spark gaps or GDTs.

Type 2 SPD – Overvoltage Protectors

Type 2 SPDs protect downstream equipment against indirect lightning currents (8/20 μ s shape) and switching transients.

They are installed in distribution boards or sub-panels within the microgrid.

Characteristics:

- Moderate surge current capacity (e.g., $I_n = 5\text{--}20\text{ kA}$).
- Commonly using Metal Oxide Varistors (MOVs).
- Fast response time.

Type 3 SPD – Point-of-Use Protectors

Type 3 SPDs provide the final layer of protection for sensitive electronic devices.

They are installed close to the load (e.g., inside control cabinets or near DC-DC converters).

Characteristics:

- Low surge current capacity (e.g., $<5\text{ kA}$).
- Very fast response time (often $<1\text{ ns}$).
- Often uses Silicon Avalanche Diodes (SADs) or hybrid circuits.

8.4.3.3 Implementation

Specific precautions must be taken when implementing SPDs. In particular, due to the very steep current wavefront, the voltage drops along the connection cables (of the form $L \cdot di/dt$) is not negligible: assuming an inductance of $1\ \mu\text{H/m}$, a standard 8/20 μ s surge current waveform can generate an overvoltage of approximately 1000 V per meter of cable. This means that the protected equipment will be exposed to the sum of the SPD's clamping voltage and the additional voltage induced by the wiring inductance. Therefore, it is essential to limit the total length of the connecting conductors to less than 50 cm (see Figure 8.40 for recommended connection rules [14]).

Figure 8.40: SPD connection rule.

In addition, SPDs must be protected against overcurrent conditions using appropriate protective device in series. This protection ensures that, in the event of an SPD failure (e.g., due to thermal runaway or end-of-life degradation), the fault current is safely interrupted without compromising the continuity of the main power supply. The selected overcurrent protective device must be coordinated with the SPD's maximum short-circuit current rating and should not trip under normal surge

conditions. This is why SPD manufacturer's should provide guidance on specific OCPDs to use, so they trip when they should and don't trip when they shouldn't.

9 How to select & set monitoring devices

9.1 Insulation Monitoring Devices (IMD & IFL)

According to IEC 60364-5-53:

- IMDs have to meet their product standard IEC 61557-8 where three IMD types are described:
 - IMD for pure AC IT systems,
 - IMD for AC IT systems with directly connected rectifiers and for pure DC IT systems and for DC IT systems with directly connected AC inverters,
 - IMD only for pure DC IT systems;
- Insulation fault location (IFL) shall be selected in accordance with IEC 61557-9 (for both AC and DC systems).

9.1.1 Technologies & performances

In the IMD, a generator of very low frequency AC current, or of DC current, (to reduce the effects of cable capacitance to negligible levels) continuously applies a measuring voltage between a live conductor and earth. This voltage causes a small measuring current to flow in the insulation resistance to earth of the whole installation. As this current is proportional to the insulation resistance, its measurement by the device allows it to calculate the insulation level.

Low-frequency injection principle can be used on AC systems which generate transient DC components under fault conditions, to avoid unwanted alarms.

The IMD measuring principle must be able to monitor both symmetrical and asymmetrical insulation faults. A symmetrical insulation fault concerns all phases or polarities, when an asymmetrical insulation fault affects only one phase or polarity.

Figure 9.1: Symmetrical and asymmetrical faults

Certain versions can distinguish between resistive and capacitive components of the leakage current. Indeed, the leakage capacitance creates a path for the measurement signal and reduces the level of the useful signal that flows through the insulation resistance and as a consequence the measurement accuracy.

Modern equipment allows for the measurement of leakage-current evolution, enabling the prevention of a first fault. It is recommended to use an IMD that signals an interruption of its measurement connections.

The insulation fault location system (IFLS) is associated with the IMD:

- The current sensors are able to detect the fault current generated by the IMD;
- A communication is generally implemented between the IFLS and the IMD.

9.1.2 Installation

An IMD must be installed at or near the origin of the part of the installation to be monitored, at a location where it is able to monitor the installation insulation in every operating mode.

In case there are several supplies, one IMD per supply has to be installed to monitor each supply before it is connected to the system. However, only one IMD should be active in a galvanically isolated IT system, the reason why IMDs associated with power supplies temporarily connected in parallel must be interlocked in such a way they exclude each other. There is no disturbance during such transitions as the fault detection in IMDs is filtered. IFLS sensors are installed on feeders to discriminate the first faulty feeder.

9.1.3 Selection & setting

The standard IEC 60364-5-53 indicates some setting values:

- As an example a minimum of $100 \Omega/V$ ($300 \Omega/V$ for pre-warning) of the rated system voltage;
- When IMDs have to be set to prevent the risk of fire (in compliance with IEC 60364-4-42):
 - Minimum $40 \Omega/V$ in a public distribution system with a galvanic supply,
 - Minimum 50 % of the insulation resistance without insulation failure and full load.

Some specific other values may exist for certain applications, like hospitals, marine...

But the best method to set an IMD is to install it and register the installation natural global insulation resistance for a typical operating period. Then the alarm can be set for example at 50% of the minimum registered value, and the pre-warning at 70%. An adjustment of the settings can be made later. Indeed, the higher the thresholds, the better the sensitivity, but unwanted alarms may arise if the installation natural insulation resistance has not been assessed correctly at the installation commissioning phase. Of course, for IT systems connected to earth through impedances, these ones are in parallel with the installation global insulation resistance and have to be taken into account in the settings.

Note: IMDs can sometimes be used to monitor off-line systems before they connect to the installation. In that case, the alarm threshold should be above $300 \text{ k}\Omega$ as the insulation resistance is generally very high, and the IMD must automatically be deactivated when the system is on-line.

9.2 Residual current monitoring device

RCMs have to meet their product standard:

- IEC 62020-1 for residential applications, applicable to AC circuits, which may include not only residual alternating current, but also residual pulsating direct current and smooth direct current.
- IEC 60947-2, annex M for industrial applications.

RCMs for use in DC supply systems are under consideration.

9.2.1 Technologies & performances

RCMs used in AC circuits are classified according to the residual current they are able to detect, similarly to RCDs:

- Type AC;
- Type A;

- Type F;
- Type B.

Directionally discriminating RCMs may be used on public distribution systems to be able to discriminate leakage capacitive currents from resistive insulation faults.

9.2.2 Installation

RCMs must be installed at or near the origin of the part of the installation to be monitored.

9.2.3 Selection & setting

The standard IEC 60364-5-53 gives the following indications concerning RCMs setting:

- when RCMs are installed to prevent the risk of fire (in compliance with IEC 60364-4-42), their rated residual warning level shall not exceed 300 mA;
- for a RCM installed downstream a RCD ($I_{\Delta n}$), it is recommended to set it not higher than $I_{\Delta n}/3$.

10 Conclusion

This deliverable provides comprehensive guidance on how to adequately protect LVDC power systems against various types of faults to ensure safety.

The first chapter introduces the importance of creating a protection plan for an electrical installation to minimise the risks and hazards that faults present. The protection plan is described, which involves identifying possible faults and defining methods to detect and remove these faults from the system to reestablish safe operating condition.

Subsequently, the second chapter describes LVDC power system architectures and topologies, such as two-wire and three-wire systems and radial, loop, and meshed topologies, as well as the system earthing types suitable for LVDC distribution systems. An example of an LVDC power system is given, providing the typical architecture of a prosumer installation and placement of protective devices. Due to the inherent nature of LVDC prosumer installations, the nomenclature of the system topology is defined as a “bus grid” or “bus topology”, as the systems are not strictly “radial”. It should be noted that loop and meshed topologies are not covered in this deliverable as none of the Shift2DC demonstrator projects are based on these network topologies.

Protection system philosophies are explored in the third chapter, specially focusing on the main objectives of protection systems including the protection of people, protection of assets, assisting in power system stability, and improving continuity of service. Furthermore, considerations that need to be made when planning a protection strategy and designing a protection system are described, such as meeting user requirements, selecting a suitable plan for the power system architecture, and selecting protection components.

The third chapter also explains the usual approach for selecting protection systems. Architecture-related protection schemes are described, illustrating the increased complexity of the protection plan/systems when multiple-source LVDC microgrids are considered. One of the main reasons for this increased complexity is due to the number of different power flow scenarios, modes of operation with respect to grid-connected and islanded states, and the increasing presence of power converters. Additionally, DC-specific concepts proposed by Current/OS and ODCA are described. These concepts have an aim to simplify the design, and protection plans, of DC systems.

Having explored the essential need of a comprehensive protection plan, LVDC power system architectures, and protection philosophies, the fourth, fifth, sixth, and seventh chapters explain how to protect against faults. Firstly, how to protect against overcurrents is covered, explaining the coordination required between conductors and protective devices for overload and short-circuit conditions. Then, how to protect against earth faults, particularly with respect to the capability of protective conductors and how to protect against electric shock, is described. The constraints associated to power converters are investigated regarding overcurrents and earth faults. Subsequently, methods to protect against thermal effects are described, as well as how to protect against overvoltages.

The devices that can be used to protect against faults are investigated in chapter eight. Technologies and performances of protective devices providing overcurrent, residual overcurrent, and overvoltage protection are discussed. Furthermore, key criteria are given to select such protective devices; common criteria include the application, system earthing, immunity to unwanted tripping, installation conditions, and specificities of the circuit/equipment being protected (e.g. inrush current, thermal stress withstand, etc.). Existing protective devices such as fuses, electromechanical circuit-breakers,

RCDs, and SPDs are included. Emerging protective devices such as semiconductor circuit-breakers are also discussed, as they are foreseen to play a pivotal role in the protection of LVDC power systems. It should be acknowledged that RCDs for AC supply systems are detailed, as they are important protective devices to be considered when non-isolated DC installations are interfaced with AC systems, particularly when power system earthing is realised on the AC system.

Finally, although not protective devices, monitoring devices such as IMDs, IFLs, and RCMs are detailed in chapter nine as they complement and play an important role in the safe operation of an installation.

In summary, this protection plan deliverable facilitates those responsible for electrical network design to formulate a protection plan to ensure the network is sufficiently protected, considering various types of faults and the constraints that power converters impose. Furthermore, it provides key criteria regarding the selection of protective devices and how to set them accordingly to protect the system.

11 Applicable standards

The IEC 60364 series is an international standard that addresses the design, erection, and verification of **low voltage electrical installations**. It aims to ensure the safety of persons, livestock, and property against dangers and damage that may arise from the use of electrical installations.

Here are the key parts of the IEC 60364 series relevant for protection:

Part 1: 2005/ COR1: 2009: Fundamental principles, assessment of general characteristics and definitions.

Part 4: Protection for safety

- Section 41: 2017: Protection against electric shock
- Section 42: 2024: Protection against thermal effects
- Section 43: 2023: Protection against overcurrent
- Section 44: 2024: Protection against voltage disturbances and electromagnetic disturbances

Part 5: Selection and erection of electrical equipment

- Section 52: 2009/ AMD1: 2024: Wiring systems
- Section 53: 2020: Devices for protection for safety, isolation, switching, control and monitoring
- Section 54: 2011/ AMD1: 2021: Earthing arrangements and protective conductors
- Section 55: 2011/ AMD1: 2012/ AMD2: 2016: Other equipment
- Section 57: 2022: Erection of stationary secondary batteries

Part 7: Requirements for special installations or locations

- Section 712: 2017: Solar photovoltaic (PV) power supply systems
- Section 722: 2018: Supplies for electric vehicles

Part 8: Functional aspects

- Section 82: 2022 Prosumer's low-voltage electrical installations

IEC 60269 series is the applicable standard for **low-voltage fuses**. Key parts relating to DC systems are:

- Part 1: 2016 General requirements
- Part 4: 2024 Supplementary requirements for fuse-links for the protection of semiconductor devices
- Part 5: 2014/ AMD1: 2020: TR - Guidance for the application of low-voltage fuses
- Part 6: 2010/ AMD1: 2021/ COR1: 2021: Supplementary requirements for fuse-links for the protection of solar photovoltaic energy systems
- Part 7: 2021: Supplementary requirements for fuse-links for the protection of batteries and battery systems

IEC 60947 series applies to low-voltage switchgear and controlgear:

- Part 2: Circuit-breakers
- Part 10: CDV 2025: Semiconductor Circuit-Breakers

Other standards:

- IEC TS 63053: 2017: General requirements for residual current operated protective devices for DC systems
- IEC 60755: 2017: General safety requirements for residual current operated protective devices.

- IEC 60755-1: 2022: General safety requirements for residual current operated protective devices - Part 1: Residual current operated protective devices for DC systems.
- IEC TR 63282: 2024: LVDC systems – Assessment of standard voltages and power quality requirements

ANSI standard device numbers are used to define common protection functions for electrical relays and systems. The following device codes are referenced in this document:

- ANSI 49: Thermal overload protection
- ANSI 50: Instantaneous overcurrent protection
- ANSI 51: Time-delay overcurrent protection
- ANSI 51V: Voltage-controlled time overcurrent protection
- ANSI 67: Directional overcurrent protection
- ANSI 87L: Line differential protection
- ANSI 87B: Busbar differential protection

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APPENDIX A: Current carrying Capacity under DC and AC

Finite element simulation was made on a trefoil copper conductor of cross section from 1 mm² to 2000 mm² with XLPE insulation. The objective of the simulation was to determine the minimum conductor cross section where the skin effect and proximity effect are noticeable which are absent under DC current. Beyond this cross section, the conductor should be able to carry higher current under DC than AC.

Results show that for copper conductor, minimum cross section must be more than 300mm² to see a difference in the ampacity under DC and AC. Any cross section below this shall have negligible difference between AC and DC. Since, most low voltage cables cross section is below 300mm², the ampacity under DC and AC shall be considered the same. These results are also confirmed with ampacity calculation using IEC 60287 series.

Figure A.1: Maximum current carrying capacity of copper conductor for cross section up to 2000mm² under AC (50Hz) and DC, maximum copper conductor temperature at 90°C.

The main reason for negligible skin or proximity effect for smaller conductor cross sections is because the skin depth is larger than the radius of the conductor. The skin depth can be theoretically determined by the formula below:

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\omega\mu\sigma}}$$

Where ω = AC frequency (@50Hz), μ = permeability and σ = conductivity of the conductor. It gives skin depth ≈ 9.2 mm (area =267 mm²). Therefore, theoretically any copper conductor below this radius experiences minimal skin effect.

However, the situation will be different under short circuit event since the high di/dt corresponds to high frequency. Even smaller cross section conductors should have current density gradient (high near the surface) under both DC and AC short circuit current. The differentiation can be made if the di/dt during rise or fall of short circuit current can be accurately know under DC and AC.

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Executive Summary

Short-circuits must be cleared from a power system as they can have serious consequences. To protect life and assets and ensure safety, it is essential to understand the maximum and minimum prospective short-circuit currents throughout an electrical installation so an appropriate protection plan can be developed and implemented. This involves the selection of suitable protective devices and protection settings to mitigate the effects and consequences of short-circuit currents.

Short-circuit currents in DC systems differ significantly from those found in traditional AC systems. As it stands, there is no existing standard or document that provides a detailed methodology to calculate prospective short-circuit currents in DC systems with multiple sources and power converters, such as those of the Shift2DC demonstrator projects. There are some existing standards regarding short-circuit currents in DC systems, however they are application-specific and have several limitations with respect to present and future DC systems. A detailed methodology is required to enable the prospective short-circuit current to be calculated.

The calculation approach proposed in this deliverable is time-domain simulation with simplified short-circuit behavioural models of sources and components, including power converters, that can contribute to and influence a short-circuit. This approach is deemed the most practical, mainly due to the complexities of power converters that are dominant in modern DC systems, whilst providing a sufficient level of accuracy. Moreover, it can be rapidly and widely adopted using existing commercial software.

Simplified short-circuit behavioural models of DC system short-circuit contributors including common power converters, AC grids, capacitors, PV systems, and batteries, that can be used in time-domain simulation, are described. The power converter models are intended to describe the output current during short-circuit conditions and are not suitable for other purposes. The use of detailed power converter models is not prohibited, providing they describe to a better extent the short-circuit behaviour. Appropriate models of other network components are also given. The input data required for each model is listed.

An overall methodology is presented (refer to Figure ES.1) which includes data gathering, building a network model, modelling of components, configuring the model, and extracting required outputs. Furthermore, conditions for calculating maximum and minimum prospective short-circuit currents are proposed and the main short-circuit current calculation outputs are described.

N.B. In the long term, a new standard for DC short-circuit current calculations needs to be drafted. This topic is addressed in WP5, and a New Work Item Proposal has been sent in this sense to IEC TC 73. Studies are underway to define an analytical calculation method.

Figure ES.1: General methodology process for the calculation of DC short-circuit currents

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Keywords, Acronym

AC	Alternating Current
DAB	Dual Active Bridge
DC	Direct Current
di/dt	Current rate-of-rise
ESL	Equivalent Series Inductance (of a capacitor)
ESR	Equivalent Series Resistance (of a capacitor)
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEC TC	International Electrotechnical Commission – Technical Committee
IEC TR	International Electrotechnical Commission – Technical Report
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IGBT	Insulated-Gate Bipolar Transistor
I_{OUT}	Output current
L	Line conductor (also a live conductor)
L-	Line conductor, negative polarity (also a live conductor)
L+	Line conductor, positive polarity (also a live conductor)
LV	Low Voltage
LVDC	Low Voltage Direct Current
M	Mid-point conductor (also a live conductor)
MMC	Modular Multilevel Converter
MOSFET	Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor Field-Effect Transistor
MV	Medium Voltage
MVDC	Medium Voltage Direct Current
ODCA	Open DC Alliance
PD	Protective Device
PE	Protective (earthing) conductor
PV	Photovoltaic
RCD	Residual Current Device
RL	Resistor-Inductor
RLC	Resistor-Inductor-Capacitor
RMS	Root Mean Square
SAB	Single Active Bridge
SLD	Single Line Diagram
SRC	System Referencing Conductor
TN	Electric system according to IEC 60364-1 where one live part is directly connected to earth, and exposed-conductive-parts are connected to the earthed point where the live part is connected to earth
TN-S	TN electric system where live conductors and protective earthing conductors are separated from each other
V_{OUT}	Output voltage
XLPE	Cross-Linked Polyethylene

Symbols, Subscripts

AC/DC and DC/DC Converters and Capacitors

C_C	Capacitance of capacitor
ESL_C	ESL of capacitor
ESR_C	ESR of capacitor given at $\sim 100\text{Hz}$ or $\sim 120\text{Hz}$
HV	Higher voltage
I_{SS-SC}	Limited steady-state short-circuit current if the current is controlled ($> 0\text{A}$) or cut ($= 0\text{A}$)
L_{ACind}	AC boost inductor inductance
L_{add}	Additional inductance up to the terminals for external connection
L_F	Filter inductance
LV	Lower voltage
R_{ACind}	AC boost inductor resistance
R_{add}	Additional resistance up to the terminals for external connection
t_{SS-SC}	Time of limited steady-state short-circuit current when the current $> 0\text{A}$
V_C	Voltage of capacitor (usually $V_C = U_{DC} \times c_{DC}$, $U_{BAT} \times c_{BAT}$, or $U_{OCARRAY}$)

DC (Grid) Voltage

c_{DC}	DC grid voltage factor or band limit (for droop-controlled system), in per unit (p.u.) of nominal value
U_{DC}	Nominal DC grid voltage

AC (Grid) Supply

$(X/R)_{k1}$	X/R ratio corresponding to I''_{k1}
$(X/R)_{k3}$	X/R ratio corresponding to I''_{k3}
c_{AC}	AC voltage factor according to IEC 60909 calculation, in p.u. of nominal
f_n	Nominal AC system frequency
I''_{k1}	Initial line-to-earth short-circuit current
I''_{k3}	Three-phase initial symmetrical short-circuit current
L_0	Zero-sequence inductance
L_1	Positive-sequence inductance
L_2	Negative-sequence inductance
R_0	Zero-sequence resistance
R_1	Positive-sequence resistance
R_2	Negative-sequence resistance
R_t	Total sequence-domain resistance ($R_t = R_1 + R_2 + R_0$)
U_n	Nominal AC system rms line voltage
X_0	Zero-sequence reactance
X_1	Positive-sequence reactance
X_2	Negative-sequence reactance
X_t	Total sequence-domain reactance ($X_t = X_1 + X_2 + X_0$)
Z_0	Zero-sequence impedance
Z_1	Positive-sequence impedance
Z_2	Negative-sequence impedance
Z_t	Total sequence-domain impedance ($Z_t = Z_1 + Z_2 + Z_0$)

PV System

$I_{SC\ STC\ ARRAY}$	Short-circuit current of the PV array under standard test conditions
K_I	Factor with a minimum value of 1.25 (that can be increased)
$U_{OC\ ARRAY}$	Open circuit voltage of the PV string/array

Battery

C_{BAT}	Battery voltage factor, in p.u. of nominal
L_{BAT}	Total inductance of the battery source
R_{BAT}	Total resistance of the battery source
U_{BAT}	Nominal open-circuit battery voltage
$\tau_{decayBAT}$	Battery decay time constant

Circuit

$L_{LIVEone-way}$	One-way inductance of a single live conductor ($L_{LIVEpul} \times l$)
$L_{LIVEpul}$	Equivalent live conductor inductance per unit length
$L_{PEone-way}$	One-way inductance of a single PE conductor ($L_{PEpul} \times l$)
L_{PEpul}	Equivalent PE conductor inductance per unit length
$R_{LIVEone-way}$	One-way resistance of a single live conductor ($R_{LIVEpul20^\circ C} \times l$)
$R_{LIVEpul20^\circ C}$	Equivalent live conductor DC resistance per unit length referred to 20°C
$R_{PEone-way}$	One-way resistance of a single PE conductor ($R_{PEpul20^\circ C} \times l$)
$R_{PEpul20^\circ C}$	Equivalent PE conductor DC resistance per unit length referred to 20°C
l	Length

Protective device

L_{PDind}	Inductance of the protective device inductor
R_{PDind}	Resistance of the protective device inductor

Short-circuit

	Possible short-circuit location
---	---------------------------------

Subscripts

$k1$	Line-to-earth short-circuit (in AC system)
$k3$	Three-phase short-circuit (in AC system)
max	Maximum
min	Minimum
SAT	Saturated value
$USAT$	Unsaturated value

1 Introduction

Short-circuit currents in Direct Current (DC) systems differ significantly from those found in traditional Alternating Current (AC) systems. This is partly due to the capacitive nature of DC systems and the types of short-circuit current sources that exist. It is also due to the architecture and behaviour of DC systems (when compared to AC systems), where sources are typically distributed, most loads contribute to short-circuits due to their capacitances, and the dominant presence of power converters that can contribute to and/or influence the short-circuit current.

The aim of this document is to describe a general methodology to calculate prospective short-circuit currents in DC systems and DC systems supplied by power converters. Some areas of this document are focused on Low Voltage Direct Current (LVDC) however this methodology is generally applicable to LVDC and Medium Voltage Direct Current (MVDC) systems.

The term “prospective” is used in this document to describe the current that would flow in the event of a short-circuit in which the operation of all protective devices is neglected.

The term “short-circuit” is used in this document to describe an abnormal zero-impedance connection between live conductors of different potential, or a live conductor and an exposed-conductive-part or a protective conductor of different potential. The latter is often referred to as an “earth fault”.

1.1 Purpose of Understanding Short-Circuit Currents

Electrical installations must be safe according to law. Installation rules and standards should be followed in the design, build, and verification of an installation to achieve a minimum level of safety. Inevitably, the calculation of short-circuit currents becomes a necessity and is of paramount importance. This is a critical part of designing a system, as it assists in evaluating the requirements of an installation and how to ensure the protection of life and assets.

Short-circuits must be cleared from a power system as they can lead to serious consequences including risk of electric shock, risk of fires, equipment damage, failure of systems, and increased costs (both equipment repair and downtime of the network). It is therefore very important to understand the short-circuit current distribution throughout a system and implement a protection plan to mitigate these risks. Refer to [1] for information regarding protection plans.

Short-circuit current calculations are usually required at different stages of a project. During the initial design phase of an installation, the short-circuit current can be conservatively estimated to enable equipment to be specified and allow the design to progress. As the design develops, short-circuit currents need to be calculated with a greater level of accuracy to ensure equipment (that is going to be purchased and installed) is adequate and inform the protection plan to allow the optimum protective devices and settings to be selected.

1.1.1 Transient and Steady-State Phases of a Short-Circuit Current

In a DC system, there are several types of sources that can contribute to a short-circuit. Some of these sources can be an AC/DC converter including the AC supply system, DC/DC converters including the DC supply system, capacitors, Photovoltaic (PV) systems, batteries, regenerative loads, and fuel cells, or a combination of these within a single piece of equipment. For example, an AC/DC voltage source

converter is connected to the AC supply system and has a capacitor on the DC side; under prospective short-circuit conditions the DC capacitor and the AC supply system will contribute.

Each source that contributes to a short-circuit will have a different response which can result in a current waveform that differs significantly to short-circuit currents found in traditional AC systems and battery-fed DC systems. A DC system is typically highly capacitive and therefore an initial large current with high rate-of-rise (di/dt) is common, followed by a steady-state contribution phase. An example of a short-circuit current (with three different contributors) in a DC system is provided in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Example of a short-circuit current and contributions having transient and steady-state phases

As can be seen, the total prospective short-circuit current has a transient phase in which the current magnitude is changing in a non-repetitive manner, which is followed by a steady-state phase in which the current is repetitive. The current magnitude is typically higher in the transient phase however this is not true in all cases. The origin of higher transient-phase currents can, for example, be due to the capacitive nature of a DC system or a result of an AC/DC converter being supplied by an AC system with a high X/R ratio or an AC generator with time-varying impedance.

It should be acknowledged that if a short-circuit was to occur multiple times at the same location, the short-circuit current could be significantly different for various reasons (which are explored in Section 4.4). It is therefore essential to estimate the maximum and minimum short-circuit current.

1.1.2 Maximum Short-Circuit Current

The maximum prospective (transient and steady-state) short-circuit current is mainly required for equipment selection purposes. Equipment selection includes the breaking and making capacity of protective devices and the electrodynamic and thermal withstand of conductors and distribution assemblies. The maximum short-circuit current is also required for protection purposes to assess if there is sufficient grading margin and/or selectivity between protective devices when maximum prospective current flows. In addition, the maximum “through-fault” current may be required if the

protection scheme measures and compares two or more points in the network, such as differential protection for example (considering out-of-zone short-circuits), for protection stability purposes.

1.1.3 Minimum Short-Circuit Current

The minimum prospective (transient and steady-state) short-circuit current is mainly required for protection purposes. This is to ensure that protective devices can detect the short-circuit current and interrupt it within a specified time for safety. Moreover, it helps to identify if additional protection measures are needed if the short-circuit current is too low for the phase overcurrent protection. For example, protective devices may require extra sensitivity to detect low short-circuit currents or specific devices (e.g. RCDs) may be required to detect earth faults. It is also required to fulfil the selectivity guidelines, allowing selectivity to be assessed for the full range of expected short-circuit currents.

1.2 Existing Standards

There are two main standards that exist regarding short-circuit current calculations and assessments in DC systems. An overview of these two standards is given along with the limitations of these standards with respect to DC systems with multiple sources and power converters.

1.2.1 IEC 61660-1 (DC Auxiliary Installations)

To support the calculation and assessment of short-circuit currents in DC systems, standardised methods are desired. One such standard is IEC 61660-1, published by the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), which provides a methodology for calculating short-circuit currents in DC auxiliary installations. The following section introduces and outlines the application of this standard.

1.2.1.1 IEC 61660-1 Overview

Standard IEC 61660-1 provides a method to calculate short-circuit currents in DC auxiliary systems in power plants and substations. The standard covers the contribution from four different sources including rectifiers in three-phase AC bridge connection (for 50Hz), stationary lead-acid batteries, smoothing capacitors, and DC motors with independent excitation. All four sources of short-circuit current are represented as a voltage source behind an impedance.

The short-circuit current contributions from each source are estimated using a standard approximation function consisting of $i_1(t)$ and $i_2(t)$, with $i_1(t)$ being the current before the peak current and $i_2(t)$ being the current afterwards (see Figure 1.2).

Figure 1.2: Standard approximation function from IEC 61660-1

Firstly, the partial short-circuit current for each contributing source is considered in which the characteristic quantities i_k , i_p , T_k , t_p , τ_1 , and τ_2 (see Figure 1.2) are determined and applied to the standard approximation function. Many factors, some of which are taken from graphs or can be calculated, are applied to the characteristic quantities throughout the procedure, with various constants being used in the equations.

Secondly, the partial short-circuit currents can be summed together if there is no common impedance to the sources to obtain the total short-circuit current. However, if there is at least one common impedance branch to the different sources, then correction factors need to be determined and applied to modify the short-circuit currents (i_k and i_p) calculated for each source. This gives the full characteristic quantities for each contributing source to allow calculation of the total short-circuit current.

Although the IEC 61660-1 standard is brief on the calculation of minimum short-circuit current, it provides considerations when determining both maximum and minimum short-circuit current, including:

- Conductor resistances are referred to 20°C for maximum current and the maximum operating temperature for minimum current.
- Resistances of busbar joints are neglected for maximum current and included for minimum current.
- Limitation of the rectifier current (using control) is neglected for maximum current and considered for minimum current.
- Diodes for decoupling parts of the system are neglected for maximum current and considered for minimum current.
- Battery (voltage) is fully charged for maximum short circuit current and at the final voltage at lowest discharge level for minimum short circuit current.

However, it also advises to consider the current-limiting effect of protective devices for maximum and minimum short-circuit current, which is contrary to the methodology in AC systems and defeats the object of trying to understand what the prospective minimum value of short-circuit current is to verify if protection will operate or not.

In summary, IEC 61660-1 provides a detailed methodology to calculate maximum and minimum short-circuit current with sources found in a DC auxiliary installation. The standard uses many pre-defined correction factors and constants throughout the calculation process, all of which have been defined based on the specificities related to DC auxiliary installations, making the process very cumbersome.

1.2.1.2 IEC 61660-1 Limitations for DC Systems

When dealing with the architecture of DC systems and DC systems supplied by power converters and the potential contributions to a short-circuit, the IEC 61660-1 standard has the following limitations and constraints:

- Only a AC/DC rectifier is considered i.e. power converters generally are not included.
- Current sources are not included e.g. PV system.
- The AC/DC rectifier considered is only for 50Hz. It does not consider 60Hz systems.
- The example networks used within the standard are simple with very few common branches. The calculation method will become even more demanding as the (larger) system size will result in numerous partial and global common branches, all which correction factors need to be determined and applied.
- Only pole-to-pole short-circuits are considered i.e. earth faults are not covered. When assessing earth faults, DC systems can result in earth fault loops which are dependent on multiple live conductors – not just the faulted conductor – due to the location of the system referencing conductor (SRC).
- Voltage levels in a modern DC system are not considered.
- Only two-wire systems are considered i.e. systems with a distributed mid-point (i.e. three-wire systems) are not covered.
- Only lead-acid batteries directly connected to the DC bus are considered; more battery types are used in modern DC systems, typically connected through a converter.
- The output of the short-circuit current calculation is not sufficient to select semiconductor circuit-breakers (refer to Section 4.5.2), which are an emerging technology in DC systems.

The standard was published in 1997 and therefore its application to existing and future DC systems with other technologies could be deemed inappropriate.

The IEC calculation method has been compared to time-domain simulations for applications other than auxiliary installations. In [2], the IEC method is demonstrated to be effective for estimating steady-state short-circuit currents and less accurate for the transient current. In [3], the IEC method generally provided conservative results (higher current values) when lumped elements were utilised in the time-domain simulation. In addition, the capacitor transient response was considered as overdamped by the IEC method but was underdamped in the time-domain simulation, which led to a higher Joule integral and indicated that the protective device (fuse) operated faster than would otherwise be the case. This could lead to incorrectly specifying equipment, unrealistic minimum short-circuit current, and unrealistic Joule integral (I^2t) values which will impact protection and safety.

1.2.2 IEEE Std 946 (DC Stationary Applications)

Another standard relevant to short-circuit current calculations in DC systems is IEEE Std 946, published by the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE). It offers guidance primarily for stationary DC power applications and focuses on the contributions from batteries, chargers, and motors.

1.2.2.1 IEEE Std 946 Overview

IEEE Std 946 provides guidance on the calculation of short-circuit currents in stationary DC power systems. The standard specifically discusses the contribution from batteries, chargers, and inductive loads such as motors.

The battery is considered as a DC voltage source behind an impedance and sample calculations are provided in the standard. Although the standard does not provide equations as a function of time, the battery short-circuit contribution can be approximated by implementing the calculated peak current (V/R) and time constant (τ) in a single exponential equation. This can be observed from the graphs provided in the Annex of IEEE Std 946.

The charger is described as a current source with the typical short-circuit contribution being a multiple of the rated current. The inductive load (i.e. motor) is described as a voltage behind an impedance and gives the maximum short-circuit contribution as a multiple of the rated current.

When accurate short-circuit current values are required, the standard advises to consult the equipment manufacturer in all cases.

In summary, IEEE Std 946 gives guidance on how to assess the short-circuit current from DC installations with lead-acid batteries, chargers, and inductive loads. A detailed methodology is not provided, and the standard is focused on maximum short-circuit current.

1.2.2.2 IEEE Std 946 Limitations for DC Systems

Some limitations mentioned in Section 1.2.1.2 are relevant to IEEE Std 946, with other specific points being:

- Guidance is provided for the calculation of maximum short-circuit current; it does not provide detailed calculations nor a clear methodology for calculating maximum and minimum short-circuit current.
- Although the standard acknowledges that (filter) capacitors within chargers can contribute to the short-circuit current, this is neglected due to the short time duration of the capacitor contribution to the short-circuit. Therefore, the capacitor contribution, which can be up to tens or hundreds of kA in a DC system supplied by power converters, is not considered.

1.3 Approaches to Calculate Short-Circuit Currents

Following the overview of existing standards, this section presents the different approaches that can be used to determine short-circuit currents in DC systems.

1.3.1 Review of Approaches

It is important to apply the appropriate methods when calculating short-circuit currents to minimise the expense of calculation, and it is mainly dependent upon the purpose of the calculation. As previously mentioned, calculations are usually required at different phases of a project and the purpose of the calculation, along with the level of required accuracy, can be different.

Different stages of a short-circuit current can be calculated as they might be of varying interest for different design aspects. This may be required for the initial selection of equipment at an early design stage. On the other hand, the full short-circuit current waveform and contribution from each source

may be required at a later design stage for protection and selectivity purposes and equipment capability verification (e.g. I^2t thermal stress of conductors, Root Mean Square (RMS) current for fuse assessment, current rate-of-rise for protective device selection, etc.).

Although the existing standards have several limitations for modern DC systems (see Section 1.2.1.2 and Section 1.2.2.2), they can still be utilised for preliminary calculations if they are applicable (refer to Table 1.1) and can expedite the calculation process. The IEC 61660 standard is a feature that can be applied in many existing commercial software packages, such as ETAP¹.

Time-domain simulation has been utilised in many DC system short-circuit current studies and is widely used in DC microgrid research. Even so, there are several drawbacks to recognise including:

- A required knowledge of transient analysis tools (circuit simulators) and awareness of potential issues e.g. numerical stability and time-step sensitivity.
- Computational intensity and time consumption if the simulation is not optimised.
- Having to build models of network components from fundamental blocks.

However, the benefits of time-domain simulation include:

- Detailed representation of each component enabling precise calculations.
- Complex equations of large networks which are changing according to the short-circuit location are handled by the solver which reduces manual error.
- Different fundamental sources can be utilised such as DC current sources, DC voltage sources, and AC voltage sources at 50Hz, 60Hz, and other frequencies.
- Flexibility in adapting the simulation model and the block parameters. This helps with modern DC system specificities such as voltage levels, different mid-point configurations, and long earth fault loops that can be dependent, or not, on more than two conductors.
- Flexibility of data processing e.g. the I^2t or RMS current can easily be computed from the time-varying short-circuit current which is important for conductor sizing and protection.
- System interactions are considered e.g. commutation of diodes which can be important for accurate current waveforms (and therefore I^2t).

Considering this, Table 1.1 summarises calculation approaches according to the purpose of the calculation.

Table 1.1: Short-circuit current calculation purpose and approaches for DC systems

Calculation purpose	Calculation type	Calculation approaches
Initial peak short-circuit current from capacitors	Preliminary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilise capacitor discharge equations from IEC 61660-1 for a single capacitor; or • Time-domain simulation for a single or multiple distributed capacitors (see APPENDIX A: IEC 61660 vs. Time-Domain Simulation for Capacitors).
Steady-state short-circuit current (excluding earth faults)	Preliminary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilise IEC 61660-1 for networks with sources of short-circuit current that are covered by the standard with more relevant conditions applied

¹<https://etap.com/>

Calculation purpose	Calculation type	Calculation approaches
		for maximum and minimum short-circuit currents; or <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time-domain simulation.
Transient and steady-state short-circuit current and contribution from all sources (including earth faults)	Suitable for protection assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time-domain simulation with simplified models of components to approximate short-circuit behaviour; or Time-domain simulation with detailed models of components including converters and their control loops and internal current-limitation protection (if any).

1.3.2 Selected Approach

No matter the purpose of the calculation, time-domain simulation, if used appropriately, can provide relatively fast and accurate results of prospective transient and steady-state short-circuit currents including earth faults for DC systems and DC systems supplied by power converters.

Due to limitations in the existing standards, and that the purpose of calculating short-circuit currents is for protection and safety, the selected calculation approach (and the focus in this document) is time-domain simulation with simplified behavioural models of power system components. This is because it is deemed the most practical approach providing accuracy that can be rapidly and widely adopted using commercialised software. The use of detailed component models is possible however it is not practical for rapid and wide adoption, mainly due to the complexities of power converters that are dominant in modern DC systems.

N.B. In the long term, a new standard for DC short-circuit current calculations needs to be drafted. This topic is addressed in WP5, and a New Work Item Proposal has been sent in this sense to IEC Technical Committee (TC) 73. In a standard, analytical methods such as those of IEC 60909 and IEC 61660 are preferred over time-domain (Electromagnetic Transient) simulations. Studies are underway to define an analytical calculation method (see the deliverable that will result from Task T5.2).

2 Behaviour of DC System Short-Circuit Contributors

As previously explained, there are several types of sources that can contribute to a short-circuit in a DC system. The main sources of short-circuit current foreseen in a DC system are:

- AC/DC converters
- DC/DC converters
- AC sources through AC/DC converters i.e. AC in-feed
- Capacitors e.g. capacitor bank connected to the bus, capacitor inside load, supercapacitor, etc.
- PV systems
- Batteries
- Regenerative loads
- Fuel cells

It is important to understand the behaviour of these sources with respect to short-circuits. The purpose of the following sections is to overview the generic short-circuit behaviour rather than give deep explanations on how the converters and sources operate in normal and abnormal conditions.

Although acknowledged, the short-circuit behaviour and modelling approach of regenerative loads and fuel cells are not covered in this document. These sources shall be considered separately if required, however they are not foreseen within the Shift2DC project.

2.1 AC/DC and DC/DC Converters

This section presents typical short-circuit behaviours of power converters in DC systems. It introduces differences between power converter topologies and modelling approaches to support short-circuit studies.

2.1.1 Introduction to Power Converters

The realisation and development of DC power systems relies upon the use of power converters. Power converters control the flow of power and energy by providing voltages and currents in a desired form. In a DC system, this includes conversion between an AC and a DC system, and the conversion between two different DC systems. The different systems may or may not be galvanically isolated.

There are a wide variety of power converter topologies, and each type behaves differently to short-circuits. To generalise the short-circuit behaviour, two categories are commonly referred to when studying a power converter's short-circuit behaviour, as follows:

- **Limiting converters:**
 - It limits the current from its input in the event of an output-side short-circuit.
 - There aren't any direct input-to-output freewheeling paths.
 - The limited current is controlled and can be realised by internal control loops acting on the active switch (e.g. transistor in the current path) to maintain a steady-state output current no higher than the maximum setpoint.
 - The limited current will continue to flow until protective devices operate, the converter stops due to other reasons (e.g. temperature, voltage, etc.), or energy sources deplete.
 - It should be noted that diodes can decouple parts of the system and can be considered to block the current in some scenarios (which effectively limits it) e.g. a short-circuit on the input of a boost converter. Semiconductor switches can also block current e.g.

Insulated-Gate Bipolar Transistor (IGBT) opening to prevent capacitor discharge in Modular Multilevel Converter (MMC).

- **Non-limiting converters:**

- It allows current to flow in an uncontrolled manner from its input in the event of an output-side short-circuit.
- There is a direct input-to-output freewheeling path allowing current to flow (depending on the network conditions).
- The non-limited current will continue to flow until protective devices operate, the converter stops due to other reasons (e.g. temperature, voltage, etc.), or energy sources deplete.
- It should be noted that if short-circuit current is allowed to flow uncontrollably through freewheeling paths (e.g. body diodes or antiparallel diodes), they can be rapidly damaged if not properly protected.

Figure 2.1 illustrates the basic generalisation of limiting and non-limiting converters in short-circuit conditions, respectively, using a buck and boost converter.

Figure 2.1: Example of limiting and non-limiting power converters

2.1.2 Modelling Challenges

It is difficult to predict the full short-circuit behaviour of power converters unless the complete converter design including the control loops and internal current-limitation protection (if any) is known. In practice, the full short-circuit behaviour can only be understood through advanced simulations, specific short-circuit tests, and field measurements. In addition, there are an endless number of converter designs. It would therefore take substantial effort and time to obtain the required information and model a converter with a high level of fidelity for every study, and it is likely that the manufacturer will not share this level of information. It is deemed impractical to take this approach for rapid and wide adoption.

For this reason, a simplified model of a converter shall be utilised with enough fidelity that can describe an estimated short-circuit behaviour. This will still require some data from the converter manufacturer however it is a more practical approach for generic short-circuit current studies.

Refer to APPENDIX B: Converter Switching Model vs. Simplified Model for a comparison between a switching model and simplified model regarding short-circuit behaviour. A simplified model, if used appropriately, can give a very good estimation of the converter behaviour during a short-circuit.

2.1.3 Short-Circuit Behaviour General Characterisation

This section aims to characterise the short-circuit behaviour of power converters, discussing the different stages and power converter simplified short-circuit models.

2.1.3.1 Stages

Generally, several stages of a short-circuit current can occur when a power converter has internal filtering stages (including capacitors and inductors) and diodes, and when voltage or current sources are present. The different stages of a short-circuit have been analysed in various literature [4], [5], however a summary of the stages is required to understand the development of simplified behavioural models. It must be acknowledged that the different stages relate to the prospective short-circuit current and do not consider overcurrent protective devices (e.g. fast-acting fuses, circuit-breakers, etc.) contained within power converters or in the external network.

In summary, the different stages are:

1. If a capacitor is present, a capacitor discharge stage will occur first, whereby the capacitor that is exposed to the short-circuited part of the system will discharge resulting in a typically high current magnitude with high di/dt . The current magnitude and rate-of-rise will be dependent on the capacitor and network parameters (as explained in Section 2.3). This stage is energy-limited dictated by the energy stored in the capacitor.
2. Assuming a capacitor is present and has fully discharged, freewheeling of diodes (if present) will occur because of the short-circuit loop inductance. This occurs only if the voltage goes negative (i.e. under-damped response) and the diodes become forward biased.
3. Subsequently, a third stage will occur in which the input source feeds the short-circuit. After some time, the current is repetitive meaning a steady-state phase has been reached. Note that some limiting converters will stop delivering current completely, so there is no steady-state output current (see Figure 2.4 and related text). Generally, the steady-state phase can be:
 - a. Limited, such as a battery in-feed controlled by a buck converter, for example, or;
 - b. Non-limited, such as an AC in-feed through an AC/DC InterLink converter, for example.

The different stages summarised above can be visualised by using an AC/DC non-isolated InterLink 2-level converter as an example, illustrated in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Short-circuit current stages illustration for an AC/DC non-isolated InterLink 2-level converter

Typical short-circuit current waveforms from converters with limited (left) and non-limited (right) steady-state behaviour are shown in Figure 2.3. The axes scales are different, however it can be observed that the limiting converter output current is constant after a transient phase, whereas the non-limited AC in-feed current is present (known by the ripple in the DC current) after the transient stage with the AC/DC InterLink converter. The AC in-feed current would be higher if the short-circuit power of the AC system was higher i.e. it is not limited by the converter.

Figure 2.3: Typical short-circuit current waveforms from different types of converters (different scales)

It must be recognised that for limiting converters, the steady-state (stage 3) current magnitude can be impacted by a power converter’s control. During a short-circuit condition, the limited current can follow a “brick-wall” type limit where the output current is constant (or slightly increases above nominal rating) when the voltage drops, or it may be voltage-dependent. In some cases, a power converter can curtail the output current or stop delivering current completely if the voltage reaches a minimum threshold; this is done mainly for self-protection [6] and is important to understand, especially for minimum short-circuit current evaluation. Figure 2.4 illustrates the concept of a limiting converter with a voltage-dependent output current through a simplified model using a voltage-dependent current source with an output voltage-output current ($V_{OUT-I_{OUT}}$) profile.

Figure 2.4: Limiting converter control example affecting the steady-state output current

2.1.3.2 Modelling

With this general behaviour characterisation, Table 2.1 provides a summary view of simplified short-circuit models of common converter topologies. Refer to APPENDIX D: Power Converter Short-Circuit Models for enlarged diagrams. The models should not be utilised to assess internal components (e.g. diodes); they only represent the output current behaviour.

As there are so many variations in converter topologies and design, this document only covers some of the most common topologies. It shall be acknowledged that other converter topologies can be realised from the models provided hereafter. For example, an isolated AC/DC converter which consists of a (AC/DC) Vienna rectifier in series with a (DC/DC) single active bridge converter can be created by combining the simplified short-circuit behavioural models of the AC/DC InterLink 2-level converter and DC/DC single active bridge.

The short-circuit behaviour of a converter in both directions (i.e. for a short-circuit on the DC source-side and DC bus-side) and whether a converter has galvanic isolation or not are key aspects to consider when calculating short-circuit currents including earth faults. This is considered and represented in the models, and care should be taken if bespoke models are utilised.

Furthermore, the models can be adapted if more information of the converter is available e.g. a boost converter may be three-phase interleaved, additional capacitors could be present, etc. For limiting converters, the current limit profile, which may or may not be voltage-dependent, shall be adapted (see Section 2.1.3.1 and Section 4.4.8).

Particularly for short-circuits close to the converter or at the converter terminals, it is important to consider internal impedance of the converter up to the terminals for external connection; this is shown as R_{add} and L_{add} in Table 2.1 and can either be estimated or requested from the manufacturer. Ideally, the manufacturer will provide this information (such as the equivalent circuit parameters as seen from the terminals) or provide short-circuit test results to help estimate the values.

When a short-circuit occurs, it is assumed the converter is healthy with no faulty components i.e. diodes are in working order and included in the model. Where Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor Field-Effect Transistors (MOSFETs) are shown in the basic topology, they are considered with an inherent body diode or an additional external freewheeling diode (to prevent conduction of the inherent body diode). In some cases when different active switches are used, they may have the capability to withstand reverse voltage or realise reverse current conduction in a different way to that of a diode, meaning the diode associated with the active switch in the short-circuit model may not exist.

Table 2.1: Summary view of simplified topology and short-circuit models for common power converters

Converter description	Simplified topology	Block	Simplified short-circuit model ^(NOTE 1,2,3)
AC/DC non-isolated InterLink 2-level converter			
AC/DC non-isolated InterLink 3-level converter			
DC/DC non-isolated boost converter (unidirectional)			
DC/DC non-isolated boost converter (bidirectional)			
DC/DC non-isolated buck converter (unidirectional)			
DC/DC non-isolated buck converter (bidirectional)			
DC/DC isolated single active bridge (SAB)			
DC/DC isolated dual active bridge (DAB)			

(NOTE 1) High resistance snubbers (e.g. 1 MΩ) may be required due to current sources in series with inductors in some models.

(NOTE 2) A current source, , indicates the power converter is current limiting in the direction/short-circuit location it is facing.

(NOTE 3) It is assumed the lower/bottom line of the circuit will be a return path. (Note for earthing and 3-wire systems.)

(NOTE 4) Splitting this model into two – one for each short-circuit location – is possible.

2.2 AC (Grid) Supply

AC systems can contribute to a short-circuit on the DC system. It is possible that the AC or DC system can be earthed (if the earthing arrangement is Terre-Neutral (TN)) and therefore the AC system should be modelled to reflect the behaviour under balanced and unbalanced conditions.

This section only considers AC network feeders that are electrically distant from AC generators, including all the network components up to the input terminals of AC/DC converters. Special considerations shall be made for AC generators including the generator and regulator models for representative transient and steady-state behaviour.

AC systems are typically represented as an AC voltage source behind an impedance. The AC system impedances can be modelled in the sequence-domain or phase-domain. Whilst both approaches should give identical results, the sequence-domain is used hereafter to align with IEC 60909 (see Table 2.2 for a simplified short-circuit model of an AC grid supply).

The impedances in the sequence-domain can be determined from the nominal line voltage, U_n , voltage factor, c_{AC} , three-phase initial symmetrical short-circuit current at the AC/DC converter input terminals, I''_{k3} , the corresponding X/R ratio, $(X/R)_{k3}$, and initial line-to-earth short-circuit current at the AC/DC converter input terminals, I''_{k1} , and the corresponding X/R ratio, $(X/R)_{k1}$.

The maximum and minimum short-circuit currents (I''_{k3max} , I''_{k3min} , I''_{k1max} , and I''_{k1min}) along with the X/R ratios and voltage factors shall be obtained for the calculation of the minimum and maximum impedances, respectively. This information can be obtained from IEC 60909 calculations performed on the AC system.

In some cases, a power-frequency transformer that is external to the AC/DC converter will provide galvanic isolation and power system earthing will be realised on the DC system. If this is the case, the initial line-to-earth short-circuit current at the AC/DC converter input terminals, I''_{k1} , will become zero in accordance with IEC 60909 (due to the open-circuit equivalent zero-sequence circuit of the transformer) and therefore the AC supply can be represented by only the positive-sequence impedance.

For an AC supply network (i.e. far from generators), the positive- and negative-sequence impedances are equal. The positive- and negative-sequence parameters are calculated as follows:

$$Z_1 = \frac{c_{AC} \cdot U_n}{\sqrt{3} \cdot I''_{k3}} = Z_2 \quad (2.1)$$

$$R_1 = \frac{Z_1}{\sqrt{1 + (X/R)_{k3}^2}} = R_2 \quad (2.2)$$

$$X_1 = R_1 \cdot (X/R)_{k3} = X_2 \quad (2.3)$$

The zero-sequence parameters, if earthing is realised on the AC system, are calculated as follows:

$$Z_1 + Z_2 + Z_0 = Z_t = \frac{c_{AC} \cdot U_n \cdot \sqrt{3}}{I''_{k1}} \quad (2.4)$$

$$R_t = \frac{Z_t}{\sqrt{1 + (X/R)_{k1}^2}} \quad (2.5)$$

$$X_t = R_t \cdot (X/R)_{k1} \quad (2.6)$$

$$Z_0 = Z_t - 2 \cdot Z_1 \quad (2.7)$$

$$R_0 = R_t - 2 \cdot R_1 \quad (2.8)$$

$$X_0 = X_t - 2 \cdot X_1 \quad (2.9)$$

The positive-, negative-, and zero-sequence inductance can be computed using: $L_{1,2,0} = \frac{X_{1,2,0}}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot f_n}$, where f_n is the nominal AC power system frequency.

Table 2.2: Simplified short-circuit model for an AC grid supply

Simplified short-circuit model	Typical short-circuit current waveform (neutral earthed)	

2.3 Capacitor

Capacitors can be present in DC systems for a variety of reasons, including for stability purposes, to meet voltage ripple targets, and to help achieve protection selectivity by supplying current during short-circuit conditions to make protective devices operate faster. They can be a dedicated component connected to a main DC bus and can also be present in loads and converters. Their presence in converters is already considered in Section 2.1.

A capacitor under short-circuit conditions is generally considered as a source-free series-connected resistor-inductor-capacitor (RLC) circuit. The resistor represents dielectric losses and accounts for the electrolyte, foils, and terminal effective resistance; this is referred to as the Equivalent Series Resistance (ESR). The inductor represents the inductive reactance of the winding and terminals; this is referred to as the Equivalent Series Inductance (ESL). In some cases, the inductance (ESL) is neglected, so the capacitor equivalent circuit is reduced to a capacitor connected in series with a resistor. This is due to the ESL of capacitors typically being in the order of tens of nH, which is negligible compared to the inductance of the external connections and network that dominate the loop inductance.

There are 3 natural responses of this circuit – under-damped, over-damped, and critically damped – which depends on the resonant angular frequency (ω_0) and the Neper frequency (α) [7] Ultimately the

total resistance, inductance, and capacitance of the capacitor and external network dictate the natural response.

With this circuit, the capacitor is initially charged to a certain voltage, and it discharges through the resistance and inductance of the short-circuit loop. Further details about the theory of capacitor discharge current can be found in [7].

Table 2.3: Simplified short-circuit model for a capacitor

Simplified short-circuit model	Typical short-circuit current waveform

The current waveforms in Table 2.3 illustrate the 3 natural responses which are generally a result of the capacitor and external network characteristics (rather than only the capacitor).

2.4 PV System

From a short-circuit behaviour standpoint, PV cells/arrays act like current sources and the current under short-circuit conditions may not be much higher than normal current levels. The prospective short-circuit current depends on the short-circuit location, irradiance level, and number of strings in the array. The ambient temperature can also affect the current. See Table 2.4 for a simplified short-circuit model of a PV array.

In accordance with IEC 60364-7-712, the maximum short-circuit current ($I_{SC\ MAX}$) of a PV cell/array is calculated using the formula $I_{SC\ MAX} = K_I I_{SC\ STC}$, where K_I is a factor with a minimum value of 1.25 and $I_{SC\ STC}$ is the short-circuit current under standard test conditions.

Table 2.4: Simplified short-circuit model for a solar PV array

Simplified short-circuit model	Typical short-circuit current waveform

2.5 Battery

This document only covers the contribution of a battery to an external short-circuit, as opposed to dealing with short-circuits internal to a battery.

There are numerous applications for batteries including stationary, primary power, energy storage, electric vehicle, and small appliances. The use of a battery is different in the various applications and thus certain technologies are utilised. For example, in some applications batteries are required to support a load in the event of a mains supply failure (e.g. stationary applications). A Valve Regulated Lead Acid battery is normally suitable for this application. In other applications batteries are cycled i.e. charged and discharge repeatedly (e.g. energy storage applications), so a lithium iron phosphate battery is more suited. These technologies can have different short-circuit responses.

For short-circuit current calculations, a battery can be modelled as a DC voltage source behind an impedance (see Table 2.5 for a simplified short-circuit model). For a short-circuit located at the battery terminals, the resistance and inductance of the battery itself (i.e. the cells, modules, and connections between them), which will depend on the battery technology, shall be considered. For a short-circuit located in the external network, the resistance and inductance of both the battery and the external network shall be considered.

The resistance and inductance of the short-circuit loop will have an impact on the peak current (mainly determined by the resistance) and the time it takes to reach the peak current (mainly determined by the inductance). Moreover, the state-of-charge of the battery prior to the short-circuit will also impact the prospective current due to the pre-fault voltage level.

The evolution of the short-circuit current can be described by the following equation:

$$i(t) = I_{SC} \cdot \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}\right) \quad (2.10)$$

where:

$i(t)$ is the short-circuit current at time t

I_{SC} is the maximum short-circuit current calculated by dividing the voltage by the resistance $\left(\frac{V}{R}\right)$

τ is the time constant calculated by dividing the inductance by the resistance $\left(\frac{L}{R}\right)$

If the battery manufacturer provides the I_{SC} and τ , the resistance and inductance of the battery model can be calculated as $R = \frac{V}{I_{SC}}$ and $L = \tau \cdot R$, respectively, which is then to be added to the external network resistance and inductance as appropriate.

Table 2.5: Simplified short-circuit model for a battery

Simplified short-circuit model	Typical short-circuit current waveform
<p>The graph shows the typical battery short-circuit contribution, neglecting current decrease. The y-axis is Current i and the x-axis is Time t. The current starts at zero, rises sharply to a peak, and then remains constant. The legend indicates 'Current, battery' (solid line) and 'Current zero' (dashed line).</p>	

It shall be noted that the short-circuit current decreases after some time and this depends on the initial state-of-charge and discharging/energy rating of the battery. The time to decrease mainly depends on the battery technology and initial state-of-charge. This is not considered above. Special considerations shall be made for minimum short-circuit current calculations if the current contribution is expected to rapidly decrease in a short period after the short-circuit.

3 Input Data

The data required for a short-circuit current calculation is detailed in Table 3.1. Data which is indicated as optional is not essential for the calculation.

Table 3.1: Summary of input data

Category	Input Data	Symbol	Mandatory (M) or Optional (O)
Single line diagram	Power system architecture		M
	Earthing system(s) and location of system referencing conductor(s)		M
System configuration and operational scenarios	Normal operating conditions		M
	Abnormal operating conditions		M
DC grid voltage	Nominal DC grid voltage [V]	U_{DC}	M
	DC grid voltage factors or band limits (for droop-controlled system), in p.u. of nominal	c_{DC} c_{DCmax} c_{DCmin}	M
Converters	Basic topology		M
	AC boost inductor resistance [Ω]	R_{ACind}	M
	AC boost inductor inductance, unsaturated and saturated values [H]	L_{ACind} $L_{ACindUSAT}$ $L_{ACindSAT}$	M
	AC boost inductor saturation characteristics		M
	Capacitance of (filter) capacitor [F]	C_C	M
	ESR of capacitor given at $\sim 100\text{Hz}$ or $\sim 120\text{Hz}$ [Ω]	ESR_C	M
	ESL of capacitor [H]	ESL_C	O
	Voltage of capacitor [V] (usually $C_V = U_{DC} \times c_{DC}$, $U_{BAT} \times c_{BAT}$, or U_{OC} ARRAY)	V_C	M
	Filter inductor inductance, unsaturated and saturated values [H]	L_F L_{FUSAT} L_{FSAT}	M
	Filter inductor saturation characteristics		M
	Limited steady-state short-circuit current if the current is controlled (> 0) or cut ($= 0$) [A]	I_{SS-SC} $I_{SS-SCmax}$ $I_{SS-SCmin}$	M
	Time of limited steady-state short-circuit current when the current $> 0\text{A}$ [s]	t_{SS-SC}	M
	Additional resistance up to the terminals for external connection [Ω]	R_{add}	O
Additional inductance up to the terminals for external connection [H]	L_{add}	O	
AC (grid) supply	Nominal AC system rms line voltage [V]	U_n	M
	AC voltage factor according to IEC 60909 calculation, in p.u. of nominal	c_{AC} c_{ACmax} c_{ACmin}	M

Category	Input Data	Symbol	Mandatory (M) or Optional (O)
	Nominal AC system frequency [Hz]	f_n	M
	Three-phase initial symmetrical short-circuit current at the AC/DC converter input terminals [A]	I''_{k3} I''_{k3max} I''_{k3min}	M
	X/R ratio corresponding to I''_{k3}	$(X/R)_{k3}$ $(X/R)_{k3max}$ $(X/R)_{k3min}$	M
	Initial line-to-earth short-circuit current at the AC/DC converter input terminals [A]	I''_{k1} I''_{k1max} I''_{k1min}	M (if AC neutral is earthed)
	X/R ratio corresponding to I''_{k1}	$(X/R)_{k1}$ $(X/R)_{k1max}$ $(X/R)_{k1min}$	M (if AC neutral is earthed)
Capacitor	Capacitance of capacitor [F]	C_C	M
	ESR of capacitor given at ~100Hz or ~120Hz [Ω]	ESR_C	M
	ESL of capacitor [H]	ESL_C	O
	Voltage of capacitor [V] (usually $V_C = U_{DC} \times c_{DC}$)	V_C	M
Solar PV	Short-circuit current of the PV array under standard test conditions [A]	$I_{SC\ STC\ ARRAY}$	M
	Factor with a minimum value of 1.25 (that can be increased)	K_I	O
	Open circuit voltage of the PV string/array [V]	$U_{OC\ ARRAY}$	M
Battery	Nominal open-circuit battery voltage [V]	U_{BAT}	M
	Battery charged and discharged voltage factors, in p.u. of nominal	C_{BAT} C_{BATmax} C_{BATmin}	M
	Total resistance of the battery source [Ω]	R_{BAT} R_{BATmax} R_{BATmin}	M
	Total inductance of the battery source [H]	L_{BAT}	M
	Decreasing time constant [s], or characteristics of the decrease in current after the peak current	$\tau_{decayBAT}$	O
Circuits	Equivalent live conductor DC resistance per unit length referred to 20°C [Ω]	$R_{LIVEpul20^\circ C}$	M
	Equivalent PE conductor DC resistance per unit length referred to 20°C [Ω]	$R_{PEpul20^\circ C}$	M
	Equivalent live conductor inductance per unit length [H]	$L_{LIVEpul}$	M
	Equivalent PE conductor inductance per unit length [H]	L_{PEpul}	M
	Length [m]	l	M
	Maximum sustained conductor operating temperature [°C]		M
	Resistance of the protective device inductor [Ω]	R_{PDind}	O

Category	Input Data	Symbol	Mandatory (M) or Optional (O)
Protective devices with series inductor	Inductance of the protective device inductor, unsaturated and saturated values [H]	L_{PDind} $L_{PDindUSAT}$ $L_{PDindSAT}$	M
	Inductor saturation characteristics		M

4 Methodology

This section describes the process of conducting short-circuit current calculations using time-domain simulation (see Figure ES.1). Firstly, an outline is given on the network model build and modelling of short-circuit sources and components typically found in DC systems and DC systems supplied by power converters. Subsequently, conditions to consider when calculating maximum and minimum short-circuit current are proposed. Lastly, the main short-circuit current calculation outputs are described.

4.1 Data Gathering

All the information stated in Section 3 that is relevant to the studied network shall be obtained.

4.2 Network Build

A model shall be built in time-domain simulation software that reflects the studied network by using models of network components and short-circuit contributors that are adequate and describe the approximate short-circuit behaviour (see Sections 2 and 4.3). The simplified short-circuit behavioural models of DC system short-circuit contributors (sources and converters) can be adapted if more information is available, and more advanced models can be utilised if they describe to a better extent the short-circuit behaviour. An example of using the short-circuit behaviour models to build a network is illustrated in Figure 4.1 (assuming a short-circuit is located at a DC grid bus). For brevity, the impedance of the DC grid buses is not shown.

Figure 4.1: Example of building a DC network using simplified short-circuit behaviour models

When building the model, careful consideration shall be made to the short-circuit location and the location of the SRCs. The location of the SRCs is crucial for analysing earth faults. Figure 4.2 illustrates the importance of the SRC location in a TN system when calculating short-circuit currents, as it can result in a long earth fault loop which is dependent on more than two conductors for some contributing sources (note: protective devices are not shown and contribution from only the battery and associated converter is shown for brevity). This will impact the short-circuit (earth fault) current and the current that will flow through protective devices and therefore needs to be known to select appropriate protection.

Figure 4.2: Illustration of the SRC location resulting in a long earth fault loop (in a TN system)

As DC systems contain multiple power sources, some of which can have power flowing bi-directionally, there could be many power flow scenarios. For this reason, the system shall be modelled without any loads i.e. power is not flowing. However, factors are to be applied to the system parameters (see Section 4.4), which are impacted by power flow, in the calculations. More advanced simulations could be performed to account for power flow conditions however this will normally require control loops to be included within converter models (which is out of scope of this document).

4.3 Component Modelling

The accuracy of short-circuit current calculations in DC systems depends significantly on how each network component is modelled. Time-domain simulations require models that reflect the transient and steady-state behaviour of these components during short-circuit conditions. The following subsections describe how to model the key elements relevant for short-circuit simulations.

4.3.1 DC System Short-Circuit Contributors

These models have been explored and are represented in Section 2. These simplified models are non-exhaustive and can be modified or repurposed to suit specific converter topologies.

4.3.2 Circuits (Cables and Busway)

For prospective short-circuit current calculations in DC systems, conductors of a (cable or busway) circuit shall be modelled, at the very least, as a series resistor-inductor (RL) circuit for each individual conductor as shown in Figure 4.3.

IEC 61660 provides methods of obtaining values of resistance and inductance per unit length of basic conductor and busbar arrangements. More advanced methods shall be utilised for complex circuit arrangements to obtain accurate impedances. Generally, with parallel conductors, the overall equivalent resistance is the individual conductor resistance divided by the number of conductors. However, the calculation of the overall equivalent inductance will strongly depend on the conductor arrangement. Moreover, when circuit models with fixed resistance and inductance values are used, consideration shall be given to the frequency of the current signal. Refer to APPENDIX C: Frequency Effect on Resistance and Inductance.

The one-way resistance and inductance of the live and PE conductors can be computed from the input data by multiplying the resistance or inductance per unit length by the length.

Figure 4.3: Simplified short-circuit model for a circuit (live and Protective Earthing (PE)) conductor

Other basic models, such as “ π ” models can be used. Furthermore, advanced transmission line (distributed parameters) models can be utilised with the circuit/cable arrangement parameters being computed based on physical geometry and conductor and insulation properties. This type of circuit modelling considers the self and mutual impedances and admittances between different conductors of the circuit/cable arrangement.

An important point regarding MVDC distribution systems is that cable circuits, which may be several tens of kilometres long in an MVDC system, inherit high (stray) capacitance and can result in a non-negligible discharge current under short-circuit conditions.

4.3.3 Protective Devices with Series Inductors

Protective devices are normally neglected from prospective short-circuit current calculations. However, they are deemed necessary to consider if they have non-negligible passive elements which may be within a protective device for a specific purpose, such as an inductor for limiting the current rate-of-rise (di/dt). In this case, the protective device pole shall be modelled as a series resistor-inductor (RL) circuit as shown in Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4: Simplified short-circuit model for a protective device pole with internal inductor

4.4 Conditions for Maximum and Minimum Short-Circuit Current

This section outlines the key conditions that influence the maximum and minimum short-circuit current values in a DC system, focusing on system configuration and component variation.

4.4.1 System Configuration

The number of sources that can contribute to a short-circuit will not be fixed in a DC system. This can be for a variety of reasons, including:

- Equipment out of service due to commissioning and (routine and post-fault) maintenance.
- Network configuration change due to the operation of protective devices (e.g. tripping of a circuit breaker which decouples a section of the network).
- Reduced battery contribution when a low state-of-charge is reached.
- Reduced solar PV contribution when irradiance levels are low.
- Regenerative loads being operational or not.

For **maximum** short-circuit current, the configuration and operational mode that leads to the maximum value of prospective current at the short-circuit location shall be used.

For **minimum** short-circuit current, the configuration and operational mode that leads to the minimum value of prospective current at the short-circuit location shall be used. Furthermore, the following sources of short-circuit current shall be neglected:

- PV system due to the possibility of a short-circuit occurring during nighttime.
- Regenerative loads (if considered) due to the possibility of a short-circuit occurring when they are not operational.

The responsible for the calculation shall decide what is in and out of service for the maximum and minimum short-circuit current calculation. In some cases, a power source (e.g. PV system) may be neglected though its associated converter (with internal capacitors) may be in service.

4.4.2 Live Conductor Resistance

The DC resistance of a conductor is normally referred to a temperature of 20°C. The resistance produces heat in accordance with the I^2R equation, and this heat will raise the temperature of the conductor (and its insulation), increasing the resistance of the conductor. Therefore, the pre-fault conductor resistance varies and depends on the conductor loading.

It is important to acknowledge that the temperature of a conductor, and therefore the resistance, will increase during the short-circuit as the current becomes abnormally high. In addition, skin and proximity effects will occur due to the high di/dt (high frequency) nature of short-circuit currents with capacitor discharge. However, this is neglected with basic series RL or “ π ” circuit models. It shall be noted that skin and proximity effects are typically regarded as negligible for small cross-sections (usually considered as $<120\text{mm}^2$).

For **maximum** short-circuit current, the pre-fault conductor resistance shall be referenced at 20°C.

For **minimum** short-circuit current, the pre-fault conductor resistance shall be referenced at the maximum sustained operating temperature of the conductor. This is typically 90°C for thermosetting (e.g. Cross-Linked Polyethylene (XLPE)) insulation or 70°C for thermoplastic insulation. Other temperatures can be used, for example, if by design and proper selection the conductor operating temperature will not exceed a certain temperature.

An accepted formula to calculate the resistance at a temperature other than the referenced 20°C value is:

$$R_{T^{\circ}\text{C}} = R_{20^{\circ}\text{C}} \cdot [1 + \alpha \cdot (T - 20)] \quad (4.1)$$

where:

$R_{T^{\circ}\text{C}}$ is the pre-fault conductor resistance at temperature, T

T is the pre-fault conductor temperature in °C

$R_{20^{\circ}\text{C}}$ is the conductor resistance at a temperature of 20°C which can be calculated from the nominal cross-section (A), resistivity (ρ), and length (L): $\frac{L\rho}{A}$. Note: IEC 60228 provides maximum values of $R_{20^{\circ}\text{C}}$ for different types of common conductors/cables.

α is a factor equal to 0.004/K which is considered to have sufficient accuracy for copper and aluminium (although there are minor differences)

IEC 60287-1-1 provides temperature coefficients (α) of different materials. Figure 4.5 provides correction factors in relation to the referenced 20°C DC resistance. The marginal differences can be observed between copper ($\alpha = 0.00393/K$) and aluminium ($\alpha = 0.00403/K$). The displayed data points are based on $\alpha = 0.004/K$.

Figure 4.5: Resistance correction factors for different conductor operating temperatures and materials

4.4.3 PE Conductor Resistance

The PE conductor resistance should ideally be assessed differently to the live conductor because it is not designed to carry load current. There are various types of PE conductors; some types in cable circuits are illustrated in Figure 4.6.

Figure 4.6: Examples of different ways to distribute a PE conductor in a cable circuit

The required cross-sectional area (S) of a PE conductor can be determined by the formula defined in Section 543.1.2 of IEC 60364-5-54, which is dependent upon the prospective RMS short-circuit current (I), operating time of the protective device (t), and k factor which is based on the material, insulation, and initial and final temperatures.

If PE conductors are sized in accordance with the IEC 60364-5-54 formula, $S = \frac{\sqrt{I^2 t}}{k}$, then the initial temperature has already been defined. The initial temperature can be taken as the temperature to be used to compute the resistance for minimum short-circuit currents; this is because the formula is based on the adiabatic temperature rise from an initial temperature to a final temperature, and a higher initial temperature could lead to the PE not being adequate.

If an initial temperature of 30°C and a final temperature of 250°C is taken (e.g. PE conductor with 90°C thermosetting insulation not incorporated in a cable and not bunched with other cables), for a RMS short-circuit current of 40kA and a tripping time of 250ms, the required cross-sectional area of the PE conductor is 114mm² (i.e. 120mm² selected). However, if for the same conditions an initial temperature of 60°C is taken, the cross-sectional area would need to be at least 126mm². This highlights that the assumed initial temperature of the protective conductors in IEC 60364-5-54 is a limiting factor, and the initial temperature should not be higher than this (unless special design measures are taken).

Table 4.1: Initial temperatures for common PE conductors as defined in IEC 60364-5-54

Type	Illustration	IEC Table	Initial temperature (°C)
Insulated protective conductors not incorporated in cables and not bunched with other cables	<p>Separate PE conductor</p>	A.54.2	30
Protective conductors as a core incorporated in a cable or bunched with other cables or insulated conductors	<p>Integral PE conductor</p>	A.54.4	70 (70°C thermoplastic) 90 (90°C thermosetting)
Protective conductors as a metallic layer of a cable (e.g. armour, metallic sheath, etc.)	<p>Armour/metallic sheath as PE conductor</p>	A.54.5	60 (70°C thermoplastic) 80 (90°C thermosetting)

For the purpose of calculating maximum and minimum short-circuit current, the background of PE conductor selection can complicate the process and therefore a more simple approach is proposed.

For **maximum** short-circuit current, the pre-fault conductor resistance shall be referenced at 20°C. This is to align with the pre-fault resistance of the live conductor.

For **minimum** short-circuit current, the pre-fault conductor resistance shall be referenced at the maximum sustained operating temperature of the conductor, unless project-specific measures or equipment-specific considerations (e.g. casing of busway used as the PE) are taken. This will also

simplify short-circuit current calculations, as the same factors can be applied to both the live and PE conductor resistances.

4.4.4 Pre-Fault Voltage

The voltage before a short-circuit occurs will impact the short-circuit current. In the simplest form, a short-circuit loop can be viewed in most cases as a voltage source behind a constant impedance, meaning the higher the voltage, the higher the current. On the other hand, the lower the voltage, the lower the current.

Voltage levels across the DC system shall be considered, as well as the voltage level of the AC grid when AC/DC converters are present.

4.4.4.1 DC Grid Voltage

DC systems typically contain multiple sources and loads. Droop control is a control strategy that can be implemented to achieve energy balance. This means the voltage can fluctuate during normal operating conditions as the power needs of the system are met and therefore voltage bands are proposed in IEC Technical Report (TR) 63282.

IEC TR 63282 describes voltage areas to ensure safe interoperability. Along with the voltage bands (B1 through to B7), there are voltage areas (A1 through to A7) and ranges (R1 through to R4). To select pre-fault voltages for DC systems using the IEC TR 63282 voltage bands and areas, range R2 (system fault range) is deemed the most appropriate with areas A3 and A4. This is illustrated in Figure 4.7.

Figure 4.7: Voltage areas of active DC systems according to IEC TR 63282

Area A1 is the blackout state in which system operation cannot be maintained due to supply limitations. Area A5 and A6 are overvoltage states in which the voltage may enter due to switching events, and area A6 is where overvoltage protection devices should operate to limit the voltage. For this reason, only areas A3 and A4 in the R2 range is deemed appropriate for the selection of pre-fault voltages. Area A3 is the normal operating area and A4 is an abnormal state which can last for an extended period.

For **maximum** short-circuit current, the pre-fault voltage shall be U_4 for LVDC systems that use the IEC TR 63282 voltage bands and areas for voltage management. If the DC system is MV or does not have

voltage bands in accordance with IEC TR 63282, the maximum permitted voltage (excluding rapid transients) shall be used.

For **minimum** short-circuit current, the pre-fault voltage shall be U1 for LVDC systems that use the IEC TR 63282 voltage bands and areas for voltage management. If the DC system is Medium Voltage (MV) or does not have voltage bands in accordance with IEC TR 63282, the minimum permitted voltage (excluding rapid transients) shall be used.

It shall be noted that for LVDC systems using the IEC TR 63282 voltage bands, the U4 and U1 voltages will depend on the system rules being followed. For instance, in a system following Current/OS rules [8], the U4 and U1 voltages are 800V and 500V, respectively, for a nominal voltage of 700V. For a nominal voltage of 650V in a system following Open DC Alliance (ODCA) rules [9], the U4 and U1 voltages are 800V and 400V, respectively.

4.4.4.2 AC Grid Voltage

As described in Section 2.2, the maximum and minimum short-circuit currents (I''_{k3max} , I''_{k3min} , I''_{k1max} , and I''_{k1min}) along with the X/R ratios and voltage factors (c_{ACmax} and c_{ACmin}) shall be obtained from the IEC 60909 study for the calculation of the minimum and maximum AC source impedances, respectively.

For **maximum** short-circuit current, the AC voltage shall be equal to the voltage factor, c_{ACmax} , multiplied by the nominal line voltage, U_n , if IEC 60909 calculations have been conducted. Otherwise, the AC voltage shall be at the maximum permitted voltage (excluding rapid transients). It shall be noted that c_{ACmax} is typically either 1.05 or 1.10.

For **minimum** short-circuit current, the AC voltage shall be equal to the voltage factor, c_{ACmin} , multiplied by the nominal line voltage, U_n , if IEC 60909 calculations have been conducted. Otherwise, the AC voltage shall be at the minimum permitted voltage (excluding rapid transients). It shall be noted that c_{ACmin} is typically either 1.00, 0.95, or 0.90.

4.4.4.3 Battery Voltage

The voltage of a battery changes in relation to the state-of-charge. For the purposes of short-circuit current calculations, a battery is to be considered as either charged or discharged in relation to its nominal open circuit voltage.

For **maximum** short-circuit current, the battery voltage shall be equal to the voltage factor, c_{BATmax} , multiplied by the nominal open-circuit battery voltage, U_{BAT} .

For **minimum** short-circuit current, the battery voltage shall be equal to the voltage factor, c_{BATmin} , multiplied by the nominal open-circuit battery voltage, U_{BAT} .

4.4.5 Capacitance

The rated/nominal value of a capacitor is stated on capacitor data sheets along with a tolerance value. From a review of various manufacturer's data sheets of aluminium electrolytic capacitors [10], [11], a typical tolerance is $\pm 20\%$. This tolerance is in line with one of the preferred values of tolerances as stated in IEC 60384-4. However, based on IEC 60384-4 and [12], the negative tolerance can be as high as -30% and the positive tolerance can be as high as $+100\%$. Variation in the capacitance also occurs

due to temperature, frequency, and the type of cycling. Generally, the capacitance decreases at lower temperatures, higher frequency, and with more frequent charge/discharge cycles [12].

For **maximum** short-circuit current, the capacitance shall be 130% of the rated/nominal capacitance (C_C). This is based on the +20% tolerance typically defined on data sheets with an additional +10% to simplify the estimation of other factors.

For **minimum** short-circuit current, the capacitance shall be 70% of the rated/nominal capacitance (C_C). This is based on the -20% tolerance typically defined on data sheets with an additional -10% to simplify the estimation of other factors.

For more accurate capacitance values (for short-circuit studies), the capacitor manufacturer shall be consulted. If other types/technologies of capacitors are utilised, including supercapacitors, appropriate factors shall be determined.

4.4.6 Capacitor Equivalent Series Resistance

As already illustrated, a capacitor equivalent circuit can be reduced to a capacitor, resistor, and inductor connected in series and in some cases the inductor is neglected, so the equivalent circuit is reduced to a capacitor connected in series with a resistor.

The ESR is stated on data sheets, typically at a certain frequency and temperature (e.g. 100Hz and 20°C). Some data sheets also show the ESR under other conditions, notably a higher frequency and temperature (e.g. 300Hz and 60°C), which gives a lower value of ESR [10].

For **maximum** short-circuit current, the ESR shall be taken as 30% of the rated ESR (ESR_C) given for a frequency ~100Hz or ~120Hz at 20°C. This is based on a ratio between ESR measured at different temperatures and frequencies [10]. For more accurate ESR values (for short-circuit studies), the capacitor manufacturer shall be consulted.

For **minimum** short-circuit current, the ESR shall be taken as 100% of the rated ESR (ESR_C) given for a frequency ~100Hz or ~120Hz at 20°C. For more accurate ESR values (for short-circuit studies), the capacitor manufacturer shall be consulted.

4.4.7 Inductors

Considering the saturation characteristics of inductors when calculating short-circuit currents will provide the most accurate results. The type of inductor is an important aspect to consider when obtaining the characteristics. For example, an air-core inductor is not subjected to saturation effects like an iron-core inductor is.

To allow the inductor model to be appropriate for maximum and minimum short-circuit current calculation, a complete model based on the saturation characteristics (e.g. non-linear inductor) should be used. In some cases, the full saturation characteristics may not be available, so a fixed inductance value may need to be applied.

For **maximum** short-circuit currents, if the inductor saturation characteristics are not available for a complete model, the saturated inductance (L_{SAT}) value shall be used as a fixed value.

For **minimum** short-circuit currents, if the inductor saturation characteristics are not available for a complete model, the unsaturated inductance (L_{USAT}) value shall be used as a fixed value. If the inductor saturation current is known, the saturated inductance (L_{SAT}) may be considered providing the inductor current exceeds the saturation current. It shall be noted that the inductance will impact the transient phase of the short-circuit current, whereas the steady-state phase will primarily be impacted by the inductance on the AC system (i.e. not the DC system inductance).

4.4.8 Converter Limitation Capability

As described in Section 2.1.3.1, some converters can limit the steady-state output current during short-circuit conditions. With certain techniques such as “fold-back”, the output current can be less than rated (maximum) current at periods of very low voltage that may be experienced during a short-circuit. Figure 4.8 is a typical example of this technique. Other current limiting techniques are possible.

Figure 4.8: Illustration of “fold-back” current limitation

For **maximum** short-circuit current, the maximum limited output current ($I_{SS-SCmax}$) declared by the manufacturer shall be used and sustained over time.

For **minimum** short-circuit current, the minimum limited output current ($I_{SS-SCmin}$) declared by the manufacturer shall be used and sustained for a time (t_{SS-SC}) declared by the manufacturer, or the limited output current shall equal zero. The use of a voltage-dependent current source model may give more representative results (see Figure 2.4 and related text).

4.4.9 Battery Resistance

The battery resistance will depend on the state-of-charge, state-of-health, and cell temperature [13]. The effect of these dependencies will vary for different battery technologies. Furthermore, for very accurate battery models, the temperature-dependency would need to be accounted for when considering events beyond the millisecond range [13].

For the purpose of calculating maximum and minimum short-circuit current, a more simple approach is proposed.

For **maximum** short-circuit current, the battery resistance (R_{BAT}) shall be modified to R_{BATmin} . The battery manufacturer shall be consulted if required to determine R_{BATmin} .

For **minimum** short-circuit current, the battery resistance (R_{BAT}) shall be modified to R_{BATmax} . The battery manufacturer shall be consulted if required to determine R_{BATmax} .

4.4.10 Summary

Table 4.2 summarises the conditions that shall be considered for maximum and minimum short-circuit current calculations. Other conditions can be imposed as appropriate for the studied network.

Table 4.2: Conditions for calculating maximum and minimum short-circuit current

Parameter	Conditions for maximum short-circuit current	Conditions for minimum short-circuit current
System configuration	Configuration and operational mode that leads to the maximum value of prospective current at the short-circuit.	Configuration and operational mode that leads to the minimum value of prospective current at the short-circuit. Note: PV system (and regenerative load, if considered) contribution shall be neglected.
Reference temperature of live conductor resistances	20°C	Maximum sustained conductor operating temperature.
Reference temperature of PE conductor resistances	20°C	Maximum sustained conductor operating temperature. Note: Equipment-specific considerations (e.g. casing of busway used as the PE) may be taken.
DC grid pre-fault voltage	$U_{DC} \times c_{DCmax}$ (equal to U4 for LVDC IEC TR 63282 voltage band systems) Alternatively, the maximum permitted voltage (excluding rapid transients) shall be used for other LVDC and MVDC systems.	$U_{DC} \times c_{DCmin}$ (equal to U1 for LVDC IEC TR 63282 voltage band systems) Alternatively, the minimum permitted voltage (excluding rapid transients) shall be used for other LVDC and MVDC systems.
AC grid pre-fault voltage	$U_n \times c_{ACmax}$ (IEC 60909 calculation) Alternatively, the maximum permitted voltage (excluding rapid transients) shall be used.	$U_n \times c_{ACmin}$ (IEC 60909 calculation) Alternatively, the minimum permitted voltage (excluding rapid transients) shall be used.
Battery pre-fault voltage	$U_{BAT} \times c_{BATmax}$	$U_{BAT} \times c_{BATmin}$
Capacitance	$C_C \times 1.3$	$C_C \times 0.7$
Capacitor ESR	$ESR_C \times 0.3$ Note: 0.3 is typical factor and the initial temperature shall be considered.	$ESR_C \times 1.0$ Note: 1.0 is typical factor and the initial temperature shall be considered.
Inductors	Use inductor saturation characteristics. Note: If saturation characteristics are not available, the saturated values (L_{SAT} , X_{SAT}) shall be used.	Use inductor saturation characteristics. Note: If saturation characteristics are not available, the unsaturated values (L_{USAT} , X_{USAT}) shall be used.
Converter steady-state limitation capability	$I_{SS-SCmax}$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$ Note: This can equal zero if the current is cut (e.g. self-protected converters).	$I_{SS-SCmin}$ for t_{SS-SC} Note: This can equal zero if the current is cut (e.g. self-protected converters). The use of a voltage-dependent current source model may give more representative results.
Battery resistance	R_{BATmin}	R_{BATmax}

4.5 Calculation

Once the full studied network is modelled with all parameters adjusted as necessary for either maximum or minimum short-circuit current calculation, the calculation can start once initial conditions are set and a short-circuit is placed in the model. Refer to Table 5.1 for guidance on the location of the short-circuit.

4.5.1 Model Configuration

This section provides some considerations when configuring the simulation model prior to the calculation. However, the responsible person(s) for the calculation will require knowledge of the software platform being used to configure the simulation, make any necessary adaptations, and ensure the results are reasonable and valid.

Consideration shall be made to the simulation time-step. A time-step of 1 μ s is typically suitable for most networks and provides relatively fast simulation speed, however a different time-step may be required depending on the network model and software.

The initial conditions, at time ≤ 0 s, of the simulation shall be:

- All voltage sources set
- All capacitors pre-charged to the initial voltage
- All current sources set
- Short-circuit in the model

As described in Section 1, a short-circuit is considered as an abnormal zero-impedance connection between live conductors of different potential, or a live conductor and an exposed-conductive-part or a protective conductor of different potential. In a simulation environment, a zero-impedance connection may not be possible (depending on the software); thus, a resistance $\leq 1\mu\Omega$ shall be used. If a short-circuit transition is required for simulation purposes, then the short-circuit shall be modelled as a variable resistor, transitioning from 1M Ω to $\leq 1\mu\Omega$ in $\leq 1\mu$ s. If a transition is required, attention shall be given to the voltage and current sources to check whether the behaviour is normal.

4.5.2 Outputs

The current shall be measured at the short-circuit location and at each protective device location or at each circuit branch. The main short-circuit current calculation outputs shall be:

- The peak current magnitude, from the instantaneous current value
- The steady-state current magnitude, from the mean current value in the steady-state phase
- The current rate-of-rise $\left(\frac{\Delta i}{\Delta t}\right)$, from the instantaneous current value at a defined current magnitude

An example of obtaining the main short-circuit current calculation outputs are given in Figure 4.9. These main outputs have been selected with consideration to emerging technologies and future standards, such as semiconductor circuit-breakers. The current magnitude for calculating the current rate-of-rise $\left(\frac{\Delta i}{\Delta t}\right)$ shall be defined according to the semiconductor circuit-breaker standard definition.

In the future IEC 60947-10 standard, the initial rate-of-rise is of interest, therefore the rate-of-rise can be referenced at a very low current magnitude at the onset of the short-circuit. In UL 489i, this is proposed to be 63% of the peak current for capacitive discharge interrupting. It should be noted that

other conditions may apply for certain circuit-breakers (such as those complying with the future IEC 60947-10 standard), such as the maximum switchable inductance, and must be respected.

Figure 4.9: Short-circuit current characterisation example and main calculation outputs

It should be acknowledged that with this calculation approach, further outputs can be obtained as required. For example, accurate I^2t values or the RMS current can be obtained as the full short-circuit current waveform is understood and this can assist with equipment and protective device assessments and selections.

5 Short-Circuit Current Calculation Example for Protection

To illustrate the application of the methodology presented earlier, this section provides a practical example with a realistic use case.

5.1 Introduction

This example uses the methodology described in Section 4 to calculate short-circuit currents and gives a focus on overcurrent protection. The power system considered for this example is based on Figure 4.1 with an additional passive load circuit and protective device to allow an illustrative focus on overcurrent protection. Refer to Figure 5.1 and Figure 5.2 for the diagrams including these modifications.

In addition to Table 4.2, Table 5.1 describes further conditions that shall be considered for calculating maximum and minimum short-circuit current for overcurrent protection purposes.

Table 5.1: Extra conditions for overcurrent protection

Parameter	Conditions for maximum short-circuit current	Conditions for minimum short-circuit current
Fault location	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) At each DC bus/switchboard. 2) At the source-end of a circuit, providing short-circuit sources are on one side only of a protective device. 3) On both immediate sides of a protective device, providing short-circuit sources are on both sides of the protective device. <p><u>Note:</u> 1) is for busbar/switchboard sizing. 2) and 3) are for protective device sizing.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) At the remote-end of a circuit, providing short-circuit sources are on one side only of a protective device. 2) On both sides of a protective device at the remote-end of the circuit, providing short-circuit sources are on both sides of the protective device. <p><u>Note:</u> 1) and 2) are for protection purposes.</p>

5.2 Data Gathering

This section contains the input data but does not show how the input data is used or derived. It is the responsibility of the person(s) in charge of the calculation to obtain the necessary input data.

5.2.1 Single Line Diagram and System Configuration

The power system considered for this example is illustrated in Figure 5.1 (single line diagram) and Figure 5.2 (more detailed network diagram).

It shall be noted that the impedances of the DC grid buses are neglected from the network diagram and from this example case for brevity.

Figure 5.1: Example case: Simplified SLD with only one overcurrent protective device (PD) shown

Figure 5.2: Example case: Network diagram with only one overcurrent PD shown

The earthing arrangement for the main DC grid is Terre-neutre Separé (TN-S) and is achieved by connecting the Line conductor with negative polarity (L-) to earth reference, and the AC grid supply is isolated. The SRC is located at the AC/DC non-isolated InterLink 2-level converter, denoted SRC 1. The earthing arrangement for the sub-DC grid is TN-S and is achieved by connecting the L- polarity to earth reference. The SRC is located at the DC/DC isolated Single Active Bridge (SAB), denoted SRC 2.

The system configuration and operational scenarios considered are:

- For **maximum** short-circuit current, all short-circuit contributors are available and connected to the system.
- For **minimum** short-circuit current, only the AC/DC non-isolated InterLink 2-level converter is available and connected to the system feeding the load. This is due to an operational restriction in which the system cannot operate and will shut down in the event the InterLink converter is not connected, whilst all other sources can be unavailable/disconnected.

The DC grids are Low Voltage (LV) and designed in line with IEC TR 63282 voltage band systems, with a nominal voltage (U_{DC}) of 700V. The pre-fault voltages of the DC grids are:

- For **maximum** short-circuit current, $U_{DC} \times c_{DCmax}$ equal to U4 (800V in this example)
- For **minimum** short-circuit current, $U_{DC} \times c_{DCmin}$ equal to U1 (500V in this example)

5.2.2 AC (Grid) Supply Data

The following data is considered from IEC 60909 calculations:

- U_n 400 V
- c_{ACmax} 1.1
- c_{ACmin} 0.9
- f_n 50 Hz
- I''_{k3max} 10 kA
- $(X/R)_{k3max}$ 5
- I''_{k3min} 6 kA
- $(X/R)_{k3min}$ 3

As the AC grid supply is isolated (e.g. by a power-frequency transformer that is external to the AC/DC converter) and power system earthing is realised on the DC system, the AC supply can be represented by only the positive-sequence impedance. Hence why I''_{k1} and $(X/R)_{k1}$ values are not available.

From the equations in Section 2.2, the minimum and maximum positive-sequence impedances for maximum and minimum short-circuit current, respectively, can be computed and are:

- Z_{1min} 0.02540 Ω
- R_{1min} 0.00498 Ω
- X_{1min} 0.02491 Ω
- L_{1min} 0.07929 mH
- Z_{1max} 0.03464 Ω
- R_{1max} 0.01095 Ω
- X_{1max} 0.03286 Ω
- L_{1max} 0.10461 mH

5.2.3 Battery Data

The following data is considered for the total battery system:

- U_{BAT} 500 V
- c_{BATmax} 1.05
- c_{BATmin} 0.90
- R_{BAT} 0.013 Ω
- L_{BAT} 0.03 mH

The decreasing current behaviour is not considered. $R_{BAT} = R_{BATmax} = R_{BATmin}$ in this example.

5.2.4 PV System Data

The following data is considered for the total PV array system:

- $I_{SCSTCARRAY}$ 30 A
- K_I 1.25
- $U_{OCARRAY}$ 600 V

5.2.5 Capacitor Data

The following data is considered for the load capacitor:

- C_C 0.005 F
- ESR_C 0.005 Ω
- ESL_C Neglected
- V_C $U_{DC} \times c_{DC}$

5.2.6 AC/DC and DC/DC Converter Data

The following data is considered for the AC/DC non-isolated InterLink 2-level converter:

- R_{ACind} 4.25 m Ω
- $L_{ACindSAT}$ 200 μ H
- $L_{ACindUSAT}$ 680 μ H
- C_C 10 mF
- ESR_C 6.7 m Ω
- ESL_C 30 nH
- V_C $U_{DC} \times c_{DC}$
- R_{add} 2 m Ω
- L_{add} 2 μ H

The following data is considered for the DC/DC non-isolated boost converter (bidirectional):

- Battery side:
 - C_C 10 μ F
 - ESR_C 7 m Ω
 - ESL_C Neglected
 - V_C $U_{BAT} \times c_{BAT}$
 - R_{add} 2 m Ω
 - L_{add} 2 μ H
 - L_{FSAT} 0.5 mH
 - L_{FUSAT} Neglected
- Main DC grid side:
 - C_C 10 μ F
 - ESR_C 7 m Ω
 - ESL_C Neglected
 - V_C $U_{DC} \times c_{DC}$
 - R_{add} 2 m Ω
 - L_{add} 2 μ H

The following data is considered for the DC/DC non-isolated boost converter (unidirectional):

- PV system side:
 - C_C 10 μ F
 - ESR_C 7 m Ω
 - ESL_C Neglected
 - V_C $U_{OCARRAY}$
 - R_{add} 2 m Ω
 - L_{add} 2 μ H
 - L_{FSAT} 0.5 mH
 - L_{FUSAT} Neglected

- Main DC grid side:
 - C_C 10 μ F
 - ESR_C 7 m Ω
 - ESL_C Neglected
 - V_C $U_{DC} \times C_{DC}$
 - R_{add} 2 m Ω
 - L_{add} 2 μ H

The following data is considered for the DC/DC isolated SAB:

- Main DC grid side:
 - C_C 1.5 mF
 - ESR_C 65 m Ω
 - ESL_C Neglected
 - V_C $U_{DC} \times C_{DC}$ (of main DC grid)
 - R_{add} 2 m Ω
 - L_{add} 2 μ H
- The sub-DC grid side of the SAB is neglected in this example due to the location of the short-circuits.

5.2.7 Circuit Data

The following data is considered for circuit 1:

- $R_{LIVEpul20^\circ C}$ 0.124 m Ω /m (150mm² cable)
- $R_{PEpul20^\circ C}$ 0.387 m Ω /m (50mm² cable)
- $L_{LIVEpul}$ 0.5 μ H/m
- L_{PEpul} 0.5 μ H/m
- l 20 m

The following data is considered for circuit 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7:

- $R_{LIVEpul20^\circ C}$ 0.524 m Ω /m (35mm² cable)
- $R_{PEpul20^\circ C}$ 1.150 m Ω /m (16mm² cable)
- $L_{LIVEpul}$ 0.35 μ H/m
- L_{PEpul} 0.35 μ H/m
- l 30 m

For circuit resistance corrections for minimum short-circuit current, the maximum sustained operating temperature for all conductors is considered as 90°C.

5.3 Model

The model for calculating the maximum short-circuit current specifically for assessing the requirements of the overcurrent protective device “PD” is given in Figure 5.3. Considering the extra conditions of Table 5.1, the short-circuit locations (L+ to L- and L+ to PE) are at the source-end of the circuit, which is also the same as the main DC grid bus location. All short-circuit contributors are available and connected to the system as per Section 5.2.1. All input data used in this model will be in accordance with the conditions of Table 4.2 for maximum short-circuit current.

Figure 5.3: Example case: Model and short-circuit locations for assessing maximum short-circuit current

The model for calculating the minimum short-circuit current specifically for assessing the requirements of the overcurrent protective device “PD” is given in Figure 5.4. Considering the extra conditions of Table 5.1, the short-circuit locations (L+ to L- and L+ to PE) are at the remote-end of the circuit. Only the AC/DC non-isolated InterLink 2-level converter is available and connected to the system feeding the load as per Section 5.2.1. This is why all other equipment is greyed-out, indicating it is not available/connected. All input data used in this model will be in accordance with the conditions of Table 4.2 for minimum short-circuit current.

Figure 5.4: Example case: Model and short-circuit locations for assessing minimum short-circuit current

5.4 Calculation & Output

Based on the gathered data and developed models, a time-domain simulation is performed with a time-step of $1\mu\text{s}$. The short-circuit is placed in the model at time equal to zero. The current is measured at the short-circuit location, which in this example is also the protective device branch, as well as the contribution from each source or converter. The short-circuit current waveforms from the calculations are given in Figure 5.5 and Figure 5.6.

Figure 5.5: Example case: Prospective maximum short-circuit currents

Figure 5.6: Example case: Prospective minimum short-circuit currents

From these results, the main short-circuit current calculation outputs stated in Section 4.5.2 can be obtained.

Table 5.2: Example case: Main short-circuit current calculation outputs

Short-circuit case	Peak short-circuit current	Steady-state short-circuit current	Current rate-of-rise ^(NOTE 1)
Maximum, L+ to L-	27.7 kA	13.0 kA	48.1 A/μs
Maximum, L+ to PE	19.4 kA	11.0 kA	22.8 A/μs
Minimum, L+ to L-	3.94 kA	1.17 kA	5.43 A/μs
Minimum, L+ to PE	3.26 kA	1.13 kA	4.91 A/μs

(NOTE 1) Defined based on the peak short-circuit current

The differences in the total short-circuit (and protective device) current and contributions from each source can easily be observed.

For maximum short-circuit current, the differences between the positive polarity Line conductor, L+, to L- and L+ to PE short-circuits are obvious in this example. Due to the higher impedance fault loop created by the L+ to PE short-circuit (compared to the L+ to L- short-circuit), the contribution from each source is reduced, resulting in a lower transient and steady-state short-circuit current. This is also emphasised by the longer fault loop for some sources due to the location of the system referencing conductor (i.e. SRC 1).

For minimum short-circuit current, the differences are less obvious as there is only one contribution to the short-circuit – the AC/DC InterLink converter. However, the L+ to PE short-circuit has resulted in a slightly lower transient and steady-state short-circuit current in this example due to the higher impedance PE conductors.

These prospective maximum and minimum short-circuit current calculation outputs will enable the responsible person(s) to verify equipment capabilities and deploy appropriate protection plans i.e. devices and settings.

6 Conclusion

This deliverable provides a comprehensive methodology for the calculation of prospective short-circuit currents in a DC system and DC system supplied by power converters.

The first chapter introduces the necessity to understand the prospective short-circuit current throughout an electrical installation. The main requirement is to ensure safety by protecting life and assets, which requires the calculation of the maximum and minimum prospective short-circuit currents. The transient and steady-state phases of a short-circuit current are described, illustrating that short-circuit currents in a DC system can be very different to that of traditional AC systems and battery-fed DC systems.

Furthermore, the different approaches to calculating DC short-circuit currents are explored by firstly examining the approaches in IEC 61660 and IEEE Std 946. The most relevant existing standard is IEC 61660, as this contains a methodology for the calculation of maximum and minimum short-circuit currents, whereas IEEE Std 946 provides guidance about short-circuit current assessments (i.e. it lacks a methodology and calculation approach). Both standards have several shortcomings when dealing with present and future DC systems and applications. Notably, the limited number and type of short-circuit current sources including power converters that can significantly contribute to and influence the short-circuit current. Due to this, the calculation approach of time-domain simulation with simplified short-circuit behavioural models is selected in this methodology. It is deemed the most practical approach whilst providing a sufficient level of accuracy, and it can be rapidly and widely adopted using existing commercial software making it favourable for the Shift2DC project.

Subsequently, the second chapter highlights the main sources of short-circuit current that are foreseen in a DC system including power converters, AC sources, capacitors, PV systems, and batteries. Each of these sources are described in terms of its behaviour under short-circuit conditions, with a simplified model proposed with the minimum level of description required for time-domain simulation. Regenerative loads and fuel cells are acknowledged as potential short-circuit contributors; however further details (as given for other sources) are not provided.

As power converters play such an essential role in the realisation and development of DC power systems and have not been greatly considered in existing standards (related to DC short-circuit currents) to date, the second chapter includes an introductory section to power converters. The concept of limiting and non-limiting converters is given and the characterisation of their short-circuit behaviour is expanded upon, illustrating three possible stages of the short-circuit current. This generalisation assists in developing and understanding the simplified short-circuit behavioural models for common power converter topologies which are given in Table 2.1. These models are intended to describe the output current during short-circuit conditions and shall not be used for any other purpose. The use of detailed power converter models is not prohibited, providing they describe to a better extent the short-circuit behaviour.

Having explored the calculation necessity, purpose, and approach, as well as the behaviour and models of DC system short-circuit contributors, the third and fourth chapters delve into the methodology of how to undertake the calculation. This consists of 5 main areas:

1. Gathering the input data
2. Building network model
3. Modelling components
4. Adjusting/configuring the model (i.e. applying conditions for maximum and minimum current)
5. Running the computation and extracting the required outputs

Guidance on building the network model is provided and the modelling of other network components such as cable/busbar circuits and protective devices are discussed. A key part of the methodology is the conditions to consider when calculating maximum and minimum prospective short-circuit current. The conditions include the system configuration, conductor resistances, pre-fault (DC and AC) voltages, variation in capacitor characteristics (capacitance and ESR), inductor characteristics, converter limitation capability, and battery resistance. For each condition, context is given in terms of why this should be considered and how typical condition values/factors (if given) are derived. Moreover, the calculation outputs of peak short-circuit current, steady-state short-circuit current, and short-circuit current rate-of-rise $\left(\frac{\Delta i}{\Delta t}\right)$ are defined as these are deemed necessary when considering emerging technologies and future standards, such as semiconductor circuit-breakers.

Finally, the application of the methodology to a sample network is illustrated, starting from the data gathering process through to obtaining the maximum and minimum prospective short-circuit current calculation outputs.

In summary, this methodology facilitates the calculation of maximum and minimum prospective short-circuit currents in a DC system and DC system supplied by power converters. It will enable the person(s) responsible to verify equipment capabilities and deploy appropriate (current-based) protection plans, including the selection of suitable protective devices and protection settings to mitigate the effects and consequences of short-circuit currents.

7 Applicable Standards

IEC Standards

DC Short-Circuit Current Calculation

- **IEC 61660-1:1997** – First edition 1997-06, *Short-circuit currents in d.c. auxiliary installations in power plants and substations – Part 1: Calculation of short-circuit currents*
- **IEC/TR 61660-3:2000** – First edition 2000-02, *Short-circuit currents in d.c. auxiliary installations in power plants and substations – Part 3: Examples of calculations*

AC Short-Circuit Current Calculation

- **IEC 60909-0:2016** – Edition 2.0 2016-01, *Short-circuit currents in three-phase a.c. systems – Part 0: Calculation of currents*

Electrical Installations and Protection (IEC 60364 series)

- **IEC 60364-5-54:2021** – Earthing arrangements and protective conductors
- **IEC 60364-7-712:2017** – Edition 2.0 2017-04, *Low voltage electrical installations – Part 7-712: Requirements for special installations or locations – Solar photovoltaic (PV) power supply systems*
- **IEC 60364-5-54 COMPIL:2021** – *Low-voltage electrical installations – Part 5-54: Selection and erection of electrical equipment – Earthing arrangements and protective conductors*

Component Standards

- **IEC 60384-4:2016**, 2016-08 – *Fixed capacitors for use in electronic equipment – Part 4: Sectional specification – Fixed aluminium electrolytic capacitors with solid (MnO₂) and non-solid electrolyte.*
- **IEC CDV 60947-10** (121A/635/CDV), *Low-voltage switchgear and controlgear – Part 10: Semiconductor Circuit-Breakers. (or similar).*

Conductor and Cable Sizing

- **IEC 60228:2023**, Edition 4.0 2023-12 – *Conductors of insulated cables.*
- **IEC 60287-1-1:2023**, Edition 3.0 2023-05 – *Electric cables – Calculation of the current rating – Part 1-1: Current rating equations (100 % load factor) and calculation of losses – General*

System Performance and Power Quality

- **IEC TR 63282:2024** – LVDC systems – Assessment of standard voltages and power quality requirements

IEEE Standards

DC Power Systems and Protection

- **IEEE Std 946-2020** – Recommended Practice for the Design of DC Power Systems for Stationary Applications

UL Standards

Drafts and Manufacturer Guidance

- **UL 489i (Draft)** – Proposed standard for DC circuit-breakers, particularly those interrupting capacitive discharges. Defines testing thresholds such as 63% of peak current and emerging requirements for semiconductor breakers.

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APPENDIX A: IEC 61660 vs. Time-Domain Simulation for Capacitors

A comparison of the IEC 61660 calculation method and time-domain simulation is performed for a system of only capacitor sources, with the capacitors distributed across an impedance network to represent a typical section of a DC system supplied by power converters. This is to assess the performance of the IEC 61660 calculation method with parallel capacitors having different impedances up to the short-circuit location.

The network used for this assessment is as per Figure A.1. The capacitors have a capacitance of 7.5mF and an ESR of 5mΩ and are pre-charged to 715V. All other impedance (series RL) components signify cable impedance with values that are representative of 10m of 50mm² cable i.e. 0.37mΩ/m and 0.5μH/m.

Figure A.1: Network of distributed capacitors for comparison

For this comparison case, PowerFactory (DIgSILENT) software was used to compute the short-circuit current at the short-circuit location and corrected partial short-circuit currents for each capacitor branch in accordance with IEC 61660. The MATLAB/Simulink environment was used for time-domain simulation.

The current waveforms from the time-domain simulation and those derived from the IEC 61660 calculation results (i.e. characteristic quantities) are shown in Figure A.2. It shall be noted that the total short-circuit current plot is the short-circuit current at the short-circuit location, and the partial short-circuit current plots are the corrected partial short-circuit currents for each capacitor branch for the IEC calculation, or the capacitor contribution in the time-domain simulation.

Although not explicitly depicted in IEC 61660, the corrected partial short-circuit current is presumed to be the contribution from the capacitor to the short-circuit because the total short-circuit current is determined from the superposition of the corrected partial short-circuit currents.

Figure A.2: Short-circuit current and (corrected) partial short-circuit current results

From the calculation results, the peak and rising time of the total short-circuit current calculated with the IEC 61660 method is very similar to the time-domain simulation. The same can be said for the contribution from capacitor C3, C4, and C5. However, the capacitor contribution from C1 and C2, which are the most electrically distant capacitors from the short-circuit location, is not accurate. The peak current has a lower magnitude and the time to reach the peak current is too fast. This could be an issue if accurate contribution from each contributing source is required, for example, for protection assessments.

The portion of the current waveform after the peak current is not accurate in all cases with the IEC 61660 calculation method.

APPENDIX B: Converter Switching Model vs. Simplified Model

In this appendix, a comparison between a full switching and simplified converter model for short-circuit behaviour is conducted. The converter used in this example is a DC/DC non-isolated buck converter (bidirectional). The main converter ratings are:

- Nominal power: 100 kW
- Nominal input voltage: 1300 V (with a battery source)
- Nominal output voltage: 700 V
- Nominal output current: 142 A
- Limited (maximum setpoint) output current: 170 A (120%) constant output

A pole-to-pole short-circuit is on the lower-voltage side and thus the simplified converter model consists of a current source, diode with high resistance (500 Ω) snubber, inductor, and capacitor. The additional resistance (R_{add}) and inductance (L_{add}) up to the converter terminals is neglected in this example and an external 70mm² cable is present as shown in Figure B.1. The inductor and capacitor characteristics match those of the switching model. The current source is set to the limited steady-state short-circuit (output) current of 170A.

A basic overview of the switching converter model with a battery input is also given in Figure B.1. It is modelled with switch-diode pairs controlled by firing pulses produced by a generator. The control includes a voltage and current loop with current-limiting control which operates based on configuration, reference values, and measurement inputs.

Figure B.1: Converter models for a short-circuit on the lower-voltage side (test case)

The results of the short-circuit simulation are plotted in Figure B.2. Whilst there is slight deviation in what happens inside the converter (i.e. inductor current is not exact), the output current is nearly identical. This indicates that a simplified model, if used appropriately, can give a very good estimation of the converter prospective output current during a short-circuit.

Figure B.2: Comparison of converter switching and simplified model under short-circuit conditions

APPENDIX C: Frequency Effect on Resistance and Inductance

This appendix illustrates the effect that frequency has on the resistance and inductance of a circuit/conductor. This emphasises that the person(s) in charge of the short-circuit current calculation shall determine appropriate impedance values when circuit models with fixed (i.e. non-frequency-dependent) resistance and inductance values are used.

The basic conductor arrangement shown in Figure C.1 was modelled in software [13] which is dedicated for the modelling of transmission lines. The method and formulas for computing cable parameters are very complex and demanding, hence they are omitted for brevity, and the software results are relied upon.

Figure C.1: Cable arrangement and cross-section view

Based on the physical geometry as well as conductor and insulation properties which are the input parameters, the cable parameters were computed by the software [13]. Figure C.2 shows the effect that frequency has on the resistance and inductance of the basic conductor arrangement. Only the trends are illustrated without explicit impedance values, as the values can change significantly depending on the conductors and how they are arranged.

Figure C.2: Typical resistance and inductance trends as a function of frequency (basic cable circuit)

APPENDIX D: Power Converter Short-Circuit Models

This section has been included to enlarge the diagrams of Table 2.1. In the following Figures, (a) is the block diagram, (b) is the simplified topology diagram, and (c) is the simplified short-circuit model.

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Figure D.3: Diagrams of DC/DC non-isolated boost converter (unidirectional)

Figure D.4: Diagrams of DC/DC non-isolated boost converter (bidirectional)

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Figure D.6: Diagrams of DC/DC non-isolated buck converter (bidirectional)

Figure D.7: Diagrams of DC/DC isolated SAB

Figure D.8: Diagrams of DC/DC isolated dual active bridge (DAB)

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Executive Summary

This document, prepared as part of the Shift2DC project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe program, is part of a series of four interrelated deliverables that reference each other:

- D2.2.A, Earthing Systems for DC Microgrids.
- D2.2.B, Protection Plan Methodology.
- D2.2.C, Short-Circuit Current Calculation Methodology.
- D2.2.D, Selectivity in DC systems.

This deliverable D2.2.D, presents a comprehensive methodology for achieving selectivity in Low Voltage Direct Current (LVDC) systems, within the context of the Shift2DC project. Selectivity is a critical aspect of electrical protection design, ensuring that only the faulty section of a network is isolated during a fault, thereby maintaining service continuity elsewhere.

The document begins by reviewing conventional selectivity principles in Alternating Current (AC) systems—such as time-based, current-based, energy-based, logic, directional, and differential selectivity—and evaluates their applicability to LVDC networks. It then identifies the unique challenges posed by LVDC systems, particularly those related to the behaviour of power converters, bidirectional fault currents in multisource systems, and the risk of sympathetic tripping.

Two main scenarios are analysed: systems with non-limiting converters requiring ultra-fast protection, and systems with current limiting converters that may allow for more conventional protection schemes. Various protection technologies are assessed, including fuses, Electromechanical Circuit Breakers (EMCBs), Semiconductor Hybrid Circuit Breakers (SCHCBs), and Solid-State Circuit Breakers (SCCBs). The document also explores advanced strategies such as directional and logic-based selectivity, centralized protection schemes, and other innovative architectures based on capacitors.

The findings highlight that while traditional protection methods face limitations in LVDC environments, emerging technologies—particularly SCCBs—offer promising solutions for ensuring selectivity and enhancing system resilience.

While promising, many of the technologies capable of delivering the required selectivity performance are still emerging and under development. It is expected that new solutions will continue to appear in the coming years, driven by the evolving needs of LVDC systems and the increasing integration of power electronics.

This study reinforces the idea that a robust protection system is always a compromise between the performance of converters and protection devices—particularly when aiming to ensure both selectivity and continuity of service. Achieving this balance is essential for the reliable and resilient operation of future LVDC networks.

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Keywords, Acronym

AC	Alternating Current
ACB	Air Circuit Breaker
ANSI	American National Standards Institute
DC	Direct Current
di/dt	Current rate-of-rise
EMCB	Electromechanical Circuit-Breaker
FRT	Fault Ride Through
FW	Forward direction
HV	High Voltage
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEV	International Electrotechnical Vocabulary
IGBT	Insulated-Gate Bipolar Transistor
I_{OUT}	Output current
TN	Electric system according to IEC 60364-1 where one live part is directly connected to earth, and exposed-conductive-parts are connected to the earthed point where the live part is connected to earth
TN-C	TN electric system where the function of a live conductor is combined with the function of a protective earthing conductor to form a single conductor
TN-S	TN electric system where live conductors and protective earthing conductors are separated from each other
IT	Electric system according to IEC 60364-1 where all live parts are isolated from earth, or one live part is connected to earth through a high impedance
TT	Electric system according to IEC 60364-1 where one live part is directly connected to earth, and exposed-conductive-parts are connected to earth, independent of the earthing of the live parts of the electric system
L	Line conductor (also a live conductor)
L-	Line conductor, negative polarity (also a live conductor)
L+	Line conductor, positive polarity (also a live conductor)
LV	Low Voltage
LVAC	Low Voltage Alternating Current
LVDC	Low Voltage Direct Current
LVRT	Low Voltage Ride-Through
M	Mid-point conductor (also a live conductor)
MCB	Miniature Circuit Breaker
MCCB	Moulded Case Circuit Breaker
MOSFE	Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor Field-Effect Transistor
T	
MV	Medium Voltage
OCPD	Overcurrent Protective Device
PD	Protective Device
PDU	Power Distribution Unit
RCCB	Residual Current Circuit Breaker

RCD	Residual Current Device
RV	Reverse direction
SCCB	Semiconductor Circuit-Breaker
SCHCB	Semiconductor Hybrid Circuit-Breaker
SiC	Silicon Carbide
SLD	Single Line Diagram
SRC	System Referencing Conductor
SSCB	Solid-State Circuit-Breaker
UVLO	Undervoltage Lockout
UVRT	Under Voltage Ride-Through
V_{OUT}	Output voltage
ZSI	Zone Selective Interlocking

Symbols, Subscripts

E_{cap}	Energy stored in the input capacitor
I_{comb}	Combined breaking capacity of two devices in series
I_{osc}	Oscillating current during or after fault clearance
I_r	Pick-up threshold current for current-based protection
I_{scmax}	Maximum prospective short-circuit current at the installation point
I_s	Selectivity limit current
$I_{\Delta n}$	Rated residual operating current of a residual protection device
V_{cap}	Voltage across the converter input capacitor
V_{dc}	DC bus voltage
V_{min}	Minimum voltage required to maintain converter operation
k_r	Long-time threshold ratio between two protection devices
k_{sd}	Short-time threshold ratio between two protection devices
t_{FRT}	Fault Ride Through duration
A	Upstream protection device
B	Downstream protection device
D1	Upstream overcurrent protective device
D2	Downstream overcurrent protective device
F1, F2, F3	Fault locations in the DC network or source
I^2t	Joule integral
T	Operating time of a protection device
V_{ov}	Overtoltage level at which protection triggers
k	Selectivity coefficient for fuses
ΔI	Current difference used for fault detection
Δt	Time delay between protective device operations

1 Introduction

The purpose of this document is to overview protection selectivity, describe the fundamental principles, explain the challenges and constraints in LVDC power systems, and outline new methods and/or techniques to achieve and improve selectivity in LVDC power systems.

Furthermore, this document highlights certain network phenomenon that can impact selectivity, to allow those responsible for the electrical network/protection design to make necessary considerations.

This deliverable outlines a methodology for achieving **protection selectivity in LVDC systems**, addressing both conventional and advanced strategies adapted to converter-based, multi-source architectures.

Chapter 1 and 2 introduces the **objectives and scope** of the document, defines the **concept of selectivity**, and explains its importance in maintaining service continuity and fault discrimination in electrical networks.

Chapter 3 reviews the **main selectivity principles** used in AC systems—such as time-based, current-based, energy-based, logic, directional, and differential selectivity—and assesses their applicability to LVDC environments.

Chapter 4 addresses the **specific challenges associated with LVDC systems**, focusing on the behavior of power converters during fault conditions and the presence of bidirectional fault currents. In addition, it highlights various phenomena that could affect service continuity and protection selectivity.

Chapter 5 presents and **compares protection strategies for systems** with non-limiting and current-limiting converters, evaluating the performance of various technologies (fuses, EMCBS, SCHCBs, SCCBs) and introducing advanced solutions based on directional protection and innovative solutions.

This document does not cover how to protect LVDC power systems (see SHIFT to DIRECT CURRENT, Deliverable D2.2.B, Protection Plan Methodology [1]) nor the coordination of protection with other equipment (which is typically performed to ensure equipment, that may not have the required performance characteristics, is protected and fit for purpose).

2 What is selectivity?

Selectivity is part of co-ordination measures between electrical equipment in an installation. According to the International Electrotechnical Vocabulary (IEV) 448-11-06 definition, the selectivity of protection is its ability to identify the faulty section and/or phase(s) of a power system. The International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) 60947-2 is more precise when defining overcurrent selectivity by co-ordination of the operating characteristics of two or more over-current protective devices such that, on the incidence of over-currents within stated limits, the device intended to operate within these limits does so, while the other(s) does (do) not.

In other words, selectivity is achieved by protective devices if a fault, occurring at any point in the installation, is cleared by the protective device located immediately upstream of the fault, while all other protective devices remain unaffected, whether they are upstream the tripping protection (which is sometimes named “vertical selectivity”) or on parallel feeders (which is sometimes named “horizontal selectivity”), as shown on Figure 2.1.

Note: Figure 2.1 is illustrating selectivity in a radial context where the term “upstream” is self-explanatory. In a multisource context, the term “upstream” corresponds to “between each source supplying the fault and the fault”.

Figure 2.1: Selectivity principle

Selectivity is checked for each kind of current fault (overload, short-circuit and earth fault). Even if selectivity mostly deals with widespread Overcurrent Protection Devices (OCPD), it may also concern other types of protection, like under-voltage. When the installation can be supplied by different sources, selectivity must be assessed for all operating modes, as sources do generally not deliver the same short circuit currents.

Selectivity is essential to ensure continuity of supply on non-faulty parts of the installation. However, unlike protection that is mandatory for safety reasons, selectivity is only required in standards for installation supplying critical loads that must not be interrupted in case of fault on another circuit (like safety services covered by IEC 60364-5-56). Selectivity may also be required by some local regulation or for some special applications like hospitals etc. It is highly recommended where continuity of supply is critical due to the nature of the loads, like in data centres. Anyway, selectivity is generally strived to be achieved as it also allows fast fault localization by isolating only the faulty part of the installation. But selectivity is not always reachable in electrical installations, due to some of their characteristics, like architecture, short circuit currents, operating modes etc.

For a maximum prospective short-circuit current I_{sc_max} at the installation point of the downstream protection (D2 on Figure 2.2), different degrees of selectivity between two OCPDs in series are distinguished in IEC 60364-5-53 according to the selectivity limit current I_s

- **Partial selectivity** (Figure 2.2): $I_s < I_{sc_max}$
- **Full selectivity:** $I_{sc_max} \leq I_s < \text{breaking capacity of downstream protection device}$
- **Total selectivity:** $I_{sc_max} \leq I_s = \text{breaking capacity of downstream protection device}$

and even (only with manufacturer instructions):

- **Enhanced selectivity** (thanks to combined short circuit protection):
 $\text{breaking capacity of downstream device} < I_{sc_max} \leq I_s \leq I_{comb}$

Where I_{comb} represents the combined breaking capacity - for a short circuit downstream D2 - of the association D1+D2 in series. This combined breaking capacity exceeds that of the downstream device and may be as high as the breaking capacity of the upstream one.

Figure 2.2: Partial Selectivity

The selectivity limit current, I_s , defined in IEC 60947-1:2020 as the “current coordinate of the intersection between the total time-current characteristic of the protective device on the load side and the pre-arcing (for fuses) or tripping (for circuit-breakers) time-current characteristic of the other protective device, correspond to the current above which the protective device on the load side D2 cannot complete its breaking operation in time to prevent D1 from tripping. It is mainly determined thanks to the instructions of the manufacturer of the downstream and upstream OCPDs, as calculation may be complex (Annex A in IEC 60947-2 is giving a method). This implies that this limit may be difficult to guarantee between devices from different manufacturers.

It should be underlined that these definitions are based on a radial network where the same current flows from an upstream source through devices D1 and D2. If additional sources were connected between D1 and D2, they would contribute to the short-circuit and “help” D2 to trip, thereby improving selectivity.

3 How selectivity is achieved in AC

This section explains how selectivity is realised in AC systems. It introduces the main principles including time-based, current-based, energy-based, logic, directional, and differential selectivity. It also describes how these principles apply depending on the type of fault and the protective devices used.

3.1 Usual selectivity principles

Several selectivity principles can be distinguished in AC networks, some of them being more common in medium voltage (MV), but still of interest when considering new network structures like microgrids. The following principles vary in relevance and applicability for overload, short-circuit and earth-fault protection, which is underlined in a table at the beginning of each Chapter.

The selection of selectivity principles is part of the protection system, as it has a direct impact on the selection of protective devices, but final selectivity is ensured with appropriate setting of protective devices. These principles are often combined to optimize selectivity in a network.

Given that these principles are well established in the state of the art, this Chapter provides a concise overview. For more in-depth technical details, the reader can refer to the Electrical Installation Wiki¹.

3.1.1 Time-based and current-based selectivity

Time-based and current-based selectivity, or a combination of both, are very common selectivity techniques for overload and (low-level) short-circuit currents, as well as for earth fault detection, as summarized in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Applicability of time-based and current-based selectivity

Type of fault:	Overload	Short circuit	Earth fault
Application	x	x	x

Time-based selectivity consists of assigning different time delays to the overcurrent protection elements. Considering a typical radial network, downstream protection would have the shortest operating times, while the time delays on upstream protection would increase progressively towards the source. In Figure 3.1, the time delay, Δt , is applied between protection devices A (upstream) and B (downstream), so that protection A takes a longer time to operate, allowing protection B to operate and clear the fault. The maximum operating time of protection B, including the breaking time, should be less than the minimum detection time of protection A (including all tolerances) to guarantee selectivity.

¹ *Coordination between circuit-breakers*, Schneider Electric – Electrical Installation Wiki. Available at: https://www.electrical-installation.org/enwiki/Coordination_between_circuit-breakers (accessed: 17 July 2025).

Figure 3.1: Time-based selectivity principle

In multi-level systems, time-based selectivity implies longer tripping time at the origin of the installation.

Current-based selectivity is mainly used for short-circuit faults and consists of assigning different pick-up thresholds to the overcurrent protection elements. As it is mainly for short-circuit faults, it relies on the fact that the current magnitude varies with the position of the short-circuit due to the network impedance. Because of this, it often leads to partial selectivity limited by the pick-up of the upstream protection. Considering a typical radial network, downstream protection would have the lowest pick-up thresholds, while the thresholds on upstream protection would increase progressively towards the source. In Figure 3.2, the pick-up threshold, I_r , is different between protections A and B (with the same characteristic), so that protection A does not detect the short-circuit downstream of protection B due to the low current magnitude. Selectivity is ensured if the maximum pick-up threshold of protection B is less than the minimum threshold of protection A (including all tolerances), providing the short-circuit current does not exceed protection A's threshold.

Figure 3.2 : Current-based selectivity principle

Often, a combination of both time-based and current-based selectivity principles are applied, especially due to the flexibility of modern protection units. For example, a time-delay can be added to a current-based scheme to improve overall selectivity. This is shown in Figure 3.3, where protection A takes longer to operate for a short-circuit current, $I_{sc B}$, caused by a fault downstream of protection B.

Figure 3.3: Time and current-based selectivity principle

3.1.2 Energy-based selectivity

Energy-based selectivity is a technique used for high-level short-circuit currents when current-limiting protective device operating times are very fast (typically less than 20 ms). Its applicability to different fault types is summarized in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2: Applicability of energy-based selectivity

Type of fault:	Overload	Short circuit	Earth fault
Application		x	x(*)

(*) When earth fault currents are very high, like in TN system earthing.

As shown on Figure 3.4, the very high-level short-circuit current is detected by both protective devices A and B in series (fuses or electromechanical circuit-breakers): the high energy induces the operation of downstream protective device B, but is not sufficient to induce the operation of A.

Figure 3.4: Energy selectivity domain for a circuit breaker

The trip/operating criterion usually involves the Joule integral (I^2t) rather than just the value of the current or time, and it becomes necessary to consider the characteristics of devices as well as their dynamic behaviour as an association. Especially because the impedance of the devices is not always negligible. For this reason, the let-through energy (I^2t) is provided by device manufacturers (see Figure 3.5).

(a)

Item number	Rated voltage AC (IEC)	Rated voltage AC (UL)	Rated current I_n	Pre-arcing I^2t	Clearing I^2t at Rated Voltage	Rated breaking capacity AC	Power dissipation at I_n	UL certified	Package	Weight
S300373	690 V	700 V	50 A	0.116 kA ² s	0.68 kA ² s	200 kA	9 W	✓	3	0.25 kg
M300000	690 V	700 V	63 A	0.2 kA ² s	1.2 kA ² s	200 kA	14 W	✓	3	0.25 kg
S300051	690 V	700 V	80 A	0.33 kA ² s	1.9 kA ² s	200 kA	19 W	✓	3	0.25 kg
T300052	690 V	700 V	100 A	0.47 kA ² s	2.7 kA ² s	200 kA	26 W	✓	3	0.25 kg
V300053	690 V	700 V	125 A	0.85 kA ² s	4.9 kA ² s	200 kA	30 W	✓	3	0.25 kg
W300054	690 V	700 V	160 A	1.6 kA ² s	9.2 kA ² s	200 kA	37 W	✓	3	0.25 kg
X300055	690 V	700 V	200 A	3 kA ² s	16.7 kA ² s	200 kA	42 W	✓	3	0.25 kg
Y300056	690 V	700 V	250 A	5.8 kA ² s	32.4 kA ² s	200 kA	48 W	✓	3	0.25 kg
Z300057	690 V	700 V	315 A	12 kA ² s	67 kA ² s	200 kA	53 W	✓	3	0.25 kg

(b)

Figure 3.5: Typical let-through energy data given by (a) fuse manufacturers and (b) circuit-breaker manufacturers

For current-limiting fuses (according to IEC 60269), short-circuit selectivity verification comprises of a comparison between pre-arcing and operating (also known as clearing) I^2t values for operating times < 0.1 s. Taking two fuses in series, the upstream device's minimum pre-arcing I^2t value shall be higher than the downstream devices maximum operating I^2t value, to achieve selectivity.

For current-limiting electromechanical circuit-breakers, short-circuit selectivity verification involves an assessment of the energy dissipated between devices during a short-circuit event. Taking a simple radial network with two circuit-breakers in series, the energy that the downstream circuit-breaker lets through must be less than that required to trip the upstream circuit-breaker, to achieve total selectivity. If the curves cross, this determines the selectivity limit current, I_s , as shown on Figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6: Example of comparison between circuit breakers energy curves to check selectivity

This assessment is a more complex task when compared to fuses, as the let-through energy can be a combination of several aspects, including the circuit-breaker characterisation, trip unit sensitivity and response time, and any specific energy-dependent system designed and implemented within the circuit-breaker. Due to the speed of operation, the common time-current curves are of no use under high short-circuit currents, so manufacturers typically provide selectivity tables to confirm if a certain combination of devices achieve selectivity or not and provide the selectivity limit current if any.

This assessment method can also be applied when an electromechanical circuit-breaker and fuse are in series. Assuming a radial network with the fuse upstream, selectivity can be determined (by desk study) from the I^2t characteristics. Selectivity is deemed to be achieved if the let-through energy (I^2t) of the circuit-breaker is lower than the pre-arcing I^2t value of the fuse.

It should be noted that because energy-based selectivity generally involves current-limiting protective devices, the peak let-through current is another factor to consider in some cases, for example, considering the peak current value corresponding to instantaneous trip thresholds or that required for contact repulsion, but it is not the focus of this section.

3.1.3 Logic selectivity (Zone Selective Interlocking)

One example of this type of selectivity is Zone Selective Interlocking (ZSI), as described in standards IEC/TR 61912-2 and IEEE C37.234-2021 (referred to as Blocking Zone-Interlocked Schemes). It can be implemented using circuit breakers equipped with specially designed electronic trip units. The applicability of logic selectivity to various fault types is summarized in Table 3.3.

Table 3.3: Applicability of logic-based selectivity

Type of fault:	Overload	Short circuit	Earth fault
Application	(**)	x	x (*)

(*) When earth fault currents are very high, like in TN system earthing.

(**) In current offer, Logic selectivity is not widely used for overload protection. Nevertheless, it could be relevant in LVDC with low short-circuit currents magnitude (limited by power converters).

The logic selectivity function is activated through the transmission of information via a pilot wire that cascades between the protection devices in an installation. When a fault occurs, each circuit breaker that detects it sends an interlocking signal, causing the receiving circuit breaker to apply its preset time delay. The circuit breaker located immediately upstream of the fault does not receive any interlocking signal and therefore trips almost instantaneously. If it fails to trip, the next upstream circuit breaker will operate after its configured short-time delay has elapsed (see Figure 3.7).

The main benefits of this solution are as follows:

- **It maintains short tripping times in multi-level systems**—even when using category B circuit breakers (see Section 3.3 for the definition)—which helps limit the stress on the installation and avoids unacceptably long delays. For this reason, it is widely used for bus protection.
- **It enables selectivity between circuit breakers with similar ratings.**
- **It does not require the application of current threshold rules between the cascaded breakers.**

Figure 3.7: Logic selectivity

A detailed example is given in IEC TR 61912-2.

3.1.4 Directional selectivity

Basic overcurrent protection (ANSI 50/51), detects current flowing in both directions. In networks supplied by multiple sources in parallel, or with parallel feeders (meshed structures), this detection method does not allow for discrimination of the faulty source in comer. In contrast, directional overcurrent protection (ANSI 67) can distinguish between the directions of current flow. Its applicability to different fault types is summarized in Table 3.4.

Table 3.4: Applicability of directional selectivity

Type of fault:	Overload	Short circuit	Earth fault
Application	x	x	x(*)

(*) When earth fault currents are very high, like in TN system earthing.

The directional selectivity principle relies on:

- a protection able to detect the current direction (with one current setting for each direction);
- an action depending on the detected direction (tripping for one direction only, with a specific time-delay for each direction).

Figure 3.8 gives a first example of implementation for two sources operating in parallel, where the directional protection trips only when the fault is located on the source side. The directional selectivity is generally combined with time-based selectivity to allow selectivity between ANSI 67 and 51 protections installed on source incomers to be ensured: the directional protection operates faster, while the ANSI 51 protection—which detects current in both directions—must be time-delayed.

Directional protection is becoming increasingly useful with the emergence of microgrids featuring several energy sources and power electronics converters operating in parallel. These converters often limit the fault current to values barely greater than the rated current observed in normal operation (typically by a factor of 1.2). In such networks, the direction of the current flow is often complementary to the magnitude of the current.

Figure 3.8: Directional selectivity applied to sources in parallel

Figure 3.9 shows an example of implementation of the directional selectivity principle to feeders supplying loads in parallel. Such meshed systems are becoming increasingly relevant in microgrids, especially in LVDC applications. Both directional overcurrent protective devices trip only if the current flows opposite to the normal flow of current. They are also set to be selective with respect to the non-directional protective devices.

Figure 3.9: Directional selectivity applied to parallel feeders

If a fault occurs in feeder A, the current follows two paths.

- If all breakers were non-directional, breakers A2 and B2 would both trip, interrupting the supply of the load, and then A1 would trip to isolate the fault.
- If A2 and B2 are directional overcurrent devices, B2 does not trip because the current flows in the normal direction, but A2 trips because the current flows in the abnormal direction. Breaker A1 will also trip just after to suppress the fault in feeder A completely. However, feeder B is not interrupted and continues to supply the load, maintaining some continuity of service

3.1.5 Differential selectivity

Differential protection operates by detecting and clearing faults within a defined zone, based on the difference between the input and output currents. A significant discrepancy between these currents indicates the presence of a fault inside the zone. As a result, differential protection is inherently sensitive to in-zone faults and insensitive to out-of-zone faults—provided it is correctly designed and implemented. This inherent discrimination makes it naturally selective. The applicability of differential selectivity to various fault types is summarized in Table 3.5.

Table 3.5: Applicability of differential-based selectivity

Type of fault:	Overload	Short circuit	Earth fault
Application		x	x

This selectivity principle implies a physical link between input and output detection devices. It is largely applied in Medium Voltage and High Voltage (HV) networks (ANSI 87 and 64REF) for different kinds of zones: busbars, transformers, machines, lines. It is highly valued for its ability to clear faults very quickly within each protected zone, without requiring coordination with adjacent zones. However, it is generally complex and costly to implement because:

- multiple current sensors at the input and output may be required;
- the fault detection must be sufficiently sensitive to detect real faults without causing unwanted tripping, which can be challenging due to sensor saturation.

This selectivity principle implies a physical link between input and output detection devices. This principle is occasionally used in low voltage (LV) AC systems through the use of MV relays, for example, for earth fault protection (ANSI 64REF). Its relevance may increase with the development of digitalized sensing technologies, for example for the protection of Direct Current (DC) bus Jprotection.

Figure 3.10 illustrates what could be differential selectivity applied to a Low Voltage Alternating Current (LVAC) microgrid.

Figure 3.10: Differential selectivity applied to a LV AC microgrid

3.2 Phase to phase and earth fault protection selectivity

In a protection system designed for a network that includes both phase-to-phase overcurrent protection and earth fault protection, selectivity must be assessed for both types of faults. However, three key differences apply:

- as shown in Section 3.1, phase-to-phase fault protection involves a wider range of selectivity principles;
- protection and selectivity for phase-to-phase faults do not depend on the system earthing;
- selectivity for earth fault protection has to be assessed for each galvanically isolated zone.

Except for differential selectivity principle dedicated to a zone, the sources of faults have to be clearly identified to understand how selectivity can be ensured, and how protections should be properly set:

- **For phase-to-phase faults**, sources are easy to identify, but even with several selectivity principles implemented, it may be sometimes impossible to meet selectivity for all operating modes, which requires the prioritization of needs. An example of OCPD serialization is shown on Figure 3.11: only the OCPD marked in red must trip, even though upstream sources OCPDs may also detect the overcurrent.

Figure 3.11: Example of Phase-to-phase selectivity in a LV AC microgrid

- For earth faults**, in each galvanically separated zone, the “upstream source” is unique and must be visualized at the System Referencing Conductor (SRC), preferably located at the common point between sources. Only earth fault protective devices located between the SRC and the earth fault can detect the fault. For example, earth fault protective devices located at the source incomers cannot detect earth faults occurring on downstream feeders. Once this mindset is adopted, achieving selectivity is generally simpler. However, any displacement of the SRC (in certain operating modes) introduces complexity, as directional detection may become necessary.

Moreover, selectivity for phase-to-phase overcurrent faults and earth fault currents is sometimes mixed. Indeed, when TN earthing system is implemented or IT earthing system without tripping at the first earth fault, the same protective device (OCPD) often provides protection against both type of faults, as the earth fault current is generally high enough to cause it to trip.

The following example demonstrates that selectivity may sometimes need to be assessed between two different types of protective devices, such as an OCPD and a Residual Current Device (RCD). An example of earth fault protection coordination is shown in Figure 3.12 (assuming no SRC displacement): all protective devices capable of detecting earth faults must be taken into account.

Figure 3.12: Example of earth fault selectivity in a LV AC microgrid

The overcurrent detection located on the SRC is, in this case, the only device able to detect an earth fault occurring on the main distribution switchboard. In that case, it does not open the SRC itself but instead triggers the tripping of all source incomers. This constitutes the final level of protection - the ultimate back up protection - which is why downstream protective devices are expected to trip before it.

3.3 Application to current LVAC protective devices

The use of the above selectivity principles, which vary in complexity to implement, depends on the type of protective device. For example, the IEC 60947-2, which applies to circuit-breakers intended to be installed and operated by skilled persons, defines selectivity categories to distinguish devices specifically intended for selectivity by means of an intentional time delay:

- Category B** (time-based selectivity)
 These circuit breakers have high thermal and electrodynamic withstands, which allow them to be intentionally time-delayed.
- Category A**
 This category includes all other circuit breakers. Some of them cannot be time-delayed, or on a limited range of current and time. These circuit breakers have current-limiting characteristics: they limit drastically the let-through energy and prospective peak current value.

Table 3.6 shows what selectivity principles are generally available in current LV protective devices. When the differential principle is used, it may be implemented with MV relays.

Table 3.6: Selectivity principles according to LV protective devices

	Overcurrent Protective Device (OCPD)					Earth fault protective device/module	
	Fuse	Circuit breaker			RCD ($\leq 30A$)	Other	
		Category A		Category B			
		MCB	MCCB Some ACB	MCCB	ACB		
Product Standard:	IEC 60269	IEC 60898-1 IEC 60947-1 & 2	IEC 60947-1 & 2	IEC 60947-1 & 2			
Selectivity principle							
Time-based			(x)	x	x	x	x
Current-based	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Energy-based	x	x	x	x			
Logic (ZSI)			(x)	x	x		x
Directional					x		
Differential							

4 Challenges in LVDC constraints

This Chapter addresses the specificities of LVDC systems that pose significant challenges to achieving protection selectivity. These challenges primarily stem from the dynamic behaviour of the power converters which are most often interfacing all sources and loads in LVDC networks. Their response under short-circuits conditions and during voltage sags directly influences the performance of protection selectivity.

The following aspects, discussed in this Chapter, must be carefully considered when selecting and setting protection devices, as they significantly impact both selectivity and service continuity:

- Power converters short-circuit behaviour & embedded overcurrent protection
- Power converters Under voltage Ride Through capability
- Bidirectional fault current flow
- Current oscillations during and post fault clearance
- Sympathetic overcurrent tripping from overvoltage

4.1 Power converters short-circuit behaviour & embedded overcurrent protection

While power converters have been used extensively in industrial applications, their application in powering DC distribution networks is a recent development. As the standard framework for LVDC systems is still under development, there is a variety of converter technologies and control methods that can be adopted. From the perspective of system protection design, power converters can be classified into two main categories based on their behaviour during DC faults: non-limiting and limiting converters.

Non-limiting converters operate in boost mode where the source-side voltage is lower than the DC network voltage. A classification of non-limiting converters is given in *D2.2.C, Short-Circuit Current Calculation Methodology* [2].

By design, these converters include diodes or freewheeling diodes in parallel with active components such as Insulated-Gate Bipolar Transistors (IGBTs) or Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor Field-Effect Transistors (MOSFETs), which provide a direct path between the input and output of the converter during DC faults. Their behaviour in the event of a fault in DC network is typically characterized by a large DC capacitor discharge, followed by a “prospective” current drawn from the source to the fault location, also called AC or DC infeed depending on the nature of the source. The converter's internal regulator cannot prevent or limit the source-infeed current. For AC/DC interlink converter, the magnitude of AC infeed “prospective” current is limited by the short-circuit power of the upstream system (e.g. power grid, transformer and cables), typically reaching several times the converter's nominal current, as illustrated in Figure 4.1 on the left. For battery DC/DC converter, the DC infeed is only limited by the internal impedance of the battery and the impedance present in the fault path. In LV power converters, these diodes are often not designed to handle “prospective” AC or DC infeed currents.

LV fault-feeding converters are equipped with internal overcurrent protection to mitigate the fire risk. Usually, high-speed fuse or electronic-based overcurrent protection are used. In case of fault on the

DC side, this internal protection quickly disconnects the converter which could be an issue regarding selectivity with the DC grid protections and service continuity.

Indeed, selectivity with this ultra-rapid protection is a challenge with conventional protection device as the fuse could blow during the converter output capacitor discharge. In addition, high-speed fuses are not always able to fully protect the converter components from deterioration and the fuse replacement may call for heavy maintenance on the converter.

Limiting converters employ a buck stage at source side where voltage is higher than output stage voltage. A classification of limiting converters is given in *D2.2.C, Short-Circuit Current Calculation Methodology* [2]. They have inherent DC current limiting feature provided by their internal controls. When a DC fault occurs, following the capacitor discharge, the converter control enters in current-limiting mode, as illustrated in Figure 4.1 on the right. The output current is limited to a specified reference value, typically to a maximum of 1.2 to 1.5 times the nominal current of LV converter.

On theoretical basis, fault-limiting converters can remain connected during current-limiting mode over a period of time, regardless of the DC voltage drop level. In practice, to reduce overheating stress on electronic devices, converters may curtail their output current in relation to the output voltage and also embed under-voltage protection to disconnect them in case of severe faults. The current-limiting withstand duration defines therefore the Fault-Ride Through (FRT) capability of the source converters. The FRT capability of converters should provide more time for external protections to isolate faults, thereby enabling better selectivity performance.

Figure 4.1: Comparison of the fault prospective currents provided by 120 kW @ 700 VDC (a) non-limiting and (b) limiting interlink converters

Conclusion

In all cases, it is necessary to be aware of the overcurrent and undervoltage protections of the source converters, as they must be considered in the selectivity study. Depending on the converter technology, the requirements for external protection speed vary.

- Converters that do not limit the short-circuit current require the use of static protection devices in the network to isolate faults before the converter self-protection operate.
- Current-limiting converters, depending on their FRT capability, may allow for the use of slower protection devices in the network.

4.2 Undervoltage Ride Through capability of converters

LVDC load converters are based on DC/DC or DC/AC converters acting as the power module, also known as power supply unit or switching regulator unit, converting DC network voltage to the voltages required by subsequent loads. They are mainly operated in buck-configuration. Undervoltage conditions in an LVDC grid due to a short-circuit fault can risk the continuity of supply due "sympathetic" shutdown.

The FRT capability of a load converter is defined as its ability to stay connected during input voltage dips, and to recover to normal operation once the DC network voltage is restored. Unlike the use of the FRT-concept in MV or HV applications, the FRT capability of LV load converter is certainly not intended for providing grid support but rather to ensure its robust operation. This comes from the fact that the converter needs to be supplied by a certain minimum voltage to operate correctly, avoiding incorrect control signals or partial-on/off states in power switching components.

The FRT capability of a power module can be defined based on two features:

- Embedded **Undervoltage Lockout (UVLO)** function: will automatically shut down the converter when the input voltage drops below a defined threshold.
- Converter's **input (bulk) capacitor**: plays critical roles in converter operation by 1) smoothing voltage ripple caused by transients in DC network, 2) providing voltage buffering to stabilize the voltage during abrupt load variations or input voltage drop (See Figure 4.2). The size of the input capacitor - or more specifically, the amount of energy stored in it – defines how long and under which conditions the converter can maintain operation under fault or disturbance conditions. A small input capacitor increases the converter's vulnerability to even minor input voltage deviations, resulting to disconnection. Conversely, a larger capacitor extends the converter FRT capability but comes at the cost of high capacitor discharge during a fault and high recharge current at post-fault recovery. To avoid adverse effects from the capacitor discharge to the fault, some unidirectional or load converters are equipped with an anti-return diode.

Figure 4.2: Simplified scheme of a power supply unit

As LVDC standards are still evolving and do not yet mandate the FRT capability, load converter manufacturers may choose whether to include it or simply hard-protect their devices.

Considering the FRT capability of load converter is therefore essential in setting up protection schemes. A very tight FRT profile demands extremely fast fault current interruption to prevent the discharge of the load converter's input capacitor, causing unexpected load disconnection. If protections with slower response time are used, specific requirements on the load's FRT profile should be defined to ensure efficient coordination and continuity of service.

Indeed, when a short-circuit occurs, the system voltage is drastically impacted, resulting in a severe drop in voltage, particularly near to the short-circuit. As LVDC power systems are capacitive in nature, the voltage decrease can be rapid as the capacitors discharge into the fault. The rate and magnitude of the voltage decrease depends on several factors, including the capacitor characteristics, network impedance, (electrical) distance from the short-circuit location, and how fast the short-circuit is cleared from the system.

Illustration example of a short-circuit scenario, showing the impact on DC voltages

Figure 4.3 presents an illustrative example in which a short-circuit occurs at Load 1. The voltages at the main source and at the unaffected loads, as well as the short-circuit current, are shown. The fault is cleared by an MCCB-type circuit breaker in approximately 1.4 ms.

Figure 4.3: Illustration of source and load initial voltage drop due to a short-circuit event

In this example, the voltages at the load-side converters drop very quickly and to very low levels due to their smaller capacitors and their lower impedance to the fault location. In contrast, the main source converter experiences a slower and less pronounced voltage drop.

However, the undervoltage protection integrated into converters may detect a voltage dip—depending on its threshold settings and response time—and trigger a “sympathetic” shutdown, even if the converter is not directly affected by the fault. In such cases, a single short-circuit can activate multiple voltage-related protections across different converters, potentially disrupting service continuity.

Note: Sympathetic tripping refers to the unintended disconnection of a healthy section of the system due to a fault occurring in another parallel section.

4.3 Bidirectional fault current flow

LVDC systems, in the scope of Shift2DC project, are natively multisource. As state of art, AC or DC multisource applications require specific directional protections to ensure selectivity. In addition, in LVDC systems, fault current can flow bidirectionally through incomer and load feeder protections, either towards source-side or load-side as illustrated in Figure 4.4 and Figure 4.5.

- Where several sources supply the system, it is essential to differentiate between faults located in the DC network (e.g., F1 in Figure 4.4) and those on the source side (e.g., F3 in Figure 4.4). In the first case, all incomer protections (e.g., OCPD1, OCPD2 and OCPD3) shall trip, whereas in the second case, only the protection of the faulty incomer (e.g., OCPD2) shall trip. This selective tripping prevents the disconnection of all sources and avoids a potential total blackout.

Figure 4.4: Fault detected by incomers' protection: load-side fault vs. source-side fault

- Most sources and loads in a LVDC system are connected via their power converter, either with AC/DC, DC/DC, or DC/AC converters.

When a fault occurs in the DC network (e.g., F2 in Figure 4.5), the DC output capacitors of the source converters and the DC input capacitors of the load converters discharge into the fault during the initial transient. The protection device on the faulty feeder (e.g., OCPD4) detects current flowing toward the load side, while protections on healthy feeders (e.g., OCPD5, OCPD6, OCPD7) detect current flowing in the opposite direction, toward the source.

Without **directional** overcurrent detection, this can lead to the tripping of healthy feeders, depending on the protection settings and response times. Another way to prevent the contribution of load-side capacitors to the fault consist in installing anti-return diodes within the converter or as part of the feeder protection.

Figure 4.5: Fault detected by load feeders' protection: risk of spurious tripping

In summary, bidirectional fault current flow presents challenges, not only due to sources and loads contributing to short-circuits, but because protective device ratings (associated with the contributing sources) can be of a wide or narrow range, making it very difficult or impossible in some cases to optimise settings of non-directional protection to achieve selectivity. Directional protection with advanced algorithms can help overcome selectivity issues in such systems.

It should be acknowledged that sympathetic tripping may occur, even if the protection is originally coordinated to deal with current direction. This can occur during the short-circuit and after the short-circuit has been cleared, as oscillations in the current may appear as the system naturally responds to the fault application and clearance. This is illustrated in Figure 4.6, based on simulation results, where there is a short-circuit located at Load 1 with an associated overcurrent protective device named OCPD 1. During the short-circuit, all parallel capacitors (which are inside the converters) respond to the short-circuit and supply current, as (and if) they are exposed to the main DC system.

Figure 4.6: Illustration of loads contributing to a short-circuit, causing significant current (oscillating in both directions) to flow through protective devices on healthy circuits

In this case, the current that flows through parallel load overcurrent protective devices (i.e. OCPD 2 to OCPD 4) during the short-circuit could be of sufficient magnitude and duration to make them operate, noting that the current direction changes before the short-circuit is interrupted.

4.4 Current oscillations during & post fault clearance

In LVDC power systems there is a dominant presence of power converters. Most converters, even those used for loads, include capacitors that are exposed to the main DC system. The main purpose of these capacitors is for stability (and fault ride through) and to meet voltage ripple targets.

Under short-circuit conditions, these capacitors will discharge (if their contribution is not blocked with diodes, for example) into the short-circuit and deliver current. This is illustrated in Figure 4.6, based on simulation results, where there is a short-circuit located at Load 1 with an associated overcurrent protective device named OCPD 1. During the short-circuit, all parallel capacitors (which are inside the converters) respond to the short-circuit and supply current, as they are exposed to the main DC system.

In this case, the current that flows through parallel load overcurrent protective devices (i.e. OCPD 2 to OCPD 4) during the short-circuit could be of sufficient magnitude and duration to make them operate. Moreover, it should be recognised that even once OCPD 1 interrupts the current (before 2ms in Figure 4.6), there are oscillations in the current, still of significant magnitude, flowing through the devices.

Therefore, this can result in widespread disruption, where overcurrent protective devices on healthy circuits “sympathetically” trip due to a short-circuit on an adjacent circuit, because of the current contribution before the short-circuit is cleared and/or due to the current oscillations after the short-circuit is cleared.

To mitigate the current oscillations during tripping and post fault clearance several solutions can be put in place:

- Stopping the loads contributing to fault (e.g. blocking diodes)
- Using ultra-rapid protection to clear the fault and minimising current oscillation amplitude
- Using ultra-rapid protection with decoupling capacitors to further minimize the impact of the fault on the network, refer to the Section 5.1.4.4 and the surge-free Semiconductor Circuit-Breaker (SCCB) topology.

In any case, a robust protection system, based on directional or differential principle shall be implemented to avoid spurious trips.

4.5 Sympathetic overcurrent tripping from overvoltage

When protective devices interrupt current, overvoltages are created due to the system inductance. The level of overvoltage depends on the nature of the system and the current being interrupted, and the type of device breaking the current.

Equipment, including power converters, may have components which are sensitive to such overvoltages. Therefore, overvoltage protection is commonly embedded in equipment to protect power electronic components; these components may be used in the capacitor pre-charge circuit, for example, as shown in Figure 4.7 (a). One issue regarding the overvoltage generated during breaking operations, is that this can trigger equipment overvoltage protection to operate.

This is illustrated in Figure 4.7 (b), where an overvoltage is generated by feeder A overcurrent protection opening and interrupting the current (mainly due to $L\frac{di}{dt}$), which causes the overvoltage protection of equipment B to operate [3].

Figure 4.7: Opening of feeder A overcurrent protection causing (a) equipment B overvoltage or (b) current flow due to equipment B overvoltage protection operation

This triggering of overvoltage protection on adjacent circuits (with reference to the faulted circuit) will cause current to flow as the overvoltage protection transitions from a high to low resistance state to limit the voltage (and ultimately protect the equipment).

This current flowing due to the triggered overvoltage protection may cause the associated overcurrent protective devices to “sympathetically” operate, especially if they are sensitive and fast acting, such as a semiconductor circuit-breaker.

A similar situation can occur when equipment has input capacitors (assuming overvoltage protection is not provided), as the stored energy in the system inductance when current is interrupted can be absorbed by capacitors, causing overcurrent to flow in the healthy feeder and possible “sympathetic tripping”.

5 How to manage selectivity in LVDC

Given the constraints outlined in the previous Chapter, achieving selectivity in LVDC systems remains a challenge. This Chapter presents potential solutions to ensure selectivity in LVDC networks.

The behaviour of converters is key in the study of selectivity. As presented in Chapter 4, some source and load converters integrate internal protection mechanisms that may rapidly disconnect the converter in the event of a fault. It is therefore necessary to select appropriate protection devices that can coordinate effectively with the converters.

In this Chapter, two distinct scenarios of pole-to-pole faults are analyzed. First, Section 5.1 focuses on converters equipped with ultra-fast self-protection mechanisms, which place stringent requirements on the response time of external protection systems. In a second part, Section 5.2 examines converters designed to remain connected to the grid during faults. These converters are capable of delivering short-circuit current (I_{sc}) for a defined duration, thereby supporting FRT and Under Voltage Ride-Through (UVRT) capabilities. In this case, the burden of fault management shifts from the external protection to the converter itself.

For each case, several protection schemes are analysed, based on fuses, EMCBs, SCCBs & SCHCBs technologies. The conventional selectivity approaches introduced in Chapter 3 are discussed, taking into account the additional constraints associated with converters and static protection technology. Moreover, new technological solutions are proposed to enhance the selectivity performance under these specific conditions.

To guarantee selectivity and service continuity, the following aspects are discussed:

- Selectivity between power supply converters and DC network protection devices
- Selectivity between in-series protection devices in the DC network
- Multisource and bidirectionality constraints

For each case, the example presented Figure 5.1 is analysed based on faults located at F1 (on the DC bus), F2 (on a feeder) and F3 (on a source in-comer).

Figure 5.1: simplified SLD and fault location

Finally, Section 5.3 explores how the principles of AC selectivity for earth faults can be adapted and applied to DC systems.

5.1 Managing selectivity in systems with Non-Limiting Converters

As mentioned in Section 4, in the event of a fault, some converters might disconnect themselves very quickly due to their internal self-protection mechanisms:

- Non-limiting power supply converters necessitating very rapid fault clearing to protect sensitive internal components (Section 4.1).
- Load converters with low energy storage capacity (Section 4.2).

Since both power supply and loads converters have low FRT capability, the protection devices installed in the network must operate extremely quickly to ensure selectivity and, in some cases, to better protect the converter components. This paragraph evaluates the selectivity performance of various protection schemes.

5.1.1 Fuse-based protection scheme

In this section, a protection scheme based on fuses is reviewed. It is supposed that fuses are used as OCPD at incomers and load feeders. For additional information about LVDC fuses technologies the reader can refer to Shift2DC, Deliverable D2.2.B, Protection Plan Methodology [1].

Faults F1, F2, and F3 as described in Figure 5.1 are briefly discussed hereafter:

Fault F1 on the DC bus: the power supply incomers protection (OCPD1 and OCPD2) should blow. If the converters internal protections are based on high-speed fuses, they might also blow, as they are likely rated similarly. As a result, selectivity between the source-side protection and the converter's internal protection is not guaranteed. In addition, the internal components of the converters could be damaged, requiring maintenance and fuse replacement.

Fault F2 on a feeder: Selectivity may be achievable depending on the rating of OCPD4.

- If OCPD4 rating is much lower than the source incomer protections OCPD1 and OCPD2, selectivity could be possible between feeder 4 and both converter internal protection and incomer protection. This can be studied based on energetic selectivity principle as described in Section 3.1.2.
- If the rating of the OCPD4 is close or similar to one of the sources protections (internal and external), selectivity cannot be achieved.

Fault F3 on source incomer: if the ratings of OCPD1 and OCPD2 are close, both fuses could blow simultaneously, along with the internal protections of the power supply converters. If OCPD1 has a lower rating, it will even blow first and disconnect the healthy source 1. When fuse-based protection is used on the incomers, selectivity between the sources cannot be guaranteed.

For information, Figure 5.2 present the melting curves of two fuses: 200 A incomer and a 63A feeder fuses, in the context of a 700 V LVDC building protection study. It illustrates that the maximum short-circuit current delivered by the output capacitors of the 120 kW AC/DC converter (shown in blue) is barely sufficient to blow the 200 A fuse. Furthermore, the minimum short-circuit current (shown in purple) is clearly insufficient to blow the incomer fuse. This example highlights a critical point: in fuse-based protection schemes, a detailed case-by-case protection study is essential to ensure reliable fault clearing and overall system protection in LVDC applications.

Figure 5.2: Melting curves of fuses against DC faults in LVDC building [4]

Conclusion

Except in the specific case of low rating feeder protection, selectivity cannot be ensured in LVDC system based on fuse protection scheme. The absence of directionality prevents selectivity from being guaranteed in multi-source configurations. A potential solution to improve protection and selectivity could be to add capacitance in the system as presented Section 5.1.4.4 “3- Centralized bus capacitor”.

5.1.2 EMCB-based protection scheme

In this Section, it is assumed that EMCB are used as OCPD at incomers and load feeders. Miniature Circuit Breakers (MCB) and Molded Case Circuit Breakers (MCCB) are two types in the EMCB family used for LV applications. MCBs with small ratings and breaking capacity are used for residential, commercial, and light industrial applications. MCCBs support higher current ratings and greater breaking capacities, making them suitable for large commercial building and industry installations.

Today’s LVDC MCBs and MCCBs are equipped with integrated electromechanical tripping-units (see SHIFT to DIRECT CURRENT, Deliverable D2.2.B, Protection Plan Methodology [1]). MCBs are typically non-adjustable, and while MCCBs may allow adjustment of parameters such as I_r and I_m , they do not support advanced electronic protection features like directional or logic-based protection. Moreover, technical data regarding the selectivity performance of MCBs and MCCBs in LVDC applications remains limited.

Faults F1, F2, and F3 as described in Figure 5.1 are briefly discussed hereafter:

Fault F1 on the DC bus: Under short-circuit conditions, EMCBs are slower than high-speed fuses, which means the fuses may blow before the circuit breakers can clear the fault. The converter’s fast internal protection is likely to blow first, disconnecting the converter rapidly. This can result in damage to internal components of the converter. Moreover, due to the slower response of the EMCBs, selectivity between the incomer protection and the converter’s internal protection is fundamentally not achievable in this configuration.

Fault F2 on a feeder: Selectivity may be achievable depending on the rating of OCPD4.

- If OCPD4 rating is much lower than OCPD1 and OCPD2, selectivity can be achieved between feeder 4 and both the converter's internal protection and the upstream incomer protection (see Section 3.1.2).
- However, if the rating of feeder 4 is close to or equal to that of either the internal or external source protections, selectivity cannot be ensured. In such cases, the converter's internal protection may activate before or simultaneously with OCPD4, potentially causing a system blackout.

However, if fault clearing time is too long or the voltage drop is too severe, load converters may disconnect.

Fault F3 on source incomer: Since EMCBs are slower than the internal protection of power supply converters, this configuration is functionally identical to the DC bus fault case (Fault F1), leading to the same outcome: selectivity is not achievable.

Conclusion

In the case of converters without FRT capability, selectivity cannot be ensured in LVDC systems using an EMCB-based protection scheme—except in specific cases involving low-rated feeder protection. While EMCBs may offer better protection performance than fuses due to adjustable current thresholds, selectivity remains uncertain and cannot be guaranteed. The absence of directionality also prevents selectivity from being guaranteed in multi-source configurations.

5.1.3 Semiconductor Hybrid Circuit-Breaker-based protection scheme

Technical information about SCHCB technology and performances can be found in Shift2DC, Deliverable D2.2.B, Protection Plan Methodology [1].

SCHCB interruption time (from fault detection to the peak current limitation) are typically in the range of hundreds of microseconds. This is comparable to, or in some cases slower than, the melting time of high-speed fuses. As a result, achieving selectivity between SCHCBs and high-speed fuses is challenging and cannot be always guaranteed.

Faults F1, F2, and F3 as described in Figure 5.1 are briefly discussed hereafter:

Fault F1 on the DC bus: It is difficult to ensure that the SCHCB will clear the fault before the converter's internal fuse melts under all fault conditions. Therefore, selectivity between the incomer protection and the converter's internal fuse cannot be guaranteed.

Fault F2 on a feeder: Selectivity may be achievable depending on the rating of OCPD4.

- If OCPD4 rating is much lower than OCPD1 and OCPD2, selectivity between feeder 4 and both the converter's internal protection and the incomer protection may be possible, based on the energy-based selectivity principle (see Section 3.1.2).
- However, if the rating of feeder 4 is close to that of the source protections (internal or external), selectivity cannot be achieved. In such cases, the converter's internal fuse may blow before or simultaneously with OCPD4 tripping, potentially resulting in a system blackout.

Fault F3 on the source incomer: When SCHCBs are slower than the internal protection of power supply converters, this configuration is functionally identical to the DC bus fault case (Fault F1), leading to the same outcome: selectivity is not achievable.

Conclusion

In short-circuit conditions, the breaking time of SCHCBs is significantly faster than that of EMCBs, but falls within the same time range or slower than high-speed fuses. As a result, achieving selectivity with internal fuses of power converters can be challenging and cannot be guaranteed. While faults on downstream low-rated feeders may still be cleared selectively, this performance must be evaluated based on the energy-based selectivity principle described in Section 3.1.2.

The behaviour of usual load converters during voltage drop remains insufficiently documented. Given the fast interruption time of SCHCB – ranging from hundreds of microseconds to 1 millisecond – standard loads may disconnect. However, in applications such as data centres, Power Distribution Units (PDUs) which are typically designed to tolerate voltage collapses lasting up to 10 milliseconds should remain connected.

5.1.4 SCCB-based protection scheme

SCCB uses power semiconductors such as MOSFET, IGBT or Silicon Carbide (SiC) transistors to interrupt current, offering fast response time in ranges of microseconds. Additional information about SCCB technology and performances can be found in SHIFT to DIRECT CURRENT, Deliverable D2.2.B, Protection Plan Methodology [1].

5.1.4.1 Prerequisite about SCCB protection against overcurrent in DC network

While standard validation tests related to the “Time-Current Curve” (TCC) of SCCB are still under development, a typical curve which could comply to the 121A/635/CDV of IEC 60947-10 (Section 9.3.4.2.2) is illustrated in Figure 5.3.

Selectivity in the overload range is generally straightforward to assess using TCC curves and manufacturer guidelines; therefore, **the focus here is placed on short-circuit protection**. Although SCCBs could incorporate advanced short-circuit protection algorithms—based on current and voltage measurements, di/dt , or impedance, often requiring manufacturer-specific recommendations—this Section **focuses on the simpler case of overcurrent protection for short circuits detection**. Because they are sensitive to high currents and must self-protect against thermal or electrodynamic deterioration, their maximum short-circuit protection threshold can be relatively low—typically limited to around 2 times the rated current ($2I_n$).

Figure 5.3: Typical tripping curve of SCCB

The SCCB response time, i.e., the total fault clearing time of SCCB, is composed of following stages, as illustrated in Figure 5.4:

Figure 5.4 Current Interruption and transient voltage of SCCB

- **The fault detection**, which depends on the signal processing and tripping decision strategy (e.g., based on current's amplitude, rate of rise or combined criteria).
- The turn-off **switching** time of semiconductor devices, that can take hundreds of nanoseconds to several microseconds, depending on the type of devices used.
- The suppression of transient voltages, which may extend to hundreds of microseconds or milliseconds, depending on various factors such as
- the application voltage, the inductive energy stored in the fault loop and the performance of the voltage clamping circuit.

Tripping speed of semiconductor circuit-breakers:

From a time-current perspective, semiconductor circuit-breakers can trip ultra-fast, in the order of one μs or tens of μs , even for current magnitudes as low as 2 times rated current. This allows time and current-based selectivity to be easily achieved when upstream protective devices are more conventional. With rapid response time, the SCCB at incomer could react faster than the converter's internal protection. The selectivity between them could be therefore ensured.

It should be noted that long time delays should be avoided, because long delays can allow the current to rise dramatically and the circuit-breaker components can be stressed due to thermal and electrodynamic constraints.

5.1.4.2 Fault scenarios

In this Section, it is supposed that SCCB are used as OCPD at incomers and load feeders. Faults F1, F2, and F3 as described in Figure 5.1 are briefly discussed hereafter:

Fault F1 on the DC bus: SCCBs interrupting time is much faster than high-speed fuses allowing selectivity with power supply internal fuses, as illustrated Figure 5.5 with 200 A protections.

Fault F2 on a feeder: selectivity between two in-series SCCBs is possible based in different principles presented in Section 3.1 such as Time-based and logic selectivity. Section 5.1.4.3 details this topic, considering the specificities of SCCBs fast tripping and overcurrent sensitivity. If the load feeders are not equipped with anti-return diodes, the healthy loads might contribute to the fault current, then directional selectivity shall be implemented, refer to the F3 case and Section 5.1.4.4.

Fault F3 on the source inverter: basic unidirectional protection would not be sufficient to guarantee selectivity in this situation. Advanced protection based on directional and logic principles and other innovative solutions are presented hereafter in Section 5.1.4.4.

Figure 5.5: Effective coordination between SCCB and converter's internal fuse in LVDC building [4]

Conclusion

Unlike fuses, EMCBs, and SCHCBs, SCCBs appear to be the only truly viable solution to ensure selectivity in LVDC networks using converters without FRT and Low Voltage Ride-Through (LVRT) capabilities. For this reason, particular emphasis is placed on SCCB technology, which is here explored in greater depth. The following Sections delve into two key aspects of this technology:

- Selectivity between two SCCBs connected in series
- How to manage bidirectional fault currents

5.1.4.3 Selectivity between two in series SCCBs

Selectivity shall be guaranteed over the full range of current, for both overload and short-circuit protections. This paragraph focuses on the case of the **short-circuit protection** where selectivity is more complex to prove because of the high short-circuit current derivative and the ultra-fast reaction time of the SCCB.

SCCBs are sensitive to high currents, this is why they typically include an ultrafast instantaneous current protection against short circuits.

This paragraph describes the method for ensuring selectivity between two SCCBs connected in series under short-circuit conditions, as illustrated in the simplified single-line diagram (SLD) in Figure 5.6. In this configuration, SCCB1 and SCCB2 are connected in series, with their respective instantaneous current thresholds denoted as I_{m1} and I_{m2} , where $I_{m1} > I_{m2}$.

Figure 5.6: Simplified single line diagram including two SCCBs in-series

To ensure selectivity in this configuration, SCCB2—the breaker closest to the fault—must detect and clear the fault before SCCB1 reacts. Since both SCCBs have fixed instantaneous short-circuit current thresholds, the peak fault current limited by SCCB2 must remain below I_{m1} , with an appropriate safety margin to prevent unintended tripping of SCCB1.

To guarantee that the current doesn't exceed the tripping threshold I_{m1} of SCCB1, it is necessary to consider the rate of change of current di/dt and the SCCB2 reaction time Δt as illustrated in Figure 5.7. Two scenarios are illustrated, each with a different fault location. As the fault loop inductance increases with cable length, the rate of current rise (di/dt) is significantly lower in the right-hand figure compared to the left-hand one.

Figure 5.7: SCCB2 short-circuit current clearing steps for 2 different cable lengths

The delay Δt represents the short-circuit protection response time, which includes the fault detection (sensing & processing) and the triggering time of the semiconductors. This delay is sometimes referred to as the “switching” or “breaking” time, which can be misleading, as it does not account for the current decay stage down to the complete fault clearance. More details can be found in [5].

At $t = t1$, the current exceeds the tripping threshold I_{m2} of SCCB2, at $t = t1 + \Delta t$, the SCCB2 switches off its semiconductors, the current has reached a peak and starts decreasing. Selectivity could be achieved or not depending on the short-circuit current derivative di/dt during Δt -and I_{m1} threshold.

In LVDC microgrids, as explained in [2], the short-circuit currents delivered by the converter output capacitors and Lithium-ion batteries present a very high rate of rise. To guarantee selectivity, the

maximum short-circuit current derivative shall be considered. At the beginning of the short-circuit, assuming that the source voltage is constant, it could be assessed as follows:

$$\left. \frac{di}{dt} \right|_{max} = \frac{V_{max}}{L_{min}} \quad (5.1)$$

Where V_{max} is the maximum permanent operating voltage of the system and L_{min} is the minimum inductance of short-circuit loop. The inductance embedded in the devices shall be considered as they can damp drastically the di/dt .

Conclusion

Selectivity could be achieved between series-mounted SCCBs provided that the ratio between upstream and downstream CB tripping threshold (I_{m1}/I_{m2}) is sufficient, in line with the downstream breaker reaction time and system di/dt .

This principle can be applied between source incomer protection and feeders' protection devices for instance between OCPD4 and OCPD1, 2 or 3 (Figure 4.5). In this multisource application, the short-circuit contribution of several sources into the OCPD4 might improve the selectivity as the current should rise faster in this OCPD4 which should trip first.

In the example mentioned therebefore, a sufficient margin is necessary between the tripping thresholds to ensure selectivity. To improve the selectivity performance or provide selectivity when tripping thresholds are close or similar, time-based or logic selectivity should be implemented.

Nevertheless, delaying the tripping of a SCCB is possible but it has an impact on the semiconductor sizing and thus on the cost and footprint of the breaker. To damp the di/dt and avoid semiconductors oversizing, some SCCB could embed an inductance. This inductance reduces the stress on the electronic components and could allow for a better selectivity between SCCBs.

5.1.4.4 Managing bidirectional fault currents

As DC systems are typically multi-source and loads can also contribute to the short-circuit current due to their capacitances, this can result in various protective devices tripping if standard (non-directional) protection is used as explained in Section 4.3 and illustrated in Figure 4.4 & Figure 4.5. It is thus essential to distinguish between faults on load-side (F1), i.e., in DC bus direction, where all incomer protections shall trip, and faults on source-side (F3) which requires only faulty incomer to trip.

The following four subsections present various protection strategies, some of which are still at the conceptual stage and have not yet been experimentally validated. The first two approaches use a fault directionality algorithm and achieve selectivity by introducing a delay in the operation of one SCCB. To ensure selectivity, the delayed SCCB's tripping time must be long enough to allow the other SCCB to clear the fault first. However, this delay should also be kept as short as possible to avoid oversizing the SCCB components.

1. Directional protection with time-based and/or current-based selectivity

As illustrated in Figure 5.8, one option is to systematically deploy directional protection which can distinguish between current flowing into the line (commonly referred to as "forward direction", noted

FW) or into the bus (commonly referred to as “reverse direction”, noted RV) and have dedicated settings for this direction. For example, a time-delay Δt can be added to “reverse direction” protection, allowing instantaneous “forward direction” protection to clear the fault.

The faulty incomer SCCB would trip instantaneously in FW for faults on the source side. A time-delay Δt is set in RV for faults located in the DC network, providing selectivity with the FW element. It can be noted that non-directional protections could replace the FW elements, provided that its time delay Δt is sufficiently long to guarantee selectivity with the RV element.

Figure 5.8: Directional & time-graded selectivity

2. Directional protection with Logic-based selectivity

As illustrated in Figure 5.9, when a fault occurs on a source side, incomer SCCB trip instantaneously in FW direction and send a blocking or delaying order to the RV element of other source’s SCCB. Again, it can be noted that non-directional protections could take place of the RV elements, being inhibited by the FW element.

To implement this type of system, ultra-fast communication (in the microsecond range) is required. Standard communication protocols are not capable of achieving such performance, which is why proprietary solutions are currently necessary.

Figure 5.9: Directional & logic selectivity

3. Centralized Bus Capacitor

As illustrated in Figure 5.10 a supercapacitor is added to the main DC busbar. The circuit is equipped with an anti-return diode to avoid charging the capacitor from the grid and a fuse for self-protection. The size of bus capacitor is much larger than the converter's DC capacitor. When a fault occurs, large current discharges from the bus-capacitor to the fault, allowing rapid switching off of SCCB. As the tripping time is fast, the capacitor will not discharge much, reducing the constraints for recharging it.

The presence of large capacitor on DC bus brings out the directionality required and enhance the stability of the system voltage. However, the complexities introduced by the pre-charge requirements, circuit self-protection and component lifetime shall be analysed for effective implementation.

Note: this approach could also be used to improve fault detection and selectivity with conventional protection schemes.

Figure 5.10: Centralized bus capacitor

4. Bidirectional surge-less SCCB

The solution presented in Figure 5.11 is similar to the third option but offers intrinsic directional selectivity thanks to the capacitor which is integrated inside the SCCB. The capacitor in the SCCB the closest to the fault discharges into the fault, the breaker trips and isolates the faulty part from the network.

Note: The bidirectionality can be performed in one device or with two unidirectional devices at both cable-ends if the circuit itself should permit bidirectional power flow under normal conditions.

Figure 5.11: Bidirectional surge-less SCCB

A simplified architecture of such surge-less SCCB is provided in Figure 5.12.

To better understand the operation principle, a fault on the load side (F2) is used to illustrate the role of the embedded capacitor:

- On the source side, the capacitor stabilizes voltage and absorbs inductive energy during faults.
- On the load side, it initially discharges into the fault, allowing its detection.

However, long cables may dampen this discharge, potentially preventing SCCB activation.

Figure 5.12: Bidirectional (a) and unidirectional (b) surge-less SCCB

5.1.4.5 Concluding overview of Semiconductor Circuit-Breaker-based protection scheme

Depending on the design architecture and available features offered by the SCCB technology in use, the main conclusions on the performance of the SCCB-based protection are summed up as follows:

- Ultra-fast tripping- within a range of microseconds to a few tens of microseconds – is a key advantage that makes SCCBs particularly well-suited for protecting LVDC systems equipped with non-current-limiting converters. Thanks to its extremely fast response time, the SCCB can operate before the converter's internal protection mechanisms, thereby ensuring selectivity and effective fault management within DC networks.
- The SCCB fast time response could be a good solution to limit the voltage drop during a fault avoiding the triggering of converters Undervoltage (UV) protection across the network.
- As SCCB technology is under development, a wide variety of design architectures are being developed. While early implementations lacked directional protection capabilities, emerging topologies offer promising solutions for achieving bidirectional selectivity and reducing the risk of nuisance tripping caused by switching overvoltages.

5.2 Managing selectivity in LVDC system with limiting converters

As mentioned in Section 4.1, limiting converters have inherent DC current limiting feature provided by their control system. In the event of a fault, if their FRT capability allows this operation for a certain duration, it could become possible to explore, not only SCCB-based protection, but also the electro-mechanical or hybrid protection technologies which take longer time to clear faults.

In this Chapter several assumptions are made:

- Source converters are current-limiting and capable of supplying short-circuit current for a duration sufficient to allow SCHCB or EMCB devices to clear a fault.
- Undervoltage protections on both source and load converters, if present, are compatible with the FRT characteristics mentioned above. Load converters must have enough energy storage to withstand a deep voltage drop and allow time for the SCHCB or EMCB to operate.
- The peak current resulting from capacitor discharge can be safely handled by the equipment of the system or limited by the converters themselves.

If one of these conditions are not fulfilled, the reader shall refer to the solutions proposed in Section 5.1 which are based on SCCBs, as conventional protections should not be able to guarantee total selectivity. Basically, the main principle in this Chapter is to rely on the Fault Ride Through capability of source and load converters to propose innovative solutions with conventional protections and SCHCB.

5.2.1 Fuse-based protection scheme

With fault-limiting converters, it is a challenge to guarantee the protection of a LVDC network with fuses, even before considering selectivity. One of the main limitations arises from the fact that LVDC converters designed with current-limiting behaviour, typically restrict their short-circuit current output to only 1.2 or 1.5 times the rated current (I_n). This level of current is often insufficient to blow a fuse or to clear the fault before the converter stops (few hundreds milliseconds).

Unlike electronic tripping units, fuses offer no adjustability, making it impossible to fine-tune protection settings or adapt to varying system conditions. As a result, fault detection and reliable protection cannot always be guaranteed. A detailed protection study must be conducted case by case to determine whether the fuse can operate correctly under both minimum and maximum prospective short-circuit currents (I_{sc}). This feasibility depends heavily on factors such as system capacitance and fault loop impedance, which can further reduce the available fault current.

Additionally, fuses are inherently non-directional, making them unsuitable for applications requiring directional selectivity in complex or bidirectional LVDC networks.

A potential solution to improve both protection and selectivity could be to add capacitance in the system as presented Section 5.1.4.4 “3- Centralized bus capacitor”.

5.2.2 Semiconductor Circuit-Breaker-based protection scheme

The analysis and conclusions presented in Section 5.1.4 are applicable to the LVDC systems with limiting converters.

5.2.3 EMCB-based or SCHCB-based protection scheme

As explained in [1], existing EMCBs and SCHCBs offer have slower response time than SCCBs. But provided that the converters are able to provide a short-circuit current and remain connected during a short duration (few hundred milliseconds), SCHCB or EMCB could be used to protect effectively an LVDC network, as it can be done in AC microgrids.

Indeed, SCHCB or EMCB can interrupt fault current during the converter current-limiting phase if the converter can remain connected during a fault for a certain duration. This calls for the development of new LVDC breakers and more specifically new LVDC electronic tripping units, improving adjustability of time-current characteristics and integrating advanced features such as directional overcurrent protection, also required for SCCBs.

To manage both protection and selectivity the converter manufacturer should describe the behaviour of the converter in fault conditions: short-circuit current limited and maximum duration before the converter stops.

Faults F1, F2, and F3 as described in Figure 5.1 are briefly discussed hereafter:

Fault F1 on the DC bus: all incomers protection shall detect and clear the fault before the converter stops to isolate the faulty bus. This is achievable because the converter does not include a fast-acting protection mechanism, unlike non-limiting converters.

Fault F2 on a feeder: selectivity between feeders and incomer protection can be achieved by time-based selectivity as described in Section 3.1.1. For faster fault clearance, logic-based selectivity could also be applied (refer to section 0).

Fault F3 on the source incomer: selectivity between incomers can be achieved classically thanks to directional protections associated with time-based or logic-based selectivity as described and illustrated in Sections 3.1.4 and 5.1.4.4.

In all cases, it is essential to verify the coordination between the response time of EMCBs or SCHCB protection and the FRT performance of the load converters, in order to prevent load disconnection prior to fault clearance. Eventually, given the fault-limiting capability of the power supply converters, they could recharge smoothly the load converters input capacitors after the fault is cleared.

Additional notes about protection

To effectively detect the low fault currents generated by current-limiting converters, it may be necessary to implement advanced protection schemes such as Voltage-Dependent Overcurrent Protection (ANSI 51V). The same applies to SCCBs when fault detection during the capacitive discharge phase cannot be guaranteed.

Conclusion

With current-limiting converter technology, protection schemes based on EMCBs or SCHCBs could ensure selectivity in LVDC multisource applications. When both source and load converters have FRT capability, and system components can withstand the peak capacitive discharge current, conventional selectivity principles could be applied. Achieving this requires the development of new electromechanical devices equipped with electronic tripping-units and advanced protection algorithms, such as directional protection combined with time-based and logic-based selectivity strategies.

5.2.4 Communication based – centralized protection scheme

If faults can be cleared during the converter's current limiting phase, another alternative is to adopt the centralized approach. The centralized protection is fully aligned and integrated with centralized energy management for LVDC system.

Figure 5.13: Centralized protection system

The principle of the centralized protection scheme, as illustrated in Figure 5.13, consists of monitoring electrical parameters in DC network such as the amplitude and sign of currents, voltages, their derivatives. With extensive measurement points, this approach offers good observability on operational conditions. It makes accessible more advanced protection algorithms which can be implemented in the edge control allowing efficient fault detection and localization. Circuit breakers are then remotely controlled to isolate the faulted part and maintain normal operation in the healthy parts.

To setup a protection scheme based on the centralized approach, the main requirements are listed as follows:

- Source converters remain connected in current-limiting mode, at least during the centralized protection response time (including measurement synchronization, communication, ...), typically expected within 10 ms.
- The load converters have adequate FRT capability and remain connected throughout the fault duration until clearance.
- The edge control may integrate numerous advanced protection principles, with at least overcurrent directional protection. Differential (Zone) protection could also be implemented.
- In the centralized protection system, backup protection is mandatory at incomers and load feeders locally to protect the system in cases of failures of edge control or communication interfaces. Voltage-dependent overcurrent protection (ANSI 51V), as already mentioned in Section 5.2.3, is the most commonly used principle for backup protection.

A centralized protection strategy is likely not suitable for SCCBs, as they will have to withstand the high peak current caused by the capacitive discharge of converters when communication and protection processing delays could be too long.

5.3 Managing selectivity in LVDC for earth fault protection

The same approach as explained in Section 3.2 can be adopted, with the technological constraints underlined in Section 5.1 and Section 5.2.

However, for protective devices tripping on capacitive fault currents, an additional constraint has to be taken into account: unlike pole-to-pole short-circuits, earth faults are generally more or less impedant, with no precise data on the impedance value. This impedance may have a non negligible influence on the shape of the capacitive current discharge, modifying the tripping time.

6 Conclusion

Selectivity is a key factor in ensuring service continuity and resilience in LVDC networks, particularly in multisource architectures with extensive integration of power converters. This document presents a comprehensive methodology for analyzing and designing selective protection schemes tailored to the specific constraints of LVDC systems.

The study first presents the conventional selectivity principles used in AC systems—such as time-based, current-based, energy-based, logic, directional, and differential selectivity—and assesses their relevance to LVDC applications, especially when facing the dynamic behaviour of non-limiting converters and bidirectional fault currents. It also emphasizes the risks of sympathetic tripping and the challenges posed by current oscillations and switching overvoltages.

Among the technologies assessed, SCCBs emerge as the most promising solution to meet the speed and coordination requirements imposed by converters lacking FRT capability. Their ability to interrupt faults within microseconds enables selectivity to be achieved before the activation of internal converter protections.

In cases where converters are current-limiting and offer sufficient FRT capability, more conventional devices such as EMCBs or SCHCBs may be considered, provided their characteristics align with the fault profiles and required response times. Advanced strategies such as directional protection, logic-based selectivity, and centralized architectures offer promising perspectives for improving selectivity in complex networks. However, their implementation requires further technological developments, particularly in ultra-fast communication and device coordination.

This methodology once again highlights a fundamental principle: a robust protection system is always a compromise between the performance of converters and protection devices. This balance is especially critical when aiming to ensure both selectivity and continuity of service in complex, multi-source LVDC networks.

Whilst this study provides a solid foundation for the design and validation of protection systems in future LVDC networks, it is important to note that many of the enabling technologies are still emerging or under development. As the field evolves, new solutions are likely to appear in the coming years.

7 Applicable standards

- **IEC 60269-1: 2024:** Low-voltage fuses. Part 1: General requirements
- **IEC 60898-1: 2015 / COR1: 2015/ AMD1: 2019:** Electrical accessories. Circuit-breakers for over-current protection for household and similar installations. Part 1: Circuit-breakers for a.c. operation
- **IEC 60947-1: 2020 / AC1:2022:** Low-voltage switchgear and controlgear – Part 1: General rules
- **IEC 60947-2: 2024:** Low-voltage switchgear and controlgear – Part 2: Circuit-breakers
- **IEC 61008-1: 2024:** Residual current operated circuit-breakers without integral over-current protection for household and similar uses (RCCBs). Part 1: General rules
- **IEC 61009-1: 2024:** Residual current operated circuit-breakers with integral over-current protection for household and similar uses (RCBOs). Part 1: General rules
- **IEC TR 61912-2: 2009:** Low-voltage switchgear and controlgear. Over-current protective devices. Part 2: Selectivity under over-current conditions
- **IEEE C37.234-2021:** IEEE Guide for Protective Relay - Applications to Power System Buses

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8 References

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